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**THE EFFECT OF REDD+ ON COMMUNITY FOREST GOVERNANCE PRACTICES
AND RURAL LIVELIHOODS IN ZAMBIA: THE CASE OF NYIMBA DISTRICT,
EASTERN PROVINCE**

**DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY (PhD) GOVERNANCE AND REGIONAL
INTEGRATION**

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Yaoundé, Cameroon
March, 2025

**THE EFFECT OF REDD+ ON COMMUNITY FOREST GOVERNANCE
PRACTICES AND RURAL LIVELIHOODS IN ZAMBIA: THE CASE OF NYIMBA
DISTRICT, EASTERN PROVINCE**

A Dissertation submitted to the Institute of Governance, Humanities and Social Sciences of the Pan African University in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Governance and Regional Integration.

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DEDICATION

To my late parents, John Kondowe and Petronella Chavula Kondowe (May they continue to rest in peace).

STATEMENT OF AUTHOR

I, **Kondowe Jonah**, hereby declare that, to the best of my knowledge, all the information contained in this Dissertation is information generated out of my own hard work, and that it has not been produced or duplicated for any purpose before. All the sources used in this work were authentic and have been duly acknowledged. I submit this document in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) from the Pan African University.

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Jonah Kondowe is an accomplished Research and Policy Analyst with a specialized focus on Development Finance, Climate Change, Political Economy, Agriculture, and Rural Development. With an interdisciplinary academic background in Development Studies and Demography, Jonah's professional work is deeply rooted in contributing to global efforts aimed at sustainable development and climate adaptation, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa.

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His combination of fieldwork, academic rigor, and practical experience positions him as a leading expert in the intersection of development finance, climate change, and rural livelihoods, with a particular focus on leveraging data-driven insights for social change and environmental sustainability. Jonah is committed to harnessing research to support informed policy-making and sustainable development practices across Africa.

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between REDD+ initiatives, community forest governance practices, and rural livelihoods in Zambia. With a focus on the Luangwa Game Management Areas in Nyimba District, the research aims to determine the effect of REDD+ on community forest management group (CFMG) governance and the resulting impacts on local livelihoods. The study reviews the evolution of forest governance in Zambia and situates REDD+ within this context, highlighting both its potential benefits and challenges. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research integrates socio-economic, ecological, and governance data, drawn from surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions with community members, government officials, and implementing partners. Findings suggest that while REDD+ has positively influenced governance practices, promoting transparency, participation, and capacity-building among CFMGs, it also uncovered challenges related to resource distribution, equity, and governance accountability. Additionally, REDD+ has contributed to improved livelihood outcomes in areas such as access to social and physical capital, though disparities remain at the household level. The study concludes with recommendations for policymakers, community members, implementing partners, and funders, emphasizing the importance of inclusive, transparent, and context-sensitive governance practices. Further research is needed to explore the broader effects of REDD+ across regions and to understand how cultural traditions may impact project success. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of how REDD+ can support sustainable forest management while improving rural livelihoods in Zambia.

Keywords: REDD+, community forest governance, rural livelihoods, carbon financing, rural development

RÉSUMÉ

Cette étude explore la relation entre les initiatives REDD+, les pratiques de gouvernance forestière communautaire et les moyens de subsistance ruraux en Zambie. En se concentrant sur les zones de gestion de gibier de Luangwa dans le district de Nyimba, la recherche vise à déterminer l'impact de REDD+ sur la gouvernance des groupes de gestion forestière communautaire (CFMG) et les conséquences sur les moyens de subsistance locaux. L'étude passe en revue l'évolution de la gouvernance forestière en Zambie et situe REDD+ dans ce contexte, en mettant en lumière à la fois ses avantages potentiels et ses défis. En utilisant une approche méthodologique mixte, la recherche intègre des données socio-économiques, écologiques et de gouvernance, recueillies à partir d'enquêtes, d'entretiens et de discussions de groupe avec des membres de la communauté, des responsables gouvernementaux et des partenaires de mise en œuvre. Les résultats suggèrent que, bien que REDD+ ait influencé positivement les pratiques de gouvernance en favorisant la transparence, la participation et le renforcement des capacités au sein des CFMG, des défis liés à la répartition des ressources, à l'équité et à la responsabilité en matière de gouvernance ont également été identifiés. De plus, REDD+ a contribué à améliorer les résultats en matière de moyens de subsistance dans des domaines tels que l'accès au capital social et physique, bien que des disparités subsistent au niveau des ménages. L'étude se conclut par des recommandations pour les décideurs politiques, les membres de la communauté, les partenaires de mise en œuvre et les bailleurs de fonds, soulignant l'importance de pratiques de gouvernance inclusives, transparentes et sensibles au contexte. D'autres recherches sont nécessaires pour explorer les effets plus larges de REDD+ à travers les régions et pour comprendre comment les traditions culturelles peuvent influencer le succès des projets. Cette étude contribue à une compréhension plus approfondie de la manière dont REDD+ peut soutenir la gestion durable des forêts tout en améliorant les moyens de subsistance ruraux en Zambie.

Mots-clés : REDD+, gouvernance forestière communautaire, moyens de subsistance ruraux, financement carbone, développement rural.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ADCs	Area Development Committees
ART- TREES	Architecture for REDD+ Transactions – The REDD+ Environmental Excellence Standard
BCP	Biocarbon Partners
CBNRM	Community Based Natural Resources Management
CCB	Community Climate Biodiversity
CFUGs	Community Forest User Groups
CRBs	Community Resources Boards
CBF	Community Based Forestry
CCs	Conservation Concessions
COMACO	Community Markets for Conservation
COP	Conference of the Parties
CORSIA	Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
DFID	Department for International Development
EUTR	The EU Timber Regulation
EL	Emission Levels
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nation
FCPF	Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF)
FD	Forest Department
FG	Forest Governance
FGRMs	Forestry Grievance Redress Mechanisms

FIP	Forest Investment Program
FLEGT	Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade
FREL	Forest Reference Emission Levels
GCF	Green Climate Fund
GGC	Green Gigaton Challenge
GHGs	Green House Gasses
GMAs	Game Management Areas
GRZ	Government of Zambia
ITs	Indigenous Territories
ITMOs	Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
IUFRO	International Union of Forest Research Organizations
IPLCs	Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities
IRP	International Recovery Platform
JFM	Joint Forest Management
LEAF	Lowering Emissions by Accelerating Finance
MLG	Multi-Level Governance
MLNR	Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
MTA	Ministry of Tourism and Arts
NbS	Nature based Solutions
NFMS	National Forest Monitoring Systems
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
NJP	National Joint Programme

NWFPs	Non-wood Forest Products
DNPW	Department of National Parks and Wildlife
PAs	Protected Areas
RBP s	Resource-based Payments
RCD	Rural Community Development
REDD+	Reduction of Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SFM	Sustainable Forest Management
SLF	Sustainable Livelihoods Framework
S.I	Statutory Instrument
SIS	Safeguard Information System
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VAGs	Village Action Groups
VCM	Voluntary Carbon Markets
VCS	Verified Carbon Standards
VCU	Verified Carbon Units
VPAS	Voluntary Partnership Agreements
WDCs	Ward Development Committees
ZAFFICO	Zambia Forests and Forestry Industries Corporation

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The community forest management (CFM) approach has gained global recognition as a vital mechanism for achieving sustainable forest management while empowering communities and enhancing rural economies through long-term socio-economic and ecological benefits (Arts et al., 2023). This approach is particularly relevant in developing countries, especially in tropical regions where state institutions are often weak or absent in remote forested areas. CFM currently covers approximately 600 million hectares of forest, making it a significant contributor to the UN's global forest goals on sustainable forest management (Arts, 2021).

Since the 1980s, there has been a global shift toward forest management strategies that empower forest-adjacent communities to manage and, where possible, own the forests in their vicinity (Agrawal & Ostrom, 2001). This change stemmed from the realization that local communities can be effective forest managers when properly supported. Recognizing them as managers or owners of nearby forests not only incentivizes conservation but also enhances their livelihoods (Sunderlin et al., 2008). Many tropical countries have adopted community-based forest conservation initiatives, granting local communities the power to co-manage or own forests. These initiatives have taken various forms, including Joint Forest Management (JFM), Community Forestry (CF), Participatory Forest Management (PFM), Collaborative Forest Management (CFM), and Community-based Forest Management (CBFM) (Mawa, 2021).

Moreover, CFM programs are instrumental in addressing poverty alleviation by creating regulations and institutional frameworks that directly benefit marginalized and poor communities (Gilmour, 2016). As forest are estimated to directly support the livelihoods of over 500,000 indigenous people and 1.3 billion individuals globally, with households heavily reliant on forests for subsistence needs (e.g., fuelwood, wild foods, medicinal herbs) (Chao, 2012). It is thus widely acknowledged that the success of conservation efforts depends on the active involvement of communities living in or near forested areas (Lucungu et al., 2022). Such projects reduce poverty by empowering communities, enhancing forest conditions, and offering sustainable livelihoods (Charnley & Poe, 2007; Maryudi et al., 2012).

In addition to such developments, in 2007 (and again in 2021) the international community through the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES - IPBES, 2018;

2019) stressed the importance of forests in regulating our global climate and in our fight against climate change. By absorbing greenhouse gases (GHG), forests are essential for reducing climate change; nevertheless, their depletion and loss also contribute to climate change by releasing CO₂ and other GHGs (Pörtner et al., 2021). As one of the planet's most biologically varied ecosystems, forests make up about 31% of the planet's surface. On many sizes, they provide vital ecosystem functions and priceless natural resources. Thus, the Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) has been formalized in the context of climate emergency during the last decade.

Internationally there is emphasis for REDD+ projects to have socio economic non-carbon advantages, as highlighted in the international policy frameworks such as the Paris Agreement, the Warsaw Framework, and the Cancún Safeguards. UNFCCC has put in place safeguards information systems (SIS) for countries to measure these non-carbon benefits, which include advancements in economic development, social well-being, and biodiversity. Projects that show co-benefits in areas like women empowerment, social inclusion, and job development are encouraged by the Green Climate Fund. As such, 'Community-based forest management (CBFM),' projects have gained further recognition as crucial stakeholders in forest conservation, with approximately one-third of the world's forest area covered by such projects (Parrotta et al., 2022).

In Zambia, the evolution of forest governance has shifted significantly from the colonial era to the present. During colonial rule, forest management was split between crown land, managed by the British, and native reserves, governed under customary law by chiefs. After Zambia's independence in 1964, the state assumed control over crown land, while customary land management persisted. In the 1990s, Zambia began to recognize the limitations of centralized governance, leading to the adoption of participatory approaches such as Joint Forest Management (JFM), highlighted in the 1998 National Forest Policy (Chikulo, 2009). Despite efforts to implement JFM through pilot projects, stagnation resulted from institutional challenges, unclear benefit-sharing mechanisms, and insufficient legal frameworks (Mfunze, 2011). The 2014 and 2015 policy reforms, notably the Forest Act of 2015, marked a significant shift by empowering local communities with legal rights over forest resources, including timber and eco-tourism, under Community Forest Management (CFM). These reforms were further solidified with the 2018 Community Forest Regulations (Matakala et al., 2015). However,

challenges related to governance structures, overlapping land rights, and deforestation driven by rural livelihoods remain persistent (Mason-Case, 2011).

In this context, the REDD+ initiative has emerged as a central framework to combat deforestation and forest degradation by improving participation and governance in Zambia. REDD+ aims to secure land and carbon rights for local communities, addressing the historical exclusion of these groups from forest management benefits (Springate-Baginski and Wollenberg, 2010). The *Zambian National REDD+ Strategy*, developed with UN-REDD support, integrates both national and local efforts, focusing on Participatory Forest Management (PFM) and Community Forest Management (CFM) to involve local communities in sustainable forest use (Matakala et al., 2015). The strategy incorporates innovative mechanisms such as Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) to incentivize conservation, alongside legal reforms aimed at balancing traditional land governance with formal management structures (Nansikombi et al., 2020; GRZ, 2018).

In light of this, this study intends to investigate community forest management governance practices and their impact on Zambian rural lives. The study also looks at how REDD+ has affected livelihood outcomes for people that depend on forests and community forest management governance.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In Zambia, despite efforts to enhance forest governance practices, persistent power inequalities limit the meaningful participation of forest-dependent communities in decision-making processes (Adhikari et al., 2016). Because of this, there are worries that the wealthy may control the co-management mechanisms that are now in place, which would perpetuate social inequality and make it more difficult to obtain pro-poor outcomes in participatory forest governance (Schreckenberget al., 2006).

While participatory forest governance holds potential for improving livelihood security and reducing poverty, there is growing concern that its effectiveness may be compromised when governance structures are not inclusive and fail to address the needs of marginalized communities (Adhikari et al., 2016). Furthermore, the focus on monetary assessments of provisioning services in studies on livelihood benefits from community-based forest management (CBFM) often overlooks the broader range of livelihood impacts, thereby limiting

our understanding of the full benefits of CBFM to local communities (Lakerveld et al., 2015; Matiku et al., 2013; Ameha et al., 2014).

Moreover, while some community forest management groups (CFMGs) demonstrate effective governance systems for achieving conservation goals and improving livelihoods, others face challenges in this regard (Zimmerman et al., 2001; Andersson et al., 2014; Ostrom, 1990; Barrett et al., 2001). These challenges are compounded by historical constraints and power dynamics that have hindered the progress of community-based natural resource management (CBNRM) initiatives in Zambia (Gibson & Marks, 1995; Gibson, 1999; Lubilo & Child, 2010; Lindsey et al., 2014).

In addition to the complexities introduced by initiatives like REDD+, the sustainability of forest governance in Zambia is further challenged by the need to align local communities' interests with global conservation initiatives while ensuring equitable distribution of benefits (Nthenge, 2019). The nuances of REDD+'s impact on local governance systems and livelihoods must be understood in order to optimize its impact on forest conservation and community well-being (Davis et al., 2020). How well REDD+ initiatives incorporate local knowledge and involve communities in decision-making processes determines how successful they are at combating deforestation and forest degradation also need to be understood as such information is lacking in literature.

Due to ongoing agricultural land expansions into forested regions and the widespread use of charcoal for burning, Zambia's Eastern province has seen a significant decrease in forest cover. In response, the government has launched REDD+ programs to promote forest regeneration and boost agricultural output in coordination with its implementation partners. However, the degree to which these programs include substantial compromises for the livelihoods of the affected people and their firsthand knowledge is still not well examined in academic literature. Nyimba District was chosen as the focus of this study because it is at the forefront of REDD+ implementation activities and is currently facing increased threats of more forest loss.

1.3 Research Questions

Main Question

What is the effect of REDD+ on the governance practices of CFMGs and rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia?

Specific Questions

1. What is the link between governance practices among CFMGs and rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia?
2. How has REDD+ enabled good Community Forest Governance Practices in Zambia?
3. What contribution has REDD+ had on the rural livelihood outcomes among CFMGs in Zambia?
4. What are governance challenges faced by CFMGs under REDD+ and their associated livelihood outcomes in Zambia?

1.4 Research Objectives

Main Objective

To establish the effect of REDD+ on governance practices among CFMGs and rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia.

Specific Objectives are to:

1. examine the relationship between Community Forest Governance Practices and rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia.
2. determine the effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance practices in Zambia.
3. investigate the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihood outcomes among CFMGs in Zambia.
4. determine the challenges in governance faced by CFMGs in Zambia under the REDD+ implementation and their associated rural livelihood outcomes.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

1. There is significant association between governance practices among CFMGS and livelihood outcomes in Zambia.
2. REDD+ positively affects Community Forest Governance Practices in Zambia.
3. REDD+ positively affects rural livelihood outcomes among CFMGs in Zambia.
4. The governance challenges being faced by CFMGs in Zambia under REDD+ implementation affect rural livelihood outcomes negatively.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The findings of the study provided insights into establishing the link between the current governance practices of community forest management groups and rural livelihoods in Zambia. It also addressed the impact of recent developments such as REDD+ on local forest governance and livelihoods. A literature gap existed in Zambia regarding the governance of local institutions such as community forest management groups and their associated outcomes on forest conservation and livelihoods. The proposed research aimed to fill this gap and enhance understanding of participatory forest governance through empirical evidence. The outcomes of the research were intended to benefit researchers, students, policy- and decision-makers in the forest sector, and environmental NGOs in Zambia. Additionally, it contributed to assessing progress towards achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals, the African Union Agenda 2063, and the National Vision 2030 of Zambia. Finally, reforms were proposed to enhance the governance practices of community forest management groups.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study in investigating the link between the governance of community forest management groups and rural livelihoods; and the effect of REDD+ thereof, is done in terms of scientific scope, temporal scope, and spatial scope as explained below.

1.7.1 Scientific Scope

This study takes on an interdisciplinary approach from fields such as ecology, governance and rural development. These key variables will be studied within broader confines of theory. The theories adopted for the study include the forest governance decentralization theory; the common resource pool theory; and the sustainable livelihoods theory.

1.7.2 Temporal Scope

The temporal scope of the study was 15 years (2008 to 2024). The year 2008 marked the beginning point because that was when Zambia embraced the REDD+ strategy as a means to strengthen its efforts to tackle the drivers of deforestation. The year 2024 marked the terminal point because it was during the 2023 to 2024 period when the cross-sectional data was expected to be collected under the ongoing REDD+ programs in forest communities. The year 2023 was also significant in this study because the researcher attempted to evaluate the influence of policy implementation on community forest governance practices under REDD+, which was linked to livelihoods in the selected community natural resource management schemes related to forests. The study aimed to capture the current circumstances to establish associations between the identified variables; hence, it adopted an evaluative, cross-sectional study design.

1.7.3 Spatial Scope

The study was based in Nyimba district of Eastern Province, Zambia. Eastern province has over the 20 years seen a reduction in forest cover owing to deforestation as a total of 156,000 hectares was lost between 2000 and 2014. The implementation of REDD+ under the Luangwa Community Forest Program stretches from Chinyunyu, nyimba, Lundazi and Mfuwe in Game Management Areas. The current study is based in Nyimba because of the centrality of the location and more diverse views are obtainable.

1.8 Limitations

The key limitations of the study are categorized into generalizability, social desirability bias, , and temporal constraints.

Generalizability: Findings from the study may not be applicable to other contexts or populations due to unique characteristics and circumstances.

Social Desirability Bias: The research acknowledges that not all participants would respond in a socially acceptable manner, leading to overestimation or underestimation of certain behaviors or attitudes. The triangulation technique (using different tools of data collection) was used to reduce this problem.

Temporal constraints: The findings of the study are limited to the temporal scope in which the study was conducted. Thus, it may not capture changes or developments occurring before or after the study period.

1.9 Definition of Key Terms

1.9.1 Community Forest Governance

The current study seeks to assess community forestry–level governance in Zambia. Community forest (CF) governance refers to the following: “Community level management and decision-making that is undertaken by, with, or on behalf of a community, by a group of community stakeholders. The focus on ‘community’ rather than on a corporation, organization, local government or the public sector is the distinguishing feature of community governance vis a vis [sic] other forms of governance” (Totikidis et al. 2005). Management by contrast to governance refers to the processes of decision making, coordination and resource deployment that occur within a given institutional setting, assuming no change in rules and norms (Hatfield-Dodds et al., 2007). Identifying desirable strategies (by applying skills and knowledge) and putting them into practice through physical actions and technology are both aspects of management that are closely related to leading or directing effort (see Burris et al. 2005). In line with this, "management" almost always refers to circumstances in which one agent or group of agents has direct control over resources and the behavior of agents, as opposed to circumstances in which one agent or group of agents has influence or "indirect control" over the decisions or behaviors of others (which would generally refer to governance instead of management) (Hatfield-Dodds et al., 2007).

1.9.2 Forest Governance Practices

Governance refers to the institutional arrangements which shape actors’ decisions and behavior, including the exercise of authority within groups or organizations (such as firms or nations) (Hatfield-Dodds et al., 2007). The current study focuses on the governance of community forest management groups. Hence these are the "norms, processes, instruments, people, and organizations that control how people interact with forests" (Kishor and Rosenbaum, 2012). An effective forest governance also includes public participation in decision-making relating to forest management.

1.9.3 Rural Livelihoods

A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets (including both material and social resources) and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stress and shocks and maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, while not undermining the natural resource base (Chambers & Conway,

1991). In this regard, rural livelihood comprises of capabilities, assets and activities of a specific sub-section of the population, the rural section.

1.9.4 REDD+

Reducing emissions through deforestation and forest degradation refers to initiative aimed at providing financial incentives to reduce gas emissions from forest lands in developing countries. It's relevance to the current study focusing on community forest governance is based on the fact that it recognizes that governance weaknesses hinder sustainable forest management especially when institutional coordination and collaboration and the regulatory frameworks are weak. Hence in this study, REDD+ activities are hypothesized to have an effect on both governance practices and livelihood outcomes in Zambia.

1.10 Organization of the Study

The current chapter is the introduction of the study and it has highlighted the background to the study, significance, scope and limitations of the study. The subsequent chapter, is the literature review and it has presented the conceptual review, theoretical framework, empirical literature and the research gap. The third chapter of the study highlights the research methodology of the study and it has described the study area, research design, target population, sampling techniques, ethical considerations, data collection and the measurement of the variables. Chapter four is the presentation and discussion of findings. Lastly chapter five is the conclusion and recommendations section of the study.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

This section is the review of literature on the topic. The first part of the reviews the conceptual framework of the study by reviewing major concepts, how they interlinked and an analysis of how they are applied to the current study; the second part reviews theories that provide a lens to study how the governance of forest management institutions are linked to rural livelihoods in Zambia; and the third part is a review of the various empirical studies that have been conducted on the effects among the identified variables.

2.1 Conceptual Review

This section is an analytical review of the concepts of the study. Concepts reviewed in this section include governance, forest governance, rural livelihoods.

2.1.1 Forest Governance Practices

Historically, people have associated governance with exercise of power by the government. Key components discussed by a number of authors, include actors, processes, and rules/structures (Mansourian, 2017; Larson and Petkova, 2011; Broekhoven et al., 2012; Giessen and Buttoud, 2014; Kishor and Rosenbaum, 2012).

A more thorough definition is provided by Larson and Petkova (2012), who define governance as the formal and informal institutions, rules/policies, power relations, and decision-making practices that govern how decisions are made (and who makes them) at different scales (global, national, and local). In this sense, it is possible to claim that the interplay of individuals, institutions, and processes that support decision-making is governance. According to FAO (2012), policy and institutional frameworks, planning and decision-making procedures, and implementation and compliance methods are the key ways that forest governance systems are conveyed.

Forests, in this study, refer to commodities given by a forest for direct consumption or commercial use, such as tree products and forage. Therefore, according to Giessen and Buttoud (2014), forest governance "involves all formal and informal, public and private regulatory structures, i.e. institutions consisting of rules/policies, norms, principles, and decision-making processes concerning forests, their utilization and their conservation, b) the interactions between public and private actors therein, and c) the effects of either on forests." A variety of qualities are considered to be essential components of good governance practice. These include accountability, fairness, effectiveness, efficiency, and participation (Ozinga 2012; FAO 2012).

An instance of "good forest governance" is one in which these characteristics support the decision-making processes linked to forests.

Also an important aspect of forest governance to be considered is that it includes a coherent set of laws and regulations, both within the forest sector and in other sectors that influence forest management; coherent implementation of these laws; the decision-making process regarding rules, laws and regulations; and clear mandates of, and arrangements between, different stakeholders (Lockwood, 2010). Thus, forest governance involves complex multi-level processes addressing deforestation and forest degradation problems through appropriate institutional arrangements (Mohammed et al., 2017).

Since it is challenging to address every aspect while upholding scientific rigor in a single study's methodology, the definition can be changed to reflect the pertinent elements (Giessen and Buttoud, 2014). Subsequently, the current study uses community forest management groups (CRMG, CFMG, CRBs) as institutions of implementation. Governance in this context will refer to the norms, processes and instruments, and how these affects how people interact with forests. Forest governance is about how decisions regarding forests are made, who makes them, and who participates in the process. It involves policy development and implementation in accordance with the needs of the different stakeholders and principles of sustainability, as well as monitoring, supervision and law enforcement (Kishor and Rosenbaum, 2012).

Forest governance is an important factor in reducing the risk of uncontrolled deforestation and improving livelihoods (White and Martin, 2002). It is also predicated upon mutually supportive and cooperative relationships between government, the private sector and civil society (FAO, 2011). Good forest governance practice requires clear and coherent policies, laws and regulations, consistent national development plans, traditional rights of indigenous peoples, local communities and forest users, quality implementation of laws, effective adjudication of forest disputes and protection of property rights (FAO, 2011 and World Bank, 2009).

Key elements of good forest governance include effective institutions, transparency, consistent and clear legislation, and secure forest tenure and access rights. Improving forest governance requires a systematic approach to identifying areas of weakness, devising and implementing suitable responses, monitoring results, continuing adaptation and learning to ensure progress (FAO, 2011). The governance practices at the level of community forest management include being investigated include Transparency, Participation, Accountability, Enforcement and Monitoring of laws, and capacity building.

Transparency: Transparency in forest management is essential for good governance and building trust among stakeholders. It requires access to information, timeliness, availability and comprehensibility of information, and a legal framework that supports public access to information (Davis, 2013). To enhance transparency, forest-related procurement rules should be properly implemented, corruption in forest revenue management must be reported, and all parties involved in cases of corruption must be prosecuted (UN, 1992).

Participation: Public participation in environmental decision-making is essential for ensuring environmental justice. The Forest Principles 1992 and 2007 ask states to promote and provide opportunities for the participation of interested parties in the development, implementation and planning of national forest policies. This process must be inclusive, voluntary, fair and transparent for all participants. Access to participation includes having a formal space for participation in relevant forums, using appropriate mechanisms to invite participation, ensuring an inclusive and open process, and taking gathered input into account. Public participation in forestry issues can increase public awareness, maximise benefits, and enhance social acceptance (FAO, 2000; and UN, 1992).

The UN Environment Programme's Guidelines for the Development of National Legislation on Access to Information, Public Participation and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters recommend norms and practices to achieve effective public participation. These include starting early, being proactive, making information available, being meaningful, having an opportunity to participate in review processes, participating in strategic policymaking and rulemaking, and providing resources and means for capacity building (UNEP, 2010). The Helsinki Process 1993 outlines criteria for public participation in forest management, including a legal regulatory framework, institutional mechanisms, economic policy framework, financial instruments, and informational means (Castañeda et al., 2011).

Accountability: Accountability involves two dimensions: answerability and enforcement, and requires decentralisation, transparency, governmental oversight mechanisms, and engagement of private and civil society actors in forest governance. Answerability refers to the obligation to provide information about decisions and actions and justify them to stakeholders and other overseeing entities. Enforcement requires sanctions and redress when the actor fails to meet its obligations (Castañeda et al., 2011). Accountability in forest management requires decentralisation in forest administration; transparency in timber concession and rights allocation; transparency in forest revenue management; ensuring the quality of governmental

oversight mechanisms; and engaging private and civil society actors in forest governance (Minang et al., 2017).

Enforcement and Monitoring of Laws: Proper enforcement of forest laws is essential for effective forest governance. International instruments such as the International Timber Agreement 2006 and the CBD's COP 9 Decision IX/5 on Forest Biodiversity emphasize the need for proper enforcement (UNEP, 2011). Forest monitoring helps to ensure policies are operating effectively by providing up-to-date information on the actual effects of policies and institutional practices (Van Bodegom et al., 2012).

Capacity Building: Capacity building is essential for effective forest governance, as it involves developing the ability of financial, human, technological, legal and institutional resources to perform a function. It includes developing technical, managerial and organisational skill, formulating, implementing and evaluating forest laws and policies, funding education and research, and building networks for communication and information exchange (Davis, 2013).

The suitability of rulemaking procedures and perceived fairness in light of local community preferences, requirements, and expectations might affect acceptance and fit of local governing institutions (Epstein et al., 2015). Additionally, local residents' perspectives might influence how local users view resource administration by revealing information about the social acceptability of environmental management and the legitimacy of local governance (Bennett, 2016). Local institutions with poor governance, which include things like lack of openness and exclusion from decision-making, may disenfranchise communities and lower support for conservation efforts. Positive opinions of local government may increase community support, enabling conservation programs to be successful over the long term (Bennett, 2016; de Koning et al., 2017).

Thus, understanding how local governance in CBFM and perceptions of local communities on the same influence local attitudes towards forest conservation when other known motivational factors for conservation particularly economic benefits are partially fulfilled can inform management interventions for improving and strengthening institutional governance for increased participation, legitimacy of institutions and successful outcomes in forest conservation.

2.1.2 Rural Livelihoods

As a key concept of the current study, a livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets (including both material and social resources) and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stress and shocks and maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, while not undermining the natural resource base. (Chambers & Conway, 1991).

Lasse (2001) denotes that a livelihood consists of the skills, possessions (stores, resources, claims, and access), and activities necessary for a means of subsistence. Furthermore, according to DFID (2000), a way of life is considered sustainable if it can withstand stresses and shocks, recover from them, and maintain or improve its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, all without depleting the base of natural resources. A person's basic needs are met through a variety of activities that make up their livelihood strategies.

According to Farrington et al. (2002), people use livelihood capitals resources to implement their livelihood strategies. Capitals are not merely an element of production; they also serve as a foundation for the ability to take action and, eventually, transform society (Morse & McNamara 2013). A household's level of livelihood is affected by both internal and external variables. The five different categories of capital that Carney (1998) identified are the internal factors. Human, natural, financial, physical, and social capital are among these capital categories. For instance, human capital refers to the quantity and caliber of labor that is accessible, whereas natural capital refers to the natural resources that can be used to generate income. Financial capital includes the financial resources required to support a living, whereas physical capital refers to the fundamental infrastructures and means of production. Social capital assets are a sign of a household's participation in social networks and activities for both political and economic objectives. Individual households' access to systems, such as the resource base, financial system, and organizations that produce these capital kinds, is reflected in the forms of capital that are available to them (DFID, 1999).

However, external variables play a role in who has access to these resources. The evolution of structures and procedures is a significant external factor (DFID, 1999). The structural framework, which includes laws, regulations, institutions, and governance, has an impact on how assets can be accessed, how they may be used, and the livelihood strategy that is employed (Soussa et al., 2000). These characteristics are dynamic in and of themselves, making livelihoods susceptible to rapid changes in condition and trends in these elements (DFID,

1999). These external factors are crucial in defining the fundamental structure and operation of livelihood systems. For instance, land, tenure, and forest laws are essential in determining entitlements and, consequently, access to land for cultivation. This, in turn, is essential in determining the overall structure of livelihoods in rural areas. Prices and price variability are also crucial for forest crops in any given season.

The livelihood idea emerged as a result of a change in how important players view rural development. To begin with, there are a variety of perspectives on how to collaborate on rural development. For instance, one concept has locals (the local community) taking the lead and acting as the development's primary beneficiaries throughout, with donors and the receiving nation's government serving only as facilitators. In a worst-case scenario, even if a development plan (project) chosen by locals is unfavourable in their eyes, a foreign donor and the government of a recipient country may decide not to intervene. As an alternative, if the proposed actions conflict with the organization's own policies, support may not be offered. In another scenario, where there is no time to wait for a beneficiary decision, it might be required for all development activities to be managed by external organizations.

Historically, top-down approaches have been the foundation of many rural development initiatives in Africa. Villagers have taken the lead in grass-roots development initiatives, which have evolved in part as a response to this historical practice. Donors are increasingly pushing for locals to get involved from the start of development, while yet maintaining the community nature of already-existing villages. Depending on the particular nation, area, or goal and nature of a project, the members of the core organization in this situation may vary. They might include traditional and religious village leaders chosen by locals while taking into account the social and cultural facets of village life (Scoones, 2009).

In light of these movements, the term "rural development" was employed to refer to the actions necessary to better and enrich people's lives. Rural development in this context refers to "a wide range of activities necessary for the betterment and enhancement of the lives of those who reside in rural, i.e. non-urban, areas rather than a single industry, such as "agricultural, forestry, and fisheries production. As a result, it became crucial to comprehend how people support their livelihoods in order to determine their needs. Depending on the natural conditions, social structure, including traditional system and religious background, level of development of economic infrastructure, state of access to finance, etc. of the subject villages for rural development, the primary means of subsistence in Africa may vary from one village to another.

Even within a single village, a villager's standard of living might differ greatly from one villager to another based on a variety of circumstances, including the availability of land and/or cattle, the size of farming operations, the location of the residence along a road, and access to the town's resources. In Africa, a village may have several distinct ways of making a living (Scoones, 2009).

Ellis (2000) stated that livelihood comprises the assets (human, social, financial, natural and physical capital), the activities (such as income generating activities) and the access to these (the rules, social norms and relations that determine the different ability of people to own, control, claim, or make use of resources) that together determine the living gained by an individual or a household. The linkage between five assets of pentagon, livelihood and community forestry is described below.

Natural (Environmental) capital: Natural capital, community forests have improved forest conditions and provided access to forest products. To better safeguard natural resources like NTFPs, animals, biodiversity, and water, community forestry management practices are being improved. Along with indirect advantages like nitrogen cycling and defense against soil erosion, these resources bring about direct income and well-being (DFID, 1999). With CFUGs maturing and regularizing harvesting and product distribution networks, forest use is now sustainable for both immediate and long-term demands (Pokharel and Nurse, 2004).

Physical capital: The livelihoods of the disadvantaged in rural areas are impacted by CFUG investments in community development initiatives and infrastructure. In many rural areas the required physical facilities are lacking, so in such cases the CFUGs are contributing to address the basic needs of villagers as prioritized by them (Paudel, 2011). By building paths, bridges, schools, and temples as part of community forestry projects, they help to provide basic necessities. According to a study conducted in the Baglung district, the community forest contributes significantly to physical capital overall (Poudel, 2006).

Human capital: To improve forest management and the means of subsistence for the poor, the district forest office (DFO) offers trainings and workshops on health, information, and labor skills to CFUG members. As a result, the ability of government employees, non-governmental organizations, and community people to mobilize and maintain community woodlands has increased. Indicators of success for CFUG operations include the participation of women (Pokharel and Suvedi, 2007). Enhancing the financial and human capital of communities in or around forest areas is necessary for sustainable management of forest resources. It is generally

agreed upon that in order to manage forest resources sustainably, actions for forest conservation must be combined with improvements to the human and financial resources of the local communities that reside in or close to forested areas (Shahbaz et al., 2012).

Social capital: The capacity of households and people to participate in local institutions as well as their increased understanding of the rights and obligations associated with ensuring a livelihood are both necessary for the development and extraction of social benefits. CFUGs are a new source of social capital for regional organizations that depend on citizen decision-making to function. CFUGs are offering a new forum for planning development and promoting social cohesion through the regional and national level (Pandey and Subedi, 2008).

Financial capital: By managing communal money, microcredit programs give people access to financial capital. CFUGs raise money through selling forest products, accepting donations, and using revolving funds. Additionally, they sell NTFPs, manage natural resources, and create eco-tourist and homestay destinations. Women, the impoverished, and individuals who have never borrowed money before prefer microcredit programs, which have nominal interest rates set by CFUGs. The CFUG fund should be used for small loans for profitable ventures like pig farming, according to Dev et al. (2003).

2.1.3 REDD+

Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation, Conservation, Enhancement of Carbon Stocks and Sustainable Forest Management (also known as REDD+) is a key outcome of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) aimed to reduce emissions from tropical deforestation and degradation in developing countries. Though different site-specific REDD+ initiatives took different institutional forms, the central goals remained constant: incentivize developing countries to protect and manage their forests through the issuance of payments for added carbon storage, as well as to improve conservation and sustainable forest management.

As a key concept of the current study, REDD+ is relevant because it offers solutions to community forest governance identified throughout the evolution of community forest governance globally. Plausible pathways suggested by the REDD+ framework includes users incentivized to protect their forests by security of property rights, control of elite capture, community engagement and empowerment, improved livelihoods and broader environmental justice (Lawlor et al 2013, Salerno et al 2021), acting, in Duchelle et al's (2017) sense, as positive incentives for behavioral and institutional change. To achieve social co-benefits

outlined in REDD+, many projects adopt or expand upon pre-existing community forest management (CFM), and include communities in the design and implementation stages of REDD+ (Vijge et al 2016, Sharma et al 2017, Erbaugh et al 2020). With the addition of co-benefits, REDD+ has the potential to produce triple-wins for climate, forests and forest-dependent communities.

An evolving feature of REDD+ interventions has been the provision of ‘non-carbon’ social and environmental co-benefits. Often aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (Milbank et al 2018), such co-benefits are typically aimed at reducing poverty, improving forest governance, empowering women, enhancing sustainable small-scale enterprise and protecting biodiversity (Duchelle et al 2019). Social co-benefits are increasingly emphasized in REDD+ interventions, both to safeguard communities against obvious abuses to economic and social wellbeing (e.g. Brown 2013, Frewer 2021) and to compensate for costs to communities associated with reduced forest clearance (Duchelle et al 2017).

To mitigate climate change, the reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation (REDD+) initiative was introduced in 2007 at the 13th Conference of Parties (Bali conference) and subsequently extended to include safeguards, incentives and co-benefits (Den Besten et al 2014). Tropical forests store roughly 25% (250 billion tons) of the planet’s terrestrial carbon - which combines with other gases to produce greenhouse gasses (GHGs). However, since 1990, more than 420 million hectares of forests have been Deforested, releasing carbon dioxide into the atmosphere and reducing the storage and sink capacity of the forests. REDD+ proposes a solution to halt/reduce deforestation that relies, among other things, on addressing the drivers of deforestation.

The primary objective of REDD is to provide financial incentives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from forest lands in developing countries. At the 2009 UN Climate Change Conference in Copenhagen (UNFCCC COP 15), REDD was renamed REDD+ to include “the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks in developing countries” in addition to avoiding deforestation and forest degradation. The thinking behind is that economic growth in developing countries inevitably depends on exploiting forests. Therefore, tropical countries that reduce their emissions from forests relative to a calculated reference level receive financial compensation thus creating an incentive to keep forests intact. Since the 2007 Climate Change Conference in Bali (UNFCCC COP13-CMP3), a number of initiatives were started to support countries preparing for a possible REDD

mechanism as part of a post-Kyoto international climate change regime. The UN-REDD programme has been developed as a collaborative partnership between FAO, UNDP and UNEP.

The essence of REDD+ to the current study is that it recognizes that since illegal forest activity is responsible for a significant proportion of deforestation and forest degradation, governance issues present challenges for successful SFM and REDD implementation. The implementation of REDD+ projects takes into cognizance most of these issues making them to have an effect on both community forest governance and livelihoods.

Because the loss of natural forests around the world contributes more to global emissions each year than the transportation industry does, reducing deforestation is a very cost-effective strategy to reduce emissions (Stern, 2007). According to REDD+, community forest management is a practical means of lowering emissions at a reasonable price (Skutsch et al., 2007). Community forestry has been recognized by the framework as the main contributor to the carbon stock. It is further predicted that the expansion of the community forestry program and the inclusion of the regime under the REDD+ mechanism, with successful participation can bring ecological and economic benefits to the community as well as the nation, have even been shown to have a high potential for benefit (Dhital, 2009).

The REDD+ strategies, such as increasing forest land and forest density and reducing deforestation and forest degradation, require effective forest governance and sustainable management systems of forest resources to be achieved (Pokharel and Baral, 2009). The community forest has emerged as a prospective location for rewards related to carbon reductions, where REDD+ also helps biodiversity and livelihoods. However, setting up such a mechanism to benefit both the credit buyer from the developed world and community forest organizations from underdeveloped nations, who would be among the potential sellers, was regarded as a difficult undertaking (Acharya et al., 2009). Currently, development partners seem to have assumed this challenge.

2.1.4 Operationalization of Variables

The identified variable of the study comprises of the variables, “forest governance practices, rural livelihoods and REDD+.”

2.1.4.1 Governance Practices

Effective governance of community forest management groups requires clear and coherent policy; legal, institutional and regulatory frameworks; transparent and accountable decision-making and institutions; and effective implementation, enforcement and compliance (Diets and Stern, 2008). Public participation in forestry is seen as a process that is inclusive with respect to interests, voluntary with respect to participation, and ideally fair and transparent to all participants (Steele, 2001).

Table 1: Operationalization of governance practices

Variable	Indicators	Source	Outcome
Accountability and Transparency	Election of group officials	Survey & FGDs	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator
	Voting methods	FGDs	
	Selection of delegates	FGDs	
	Presiding officer(s) Attendance	FGDs	
	AGM held as per constitution	FGDs	
	Income & expenditure reports	Survey & FGDs	
	Frequency of meetings for members	FGDs	
Efficiency & collective action	Constitution	FGDs	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator
	Membership list	FGDs	
Participation and collective actions	Participation (decision making & duty roster)	Survey & FGDs	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator
	Monitoring & Patrolling (security)	FGDs	
	Rule of law & enforcement	FGDs	
Benefit sharing	Forest products	Survey & FGDs	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator
	Plots for farming	Survey & FGDs	

Source: Author (Indicators adapted from PROFOR & FAO, 2011; UNDP, 2011).

2.1.4.2 Livelihood Outcomes

Table 2: Operationalization of Livelihood Outcomes

Livelihood Dimension	Indicators
Human Capital	Level of access to Knowledge
	Level of access to Information
	Level of access to Education
	Level of access to health care
Social Capital	Membership informal networks
	Membership in formalized groups
	Level of relationships that facilitate co-operation and economic activities
Natural Capital	Level of access to land
	Level of access to water resources
	Level of access to forest resources
	Level of access to fertile soils
Physical Capital	Level of access to road infrastructure in the community.
	Level of access to water infrastructure in the community
	Level of access to school infrastructure in the community
	Level of access to ICT infrastructure
	Level of access to producer goods has increased.
	Level of tools or machinery in possession
	Level of household equipment in possession
	Level of livestock in possession
Financial Capital	Level of savings in possession
	Level of access to credit services or institutions
	Proportion of income from employment
	Proportion of income from remittances

Source: Author (Indicators adapted from the Sustainable livelihoods framework: DFID, 1999)

2.1.4.3 REDD+

Table 3: Operationalization of REDD+

REDD+ Dimension	Indicator	Data source	Outcome
	Initiatives put in place to improve livelihood outcomes as a result of forest conservation efforts	All primary sources	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator(s)
	Initiatives put in place to improve community forest governance	All primary sources	Positive if evidence suggests the existence of the corresponding indicator(s)

Source: Author's construction

2.1.5 Study Conceptual Framework

Based on the reviewed theories and concepts and the following conceptual framework has been developed to show the possible relationships among variables.

Figure 1: Study Conceptual Framework

Source: Author

According to the figure above, forest governance practices are affecting the Rural livelihood outcomes. The better the forest governance practices are in the CFMG, the better the livelihood outcomes are as there will be accountability, transparency, equity, efficiency and fair benefit sharing. REDD+, the recent phenomenon occurring in the community by government and development partners, is directly affecting the rural livelihood outcomes through the various initiatives being implemented in these communities. At the same time, REDD+ is affecting livelihoods indirectly by contributing to the forest governance practices.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This section links the concepts defined in the previous section to their associated theories and it will form as a basis for the study’s conceptual framework. The section highlights the general key theories informing the study starting from the general governance theories narrowing down to the major theory informing the study. The theories discussed in this section include the theories on decentralization in forest governance, theories on common pool resource governance and livelihood theory.

2.2.1 Forest Governance Decentralization Theory

Theories found to be relevant for the study include the adaptive governance theory and the multi-level governance theory. The relevance of the governance decentralization theories to the current study is that they highlight on the evolution of forest governance i.e. from being centrally oriented by governments to the inclusion of multipolar institutional entities in the governance of public goods. These theories provide a general background to the rise of community based natural resource management before arriving at forest governance by community institutions as units of analysis and how they affect forest sustainability and livelihood outcomes.

a) Adaptive Governance Theory

The Adaptive Governance Theory emerged in the early 21st century in response to the need for more flexible, resilient, and sustainable governance systems that could effectively address complex environmental challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource management. The theory is primarily attributed to Elinor Ostrom and other scholars in the field of environmental governance. Ostrom, renowned for her work on common-pool resources, played a crucial role in advancing the idea of governance systems that could adapt to changing conditions. The theory integrates insights from complexity science, institutional theory, and resilience thinking, proposing that governance systems should be flexible, collaborative, and capable of learning from experiences and adjusting to evolving circumstances (Folke et al., 2005; Chaffin et al., 2014).

Recognizing the dynamic and interconnected nature of environmental and social systems, adaptive governance emphasizes decentralized decision-making, experimentation, and continuous learning to better address complexities (Folke et al., 2005; Armitage et al., 2009). Key principles include flexibility, learning and experimentation, collaboration and participation, resilience and adaptive capacity, and polycentric governance, guiding adaptation to changing circumstances and stakeholder engagement at multiple scales (Folke et al., 2005; Armitage et al., 2009).

In managing shared resources like environmental assets and common pool natural resources, adaptive governance considers institutional efficiency and adoptability to address market and institutional failures (Bowles, 2003; Ostrom, 2005). This theory, vital in political economy, regulates social learning and collective decision-making processes, shaping the nature and structure of institutions controlling decisions (Karpouzoglou, 2015). Defined as the evolution

of rules and norms to satisfy human needs and preferences amid changing contexts, adaptive governance underscores how social-ecological systems adapt to high uncertainty (Hatfield-Dodds et al., 2007; Brugnach et al., 2008; Hurlbert and Diaz, 2013). It aligns with new forms of governance involving multiple actors and interactions across sectors, emphasizing decision-making at various scales and levels (Termeer et al., 2013; Vogler and Jordan, 2003; Karpouzoglou et al., 2015).

Shifting focus from ecosystem management to broader social contexts, adaptive governance integrates empirical approaches to understand how institutional arrangements evolve over time (Dietz et al., 2003; Duit and Galaz, 2008; Folke et al., 2005). Guided by shared assumptions of system complexity, imperfect knowledge, rational actors, and community governance, adaptive governance offers a robust framework for managing shared natural resources (Holling and Meffe, 1996; Gunderson and Holling, 2002; Jiggins and Röling, 2000; Gintis, 2003; Ostrom et al., 1999).

In the current research on REDD+, community forest management and rural livelihood outcomes, adopting adaptive governance theory provides a compelling framework. This theory offers a robust lens through which to examine the complex dynamics between governance structures, environmental conservation efforts, and the well-being of forest-dependent communities.

Firstly, by emphasizing flexibility and learning, adaptive governance theory acknowledges the need for interventions to evolve in response to changing environmental and socio-economic conditions. This recognition is crucial for effectively addressing the dynamic challenges faced by forest-dependent communities. By facilitating iterative learning processes and allowing for adjustments based on feedback and emerging knowledge, adaptive governance promotes resilience and enhances the long-term sustainability of livelihood outcomes.

Secondly, collaborative decision-making is central to adaptive governance, ensuring that interventions are inclusive and contextually appropriate. In the context of REDD+ and community forest management, involving diverse stakeholders promotes ownership, legitimacy, and commitment to conservation efforts. By incorporating local knowledge and perspectives, collaborative approaches address the unique needs and priorities of forest-dependent communities, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of interventions.

Moreover, decentralization and participation empower local communities to effectively manage their forest resources. Community forest management groups exemplify adaptive

governance by enabling participatory decision-making processes that allow for experimentation and learning from both successes and failures. This local participation enhances the capacity of communities to sustainably manage forests and improve livelihoods. Additionally, social learning processes facilitate the exchange of knowledge and capacity building among stakeholders, enhancing the adaptive capacity of communities to respond to environmental changes. By fostering innovation and empowering communities, social learning contributes to the resilience and well-being of forest-dependent livelihoods.

Furthermore, adaptive governance aims to enhance the resilience and well-being of forest-dependent communities by prioritizing the diversification of livelihood strategies and equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms. This focus on building resilient livelihoods contributes to the sustainable management of forests and the improvement of well-being for forest-dependent communities. Finally, feedback loops and monitoring mechanisms play a crucial role in adaptive governance, enabling stakeholders to track the effectiveness of interventions and adjust strategies accordingly. This ensures that interventions are responsive, adaptive, and accountable, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of livelihood outcomes.

Critique of the Adaptive Governance Theory

The major critiques of Adaptive Governance Theory center around its implementation challenges, as the decentralized, collaborative decision-making processes it advocates can be difficult to execute, especially in regions with weak governance or political instability. Critics argue that the theory is vague and lacks concrete guidelines for practical application, making it hard to operationalize in diverse contexts. It also faces scalability issues, as it may be effective in smaller, localized settings but struggles to address larger, more complex systems. Additionally, the theory's emphasis on local knowledge and collaborative governance can sometimes overlook the importance of scientific expertise or top-down governance, and the assumption of equal participation can be undermined by power imbalances among stakeholders.

In summary, adopting adaptive governance theory in research offers a comprehensive framework for understanding and enhancing the effectiveness of initiatives like REDD+ and community forest management in improving livelihoods for forest-dependent communities. By promoting flexibility, collaboration, decentralization, social learning, resilience, and feedback mechanisms, adaptive governance contributes to the sustainable management of forests and the well-being of forest-dependent communities.

b) Multi-level Governance Theory

The Multi-Level Governance (MLG) Theory emerged in the early 1990s as a response to the increasing complexity of political decision-making, particularly in the context of European integration. The theory primarily developed through the work of Gary Marks, who is considered a key figure in its formation. Marks and other scholars like Liesbet Hooghe, Beate Kohler-Koch, Arthur Benz, and Simona Piattoni in the field of political science sought to explain the distribution of authority and the interactions between different levels of government local, regional, national, and supranational (such as the European Union). MLG emphasizes that governance is no longer confined to the nation-state and that power is shared across various levels of government, with significant involvement from non-governmental actors (e.g., civil society, private sector) (Hooghe & Marks, 2001; Piattoni, 2010).

This theory recognizes that modern governance systems are characterized by interactions between different levels of government, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders, rather than being solely hierarchical or centralized (Piattoni, 2010). It emphasizes the interdependence and interconnectedness of various governance actors and levels, challenging traditional notions of sovereignty and jurisdictional boundaries (Bache & Flinders, 2004; Scholte, 2000). One of its key insights is the dynamic and interactive nature of policy-making processes, involving negotiation, bargaining, and compromise among diverse actors operating at different levels (Kohler-Koch & Eising, 1999). This approach acknowledges the role of both state and non-state actors in shaping policy outcomes, reflecting the increasing importance of non-governmental organizations, civil society groups, and international institutions in global governance (Tallberg et al., 2013).

Furthermore, Multi-level governance theory highlights the importance of institutional arrangements that facilitate effective coordination and cooperation across different levels of government and between different stakeholders (Benz, 2007). Mechanisms such as networks, partnerships, and forums for dialogue and exchange enable actors to share information, resources, and decision-making authority (Jordan et al., 2005). According to proponents of the theory, governance encompasses the sum of regulations, policies, programs, and decisions designed to address public problems through collective action. These problems are considered public when actors need to act in the name of collective interest or the common good (Enderlein et al., 2017 in Kondowe, 2021).

Multi-level governance is viewed as a continuous negotiation system for cross-border governance. It involves negotiation among nested governments at several territorial tiers, where authority is dispersed both vertically between levels of administration and horizontally across different sectors and spheres of influence, including non-governmental actors, markets, and civil society (Daniell and Kay, 2017). Policy ideas are formulated at higher levels, while concrete activities and projects are implemented at lower levels. Global forest governance has shifted away from the nation-state, impacting both international and domestic forest policies and programs. Local players have the option to collaborate on projects for rural development or participate in forest protection management practices. Feedback from local communities is crucial for evaluating policy effectiveness and informing potential changes at higher decision-making levels (Secco et al., 2014).

Critique of the Multi-level Governance Theory

The major critiques of Multi-Level Governance (MLG) Theory focus on its vagueness and lack of clear definitions, which make it difficult to apply consistently across different contexts. While the theory emerged from the European Union context, critics argue it is too EU-centric and doesn't account for governance structures in non-European settings. Additionally, MLG often overlooks power imbalances between various governance levels, which can lead to inequities in representation and resource distribution. Critics also highlight concerns about the potential erosion of state sovereignty, as the theory suggests shared decision-making across multiple levels, which may weaken national governance. Finally, the complexity of multi-level interactions can result in coordination challenges and fragmentation in policy-making.

The theory of multi-level governance (MLG) provides a useful framework for the current research in understanding the complexities involved in initiatives like REDD+ and community forest management groups, and how they impact livelihood outcomes. Using the Multi-level Governance Approach to REDD+ initiatives involve multiple levels of governance, including international, national, and local levels. At the international level, agreements and frameworks are established to address deforestation and forest degradation, such as UNFCCC. Nationally, governments formulate policies, laws, and strategies to implement REDD+ activities, often involving coordination between different government agencies and ministries. Locally, communities and local stakeholders play a crucial role in implementing REDD+ projects, as they are directly affected by forest conservation efforts and may have traditional knowledge of forest management practices.

Also recognizing that community forest management groups are often key actors in implementing REDD+ initiatives and other conservation projects. These groups typically consist of local community members who are directly involved in managing and protecting forest resources within their territories. MLG theory recognizes the importance of these community-level actors and emphasizes the need for their participation in decision-making processes. It highlights the importance of decentralized governance structures that empower local communities to manage their natural resources sustainably.

The MLG theory also suggests that effective governance arrangements can lead to positive livelihood outcomes for communities involved in REDD+ and community forest management initiatives. By involving local communities in decision-making processes and giving them ownership over forest resources, these initiatives can contribute to poverty reduction, improved livelihoods, and sustainable development. However, challenges such as unequal power dynamics, conflicting interests, and insufficient capacity may hinder the realization of these benefits. MLG theory underscores the importance of addressing these challenges through inclusive and participatory governance mechanisms.

In summary, the MLG approach offers valuable insights into the governance dynamics of REDD+ and community forest management initiatives and their impacts on livelihood outcomes. By recognizing the interplay between different levels of governance and the importance of local participation, MLG theory can inform efforts to design and implement more effective and equitable conservation policies and practices.

2.2.2 Common-Pool Resource Governance Theory

Having highlighted the broader theories on governance decentralization and integration, this section discusses theories that isolate forest governance at a rural community level. The theories on the common-pool resource governance are the main theories informing the current study because they narrow natural resource governance down to the context of traditional African society. These theories attempt to do so using a historical approach. The theories include are the “tragedy of the commons” theory by Hardin and the “common-pool resource theory” by Ostrom.

Based on the basis that communities lived on common lands all over the world (often referred to as commons), they relied greatly on the abounding natural resources that surrounded them for their existence prior to the modern industrial age. Ancient African traditions incorporated nature into their worldviews, belief systems, and activities in order to recognize the worth of

natural resources. Utilizing natural resources responsibly while enhancing their capacity to adapt to changes in the ecosystem were central to many traditional practices. Pulse hunting is one instance, in which animals were targeted heavily during specific seasons and given the rest of the year to recuperate. This traditional capacity for adaptation may be extremely important for coping with current climate change consequences like droughts and floods. Theories on resource common-pool resource explain on the importance of creating a modern system for managing land and resources that reflects these ancient traditions as basis that may promote climate resilience in Africa's communal lands (Chiedza, 2022).

a) “Tragedy of the Commons Theory” by Hardin (1968)

The Tragedy of the Commons is a concept introduced by economist Garrett Hardin in 1968, which describes a situation where individuals, acting in their own self-interest, exploit a shared resource to the extent that demand exceeds supply and the resource becomes depleted or degraded. The theory is often applied to environmental and ecological issues but can be extended to any shared resource. His work was published in the journal *Science*. This theory has since become a cornerstone of discussions surrounding environmental economics, resource management, and collective action problems.

According to the theory, the ‘commons’ is defined as “a shared resource such as (land) that is managed by a defined community of commoners in terms of self-determined norms, practices and traditions that commoners themselves devise for governing the commons.” The concept of the commons is believed to have developed in early England as a necessary part of the agrarian economy and the feudal land tenure system, whereby the land belonged to a titled lord but was used and managed by tenants (Hardin, 1968). The majority of Africa's communal land was collectively governed by traditional authorities like chiefs and headmen in a manner akin to the commons of medieval England. These ancient leaders had the authority to divide up the land, regulate how it was used, and, in some cases, seize land. When the chief distributes land, he does not just give it to families; he also sets aside some areas for agriculture and pasture. The chief does not make choices collectively; instead, they are based on local community members' traditions. The use and management of natural resources were traditionally governed by rules and regulations in many of their systems of government (Chiedza, 2022).

Despite the fact that commons offer necessary services, they are frequently challenging to administer when there is no strong leadership to ensure adherence to the rules of use. A "tragedy of the commons" could occur if the established rules are frequently broken. Garrett Hardin first

used the phrase "tragic of the commons" in 1968 as part of a larger discussion on the overuse of natural resources as a result of population growth.

Hardin used the example of herders who graze their animals in a common field, or "commons," and who, under stable conditions, will continue to add to their herds until the field is full, to demonstrate the structure of his theory. At that time, adding another animal will still be advantageous to the herder, but the excess grazing that results will be shared by everybody, not just that herder. As a result, the advantages of additional animals outweigh the expenses for individual herders. This causes herders to increase their individual herd sizes until the common area becomes overburdened and incapable of supplying the animals with food. According to Hardin, "apart from grazing land, places like national parks and oceans are also susceptible to tragedy if there is overexploitation of resources in such commonly owned areas." The idea of the tragedy of the commons has come to "symbolize the environmental degradation expected when many people use a scarce resource in common" (Hardin, 1968).

This is a fact on contemporary community lands throughout Southern Africa, where there is no standardized system of land tenure and old customs relating to resources and land have been lost. It was Hardin's suggestion that "the tragedy of the commons may be averted through privatization or government control of resources." Colonialists in Africa initially established a tragedy of the commons by each person overusing the continent's natural resources for their own advantage, even if they weren't intentionally adhering to Hardin's theory. African wildlife ultimately started to disappear, which led to the creation of national parks in an effort to preserve what was remained. This included evicting local community groups forcibly from their homes (Chiedza, 2022).

This caused the "Yellowstone" or "fortress" model of conservation to arise, which is characterized by the exclusion of local people through patrols, fines, and fencing to enforce land use laws, while prioritizing tourists and scientists as welcome guests. This strategy adheres to Hardin's fundamental proposition that nature is best managed either centrally by the government or on private lands (which were solely owned by colonial descendants) for the protection and promotion of biodiversity. Displacement was a result of discriminatory legislation that tried to bar black people from owning land and exercising authority over community land in several African nations (Chiedza, 2022).

Critique of the Tragedy of the Commons Theory

While Hardin's idea was groundbreaking, it has also faced criticism for oversimplifying human behavior. Critics argue that people can cooperate without a central authority and that shared resources can be sustainably managed through mutual agreements and social norms, as demonstrated in Ostrom's work as shown the subsequent theory. Furthermore, critics argue that Hardin's view of human nature as purely self-interested may not fully account for the potential for cooperation, reciprocity, and social responsibility in managing shared resources.

b) Common-pool Resource Theory by Elinor Ostrom (1990)

Elinor Ostrom's Common-Pool Resource (CPR) Theory was primarily developed and articulated through her empirical research and academic publications over several decades. Her work culminated in the 1990 book "Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action", which became her seminal contribution to the field and provided the theoretical basis for her CPR framework.

This book is considered the central work that presents Ostrom's theory on managing common-pool resources. In it, Ostrom challenges the assumptions of the Tragedy of the Commons and outlines her findings from decades of fieldwork. She argues that local communities can develop rules and mechanisms to self-organize and govern shared resources effectively. The book introduces her design principles for successful CPR management and provides empirical evidence from case studies around the world, ranging from irrigation systems in Nepal to fisheries in Turkey.

Elinor Ostrom rose to prominence as a renowned academic who challenged the relevance of Hardin's tragedy of the commons in contemporary society and established the principles of common-pool resource theory. This was despite the popularity and influence of Hardin's initial idea, the tragedy of the commons faced fierce opposition in wider scientific literature. The widespread applicability of models based on the tragedy of the commons was called into question by policy researchers in the middle of the 1980s.

Ostrom conducted in-depth studies on commons in diverse locales like Kenya, Nepal, Switzerland, and the US State of Maine, among others. She created eight design principles for sustainable management of the commons using the knowledge she gained from observing people successfully manage their resources in these many circumstances. The principles created include, (1) clearly defined boundaries of the group and land or resources they manage; (2) a close match between the rules of resource governance and local conditions; (3) those

affected by the rules participate in making the rules; (4) effective monitoring systems involving monitors who are part of or accountable to the community; (5) graduated sanctions against those who do not respect community rules; (6) conflict resolution mechanisms that are cheap and easy to access; (7) minimal recognition of rights to organise granted by external authorities (e.g. government); (8) multiple layers of nested governance responsibility from the lowest level (e.g. one village) through to the system level (e.g. whole ecosystem or country). Ostrom contends that while poorly managed commons do not adhere to the majority of the aforementioned standards, sustainably managed commons do (Ostrom, 1990).

Natural resource management organizations in southern Africa started to realize in the middle of the 1980s that they lacked the funding and personnel necessary to successfully avoid resource deterioration, which put Hardin's theoretical remedies for the tragedy of the commons under scrutiny. Around the same time that democracy emerged in southern Africa, newly elected governments put pressure on natural resource management organizations to consider the requests and cries of regional communities for increased recognition and enhanced access to ecosystem services. In the same time frame, social scientists started to influence the discussion of natural resource management and promoted a more human-centered strategy. Their greatest contribution was bringing Ostrom's common-pool resource theory to the attention of ecologists and range scientists.

The notion of community-based natural resource management (CBNRM) embodies Ostrom's ideas. Natural ecosystems within clearly defined communal lands are jointly managed by self-identified communities that are officially recognized by national authorities under CBNRM. Communities can create resource regulations that are appropriate for their particular circumstances by establishing their own management systems. They can then hire monitors to ensure that all members follow these rules and can impose sanctions on rule-breakers, typically in conjunction with local government agencies. To establish a layered structure of governance, these community-based institutions can work with nearby communities and regional government agencies. Thus, a well-managed CBNRM program should implement each of Ostrom's eight principles (Chiedza, 2022).

Instead of relying on the command-and-control structures of central government, CBNRM is a method of administering the commons that replicates traditional African governance structures at the local level. With Ostrom's ideas for sustainable resource use as a guide, it thereby seeks to avoid Hardin's forecast of tragedy. CBNRM is a promising path forward in the southern

African environment, where government resources are limited and people who have been disenfranchised and displaced are clamoring for the restoration of their rights to resources (Chiedza, 2022).

In support of Ostrom's theory, the current study is an attempt to extend this theory by highlighting governance practices within community forest management groups and how this influences forest conservation and livelihood outcomes. The current study argues that outcomes in poor governance in local organizations might not only lead to poor forest conservation outcomes but also livelihood outcomes.

Critique of Common Pool Resource Theory

Elinor Ostrom's Common-Pool Resource (CPR) Theory has faced several critiques, including concerns about its context-specificity, the scalability of local governance systems to larger or global commons, and the assumption that communities will naturally cooperate. Critics argue that the theory may not apply universally, especially in large, complex systems or settings with high inequality and power imbalances. Additionally, some question its overemphasis on local self-governance while downplaying the role of centralized regulation or market-based solutions. Ostrom responded by emphasizing the adaptability of her design principles to different contexts and advocating for a polycentric governance approach, where multiple levels of governance work together. She acknowledged the role of external interventions when needed, but stressed that local, self-organized governance can often be more flexible and effective. Ostrom also addressed concerns about enforcement by highlighting the importance of social sanctions and local accountability mechanisms in managing resources sustainably.

2.2.3 Sustainable Livelihoods Theory

The Sustainable Livelihoods Theory emerged primarily in the 1990s, developed through the contributions of Robert Chambers and Ian Scoones, along with significant input from institutions like the UK Department for International Development (DFID) and the Institute of Development Studies (IDS). The theory was designed to better understand how people make a living and how they can achieve sustainable outcomes, especially in the context of poverty reduction and development. It highlights the importance of assets (human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital) in shaping livelihood strategies and focuses on long-term sustainability across economic, social, and environmental dimensions.

The sustainable livelihoods theory is founded upon the notion that interventions must be based upon what underpins livelihoods. Previous development approaches to development were based on two forms, the immanent development approach and the intentional development approach. The immanent development approach denotes the normative broad processes of social change that occur through a host of many factors such as science, technology, medicine, arts, communication, governance etc. This key facilitator of this process is globalization (international integration) which permits for exchanges between technologies and ideas. The intentional / interventionist approach on the other hand is a focused and directional processes where governments and non-governmental organizations implement projects or programs to help the poor. Both of these forms do and may occur in parallel i.e. the immanent development that constantly happens as governments world over invest in infrastructure, education, consumer products and services. At the sometime the country might also host a number of development projects funded by foreign agencies (Morse and McNamara, 2013).

Immanent development has been happening throughout human history whereas intentional development is relatively new more visible after the second world war with the Brenttonwood institutions coming to the center stage to fund development projects globally. Even though this period is considered as pivotal in the emergence of intentional development, other occurrence of intentional development activities had already started occurring before or during the same period for example through missionaries' establishments of schools and hospitals (Morse and McNamara, 2013).

These approaches to development had criticisms which subsequently led to the development of the sustainable livelihoods approach. Some of the criticisms included the approach shifting all powers of decision making on what needs to be done to developed countries (Schuurman). Other authors like Escobar (1992) regarded intentional development as nothing more than the ideological expression of post-world war II capitalism. Other critics have argued that by large, this approach has not been successful with Africa cited as a classic example of failure (Mathews, 2004). Critics have argued that despite the colossal sums of investment made by the developed world, these projects have failed to generate positive unsustainable outcomes for people who were meant to benefit. The issue of visioning was being questioned were it was argued that, if a vision of development from the developed countries is being imposed on circumstances that are unsuitable, then it is inevitably doomed to failure. Thus, there has been a backlash to this approach to development which is often referred to as the post development movement (Rahnema and Bawtree, 1997) or anto-development (Simon, 2006).

From these past approaches came the sustainable livelihoods approach which aimed at providing a framework for analysis leading to concrete suggestions for interventions (Allison and Horemans, 2006; Tao and Wall, 2009). In this light, the sustainable livelihood approach provides a way for development practitioners to analyse people's current livelihood and what is needed for an enhancement, and useful in avoiding inappropriate interventions critiqued by post developmentalists. In this regard, the SLA does not aim at replacing the current livelihoods or having more means of livelihoods, but rather it rests on the recommendations that the people themselves may be able to put in practice rather than wait on the actions of the outsiders (Morse and McNamara, 2013).

The difference that the SLA has with the other previous integrated approaches to rural development is that interventions such as health, agriculture and infrastructure had a narrow perspective, not joined up or all embracing. Given that poverty is multi-dimensional, the history of development efforts suggested that a project ought to focus on only one of the dimensions. The result was that such projects were outlived (Krantz, 2001).

Within this the sustainable livelihoods approach, a framework that captures the livelihood circumstances of people from poor countries was developed known as the sustainable livelihood's framework. At its core is the assessment of the different capitals that are deemed to underpin livelihood at the level of the individual, household, village or group. These capitals are classified as human, social, physical, natural and financial. They are then assessed in terms of their vulnerability to shocks and the institutional context within which they exist. Once this is understood then interventions can be put in place to enhance livelihoods and their sustainability, perhaps by increasing the capital available or by reducing vulnerability. Thus, the process is about understanding the current situation and developing suggestions for improvement based upon that understanding. The SLA is meant to avoid a situation where intervention is unguided giving little positive impact or is at worst detrimental (Morse and McNamara, 2013).

Figure 2: Sustainable livelihoods framework
 Source: Author adapted from (DFID, 1999)

Critique of the Sustainable Livelihoods Theory

The Sustainable Livelihoods Theory has faced several critiques, primarily regarding its context-specific nature, which makes it difficult to apply universally, especially in large-scale or global contexts. Critics argue that the framework often overlooks broader, systemic issues such as global economic forces or climate change, which significantly impact livelihoods. It also assumes a level of stability in people's livelihood strategies, which may not hold true in situations of conflict or rapid environmental and political change. Additionally, some argue that the theory's overemphasis on local, community-based solutions may neglect the role of top-down interventions or external support in certain circumstances. Finally, the complexity of the framework, with its multiple forms of capital and their interactions, can make it difficult to apply effectively in practice, especially in assessing and measuring outcomes

Despite the critique, the sustainable livelihoods serve as a guide in the current to study to analyse the situation of forest dependent communities within their different institutional contexts. The framework does not provide particular methods to explore capitals, institutions, vulnerability etc. an SLA could utilize a dissimilar range of methods including standard techniques based upon observation, focus groups and interviewing. Morse and McNamara (2013) notes that the SLA is simply providing a framework as to what should be looked for and not necessarily how to do the looking.

There various contexts through which the sustainable livelihoods framework has been used, it has been used as a tool for analysis (Krantz, 2001), other agencies such as UNDP and CARE apply it as a tool to facilitate the planning of concrete programmes and projects. However, the current study takes the nuanced view suggested by Farrington (2001) who stated that the framework might be used as a formal analytical framework to help understand the what ‘is’ and what can be done. Other than that, the framework is viewed as a tool that helps to aid an appreciation of capitals which are available to households, their vulnerability and the involvement of institutions (Farrington, 2001).

2.3 The Evolution of REDD+ in International Governance

Since recognizing the role of forests in mitigating climate change in the Bali action plan (UNFCCC’s COP 13), the evolution of REDD+ governance has been a significant global process, progressively shaped by key international decisions and agreements aimed at reducing deforestation, promoting forest restoration, and encouraging sustainable land use. From its initial conception in 2010 to its expanding role in the global climate agenda, REDD+ has become a central mechanism for addressing climate change and supporting sustainable development worldwide (Parrotta 2022).

The framework for REDD+ trace back to COP 16 in Cancún, Mexico, in 2010, where the mechanism was officially recognized under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). This marked a major milestone in recognizing the role of forests in mitigating climate change. The Cancún decision expanded the role of forests beyond carbon sequestration to include forest conservation, sustainable management, and the enhancement of forest carbon stocks. REDD+ was envisioned as a voluntary, nationally-driven approach, where high-income countries (listed in Annex 1 of the UNFCCC) would pay low- and middle-income countries (non-Annex 1 Parties) for reducing forest emissions. The framework adopted a phased approach for REDD+ implementation, beginning with the readiness phase, moving to

implementation, and then to results-based actions, where emissions reductions would be measured, reported, and verified (Parrotta, 2022).

The Warsaw Framework, adopted at COP 19 in 2013, was a key development in the operationalization of REDD+. It clarified important aspects related to monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems, and provided technical guidelines for countries' proposed reference emissions levels (RELS) or forest reference levels (FRLs). One of the significant decisions from the Warsaw Framework was the emphasis on safeguards to ensure that REDD+ activities respect human rights and contribute to sustainable development, particularly in the social and environmental domains (UNFCCC, 2014).

The Paris Agreement, adopted in 2015 at COP 21, represented a pivotal moment for REDD+. The agreement's primary goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C underscored the vital role of forests in mitigating climate change. Article 5.2 of the Paris Agreement explicitly recognized REDD+ and provided provisions for mobilizing climate finance for forest-related mitigation efforts. Another key aspect of the Paris Agreement, under Article 6, allowed countries to explore flexible finance mechanisms, including the use of internationally transferred mitigation outcomes (ITMOs) for REDD+. This approach opened the door for broader financing of REDD+ activities through both public and private sector investments, particularly in the form of results-based payments (Streck, 2016; UN, 2015).

Alongside these institutional developments, the Green Climate Fund (GCF) emerged as a significant player in the financing of REDD+. Established at COP 16 in Cancún, the GCF has been critical in supporting REDD+ activities through results-based payments (RBPs). In 2014, the GCF recognized REDD+ as a priority area for financing, offering a 2.5% premium on RBPs for projects that deliver non-carbon benefits. This innovation further cemented REDD+ as a multifaceted tool for addressing climate change, encompassing not only carbon sequestration but also biodiversity conservation, social development, and poverty alleviation (GCF, n.d.).

At the same time, there has been growing momentum in global efforts to restore degraded lands and ecosystems, which aligns closely with REDD+'s objectives. The Bonn Challenge, launched in 2011, aimed to restore 350 million hectares of degraded land by 2030, while the African Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative (AFR100) sought to restore 100 million hectares of land across Africa by 2030. These efforts, together with the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030), which focuses on the global restoration of ecosystems, reflect a

broader international push to address forest degradation and enhance carbon sequestration (UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration website).

Another key development in the realm of forest restoration and carbon market integration is ART-TREES (Architecture for REDD+ Transactions—The REDD+ Environmental Excellence Standard), which has become a key framework for ensuring that REDD+ projects deliver high-quality environmental outcomes. ART-TREES aims to standardize the measurement, reporting, and verification of forest carbon credits, ensuring that they meet rigorous criteria for environmental integrity and sustainability. This initiative, along with the LEAF (Lowering Emissions by Accelerating Finance) Coalition, which focuses on leveraging private sector finance for forest-based emissions reductions, has gained prominence in the financing of REDD+ activities. These frameworks aim to ensure that forest carbon credits generated through REDD+ activities are credible, transparent, and contribute to the long-term sustainability of forest ecosystems (Leaf coalition website).

The fight against illegal logging and unsustainable land-use practices has remained central to REDD+'s objectives, and significant efforts have been made to combat deforestation linked to illegal activities. The European Union's Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) initiative has been at the forefront of these efforts, particularly through the Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs), which promote the trade of legally sourced timber and improve forest governance in timber-producing countries. The EU Timber Regulation (EUTR), aimed at eliminating illegal timber from the European supply chain, further supports this effort. These initiatives align with REDD+'s overarching goal of reducing deforestation while promoting the responsible use of forest resources (Parrotta et al., 2022).

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on "due diligence" by private sector actors, particularly in relation to commodities linked to deforestation, such as palm oil, soy, beef, and timber. The European Union has introduced a range of due diligence legislation aimed at ensuring that companies engaged in the trade of these commodities do not contribute to deforestation. These regulations, along with corporate commitments to zero deforestation, have added a layer of accountability to global supply chains, reinforcing the goals of REDD+ and sustainable land use. At COP 26 in 2021, over 100 countries signed the Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use, pledging to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030. This declaration reaffirmed the importance of forests in the global climate

agenda and demonstrated growing political will to address deforestation as part of climate action strategies.

The governance of REDD+ has evolved significantly since its inception in 2007, driven by international agreements, such as the 2010's Cancun to include innovative financing mechanisms, and the increasing involvement of both the public and private sectors. The establishment of frameworks such as ART-TREES and the LEAF Coalition, along with financing mechanisms like the Green Climate Fund, has bolstered the effectiveness of REDD+ as a tool for climate change mitigation, forest conservation, and sustainable development. As the global community faces mounting challenges related to climate change, biodiversity loss, and unsustainable land use, the continued development and expansion of REDD+ governance will be essential in promoting forest conservation, restoration, and the achievement of global sustainability targets.

Table 4: Key events in the evolution of REDD+

Year	Event/Development	Description
2007	Bali Action Plan (COP 13)	Inclusion of REDD (now REDD+), which recognized the role of forests in mitigating climate change. The plan encouraged discussions on the financial mechanisms to support the reduction of emissions from deforestation and forest degradation, laying the groundwork for future negotiations on forest conservation.
2010	Cancún Decision on REDD+ (COP 16)	REDD+ was expanded to include conservation of forest carbon stocks, sustainable management of forests, and enhancement of forest carbon stocks. The Cancún safeguards were adopted, including Safeguard E, which required REDD+ actions to enhance social and environmental benefits, such as the conservation of biodiversity.

Year	Event/Development	Description
2010	Green Climate Fund (GCF) Established for REDD+ (COP 16)	The GCF was officially recognized as a financing mechanism for REDD+ results-based payments, and its investment criteria began requiring projects to provide wider benefits, such as economic, social, environmental, and gender empowerment co-benefits.
2013	Warsaw Framework (COP 19)	The Warsaw Framework recognized the importance of incentivizing non-carbon benefits to ensure the long-term sustainability of REDD+ activities. It also focused on guidelines for monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems, including reference emission levels.
2015	Paris Agreement (COP 21)	The Paris Agreement reaffirmed the importance of non-carbon benefits in REDD+ and invited countries to submit information on these benefits as part of their REDD+ activities. The agreement also recognized forests' critical role in limiting global warming to 1.5°C, and set the stage for broader international cooperation on climate finance.
2016	GCF Non-Carbon Benefit Premium (COP 22)	The GCF introduced a 2.5% non-carbon benefit premium on REDD+ results-based payments, rewarding countries that provide information on the social, environmental, and other non-carbon benefits of their REDD+ activities.
2017	GCF and Co-Benefits Focus (COP 23)	As part of the ongoing implementation of the GCF criteria, countries increasingly began compiling information on co-benefits (economic, social, environmental, gender empowerment) through

Year	Event/Development	Description
2019	UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021-2030) (COP 25)	Aimed at restoring 350 million hectares of forests globally by 2030, contributing to climate mitigation and supporting biodiversity. This global restoration effort ties into the broader goals of REDD+ and forest management.
2020	ART-TREES (Architecture for REDD+ Transactions – The REDD+ Environmental Excellence Standard) (COP 26)	ART-TREES launched to enhance the integrity of REDD+ carbon credits and ensure countries demonstrate environmental and social benefits. ART-TREES seeks to improve the sustainability of forest carbon markets by ensuring transparency and robust verification of carbon and non-carbon benefits.
2020	LEAF Coalition (Lowering Emissions by Accelerating Finance) (COP 26)	The LEAF Coalition was established to accelerate financing for REDD+ and forest protection efforts. LEAF is a market-based initiative that leverages private sector funding to support large-scale emission reductions and forest conservation, with a focus on non-carbon co-benefits.
2021	Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use (COP 26)	Over 100 countries signed the Glasgow Leaders' Declaration, pledging to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030. This declaration highlights the importance of sustainable forest management and restoring degraded lands to meet climate and biodiversity goals.

Year	Event/Development	Description
Ongoing	Voluntary Carbon Market Growth	The voluntary carbon market has expanded significantly, with increasing private sector demand for deforestation-offset credits linked to net-zero deforestation commitments. REDD+ activities are increasingly included in these markets, supported by initiatives like the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSA).

Source: (Author, adapted from literature)

2.4 Architecture for REDD+ Finance

The financing of REDD+ and related activities has evolved significantly, primarily due to the growing recognition of the "biodiversity financing gap." This gap refers to the difference between current funding for global biodiversity conservation and the estimated total amount needed to maintain ecosystem integrity. In this context, nature-based solutions (NbS) and carbon markets have become vital mechanisms to mobilize additional capital flows for biodiversity conservation (Seddon et al., 2021).

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic had a notable impact on financial flows, reducing private finance across various sectors, including those related to climate change and REDD+. Public finance, primarily focused on health and economic recovery, also saw its scope limited. While there was some hope that COVID-19 might catalyze climate mitigation efforts, the anticipated "great reset" has not yet translated into substantial commitments for supporting the REDD+ agenda (Parrotta, et al., 2022).

Financial flows for REDD+ are typically categorized into readiness, implementation, and results-based payments (RBPs). A recent review found that most REDD+ finance has been directed toward readiness activities, such as capacity building, developing national strategies, and establishing systems for monitoring and verifying emissions reductions. Key multilateral sources of REDD+ funding include the Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF), the UN-REDD Programme, and the Forest Investment Programme (FIP). The Green Climate Fund (GCF), launched at COP16, has become a significant source of funding for REDD+, offering a USD 500 million pilot financing programme for REDD+ countries. This fund focuses on

developing countries meeting specific criteria, such as national strategies and reference levels for forest emissions. Since then, many countries have moved from the readiness phase to the implementation phase and, in some cases, to the results-based actions phase. In addition, the private sector has increasingly engaged in financing REDD+ activities, driven by corporate commitments to reduce their carbon footprints. Companies like Microsoft and Amazon have pledged to achieve carbon neutrality by 2030 and 2040, respectively, with forest conservation initiatives being a key part of their strategies (GCF, n.d.).

Market-based finance for REDD+ revolves around carbon credits, which are transactions in voluntary and compliance carbon markets. Voluntary carbon markets, in particular, have gained prominence, with carbon credits being transacted by a range of buyers, including companies and governments. A significant proportion of these credits is linked to REDD+ activities, with the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) playing a dominant role. In 2019, 42% of the VCS credits traded were tied to REDD+ activities (Parrotta et al., 2022).

The Architecture for REDD+ Transactions (ART) initiative has further contributed to this landscape by developing an independent standard for measuring and verifying emissions reductions from forests. ART's REDD+ Environmental Excellence Standard (TREES) allows jurisdictions to generate verified emission reduction credits, which can be transacted on public registries. Recent initiatives, such as the LEAF Coalition (a public-private partnership involving countries like Norway, the United States, and the United Kingdom), aim to scale up financing for REDD+ and use ART-TREES standards to facilitate large-scale forest-based climate solutions. The Green Gigaton Challenge (GGC), launched in 2020, similarly aims to catalyze funds for forest-based natural climate solutions and set a floor price for carbon credits (LEAF coalition website).

Meanwhile, green bonds have become increasingly important within the private sector. These bonds fund projects focused on sustainable development and climate goals, including those that support nature-based solutions such as REDD+. The rise of green bonds reflects a broader trend of private sector involvement in environmental finance, aligning with corporate and investment goals to meet climate-neutral or net-zero targets.

However, there is growing concern about the need for better transparency and tracking of financial flows for NbS, particularly when distinguishing between forest-related activities and other sectors, such as agriculture, that contribute to deforestation avoidance. This also brings

attention to the broader issue of carbon offsetting, with some experts advocating for a shift towards carbon removal projects rather than emissions reduction alone (Seddon et al., 2021).

Despite the challenges, the voluntary carbon market has shown growth, with increasing demand for nature-based offsets, including those linked to REDD+. However, estimates indicate that to meet global climate goals, the market for voluntary offsets needs to grow substantially, both in volume and price. The COVID-19 pandemic did not dampen the voluntary carbon market, and the growing corporate interest in achieving climate-neutral or net-zero goals is expected to further bolster demand for high-quality REDD+ credits in the future (Parrotta et al., 2022).

Table 5: Various sources of REDD+ financing

Category	Source/Initiative	Focus	Key Points
REDD+ Financing	Green Climate Fund (GCF)	Multilateral climate finance for REDD+ (Results-based Payments)	Launched a USD 500 million REDD+ pilot in 2017; supports countries with Warsaw Framework elements in place.
Market-based Finance	Carbon Markets	Voluntary carbon markets and compliance markets	Includes carbon credits for deforestation avoidance and sequestration; high demand for nature-based credits.
Financial Instruments	Green Bonds	Private sector investment in environmental projects	Focus on raising funds for climate and biodiversity initiatives.
Bilateral Funding	Norway (performance-based)	Climate finance for REDD+ linked to emission reductions	Norway's finance contingent on performance, but not generating tradable carbon credits.

Category	Source/Initiative	Focus	Key Points
Private-Public Partnerships	LEAF Coalition	Public-private initiative supporting REDD+ financing	Aims to mobilize USD 1 billion for jurisdictional REDD+ programs.
Voluntary Carbon Markets	Ecosystem Marketplace	Trading of forestry and land-use credits	REDD+ credits play a major role; over 99% of forestry credits verified with independent standards.
Jurisdictional REDD+	ART-TREES Standard	Verification and registry for REDD+ emission reductions	Independent standard to verify reductions from deforestation; used in initiatives like the LEAF Coalition.
Green Gigaton Challenge (GGC)	Public-private coalition	Catalyzing funds for REDD+ to reduce one gigaton of CO ₂ by 2025	Focus on jurisdictional REDD+ projects and a floor price of USD 10 per tonne CO ₂ .

Source: (Author, adapted from literature)

2.5 REDD+ Safeguards: Objectives, Challenges, and Progress

REDD+ offers significant potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote social and environmental benefits. However, its implementation also presents risks, especially for local communities and ecosystems. To address these risks and maximize the benefits, the Cancún Safeguards, agreed upon by the UNFCCC, were designed to ensure that REDD+ activities respect social, environmental, and governance criteria. These safeguards are to be addressed and respected throughout REDD+ activities.

The seven Cancún Safeguards include:

1. **Consistency with National Forest Programs and International Agreements:**
REDD+ activities should align with national forest management plans and international commitments.

2. **Effective Governance:** REDD+ must be implemented under transparent and accountable governance structures that respect national sovereignty and laws.
3. **Respect for Indigenous Peoples' Rights:** The knowledge and rights of Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) must be respected, in accordance with international conventions like the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples.
4. **Inclusive Stakeholder Participation:** REDD+ must ensure full and effective participation of relevant stakeholders, particularly IPLCs, in decision-making processes.
5. **Conservation of Natural Forests and Biodiversity:** Actions must prioritize the protection and conservation of natural forests and biodiversity, preventing the conversion of forests into other land uses.
6. **Mitigation of Reversals:** Measures should be in place to address the risks of reversing emission reductions from deforestation.
7. **Prevention of Emission Displacement:** REDD+ actions must avoid shifting deforestation to other areas (emission displacement or leakage).

While these safeguards are central to REDD+'s framework, their practical application has faced numerous challenges. Over the past decade, progress has been slow, often hindered by limited guidance from the UNFCCC, as well as evolving financial structures related to REDD+ implementation (UNFCC Decision 1/C.P. 16 Appendix 1, Paragraph 2).

2.5.1 Political Ecology of REDD+ Safeguards

The political ecology of REDD+ highlights the complexities involved in ensuring the safeguards are effectively implemented. For instance, recognizing the importance of traditional knowledge and securing land tenure rights are fundamental to ensuring that IPLCs benefit from REDD+ initiatives. Studies indicate that land tenure security reduces deforestation and strengthens custodianship, with regions where IPLC land rights are recognized showing lower deforestation rates (Parrotta et al., 2022).

However, land tenure issues remain inadequately addressed in many REDD+ initiatives. Weak legal frameworks, corruption, and governance challenges often undermine efforts to secure IPLC land rights, and there is a lack of clarity around carbon rights and legal frameworks for carbon transactions. This gap creates barriers to effective participation by IPLCs in the REDD+

process. Additionally, Grievance Redress Mechanisms (FGRMs) are crucial for resolving conflicts and ensuring transparency in REDD+ implementation. While many countries have recognized the need for FGRMs, establishing them has been slow due to inadequate funding and institutional capacity. Similarly, the design of Benefit-Sharing Mechanisms (BSMs) that are flexible, inclusive, and culturally appropriate has proven to be challenging. Such mechanisms are essential for ensuring equitable distribution of REDD+ benefits, particularly for marginalized communities (Parrotta et al., 2022).

2.6 National and Sub-National REDD+ Processes

REDD+ implementation occurs in three phases: readiness (Phase I), implementation (Phase II), and results-based actions (Phase III). Each country is expected to develop key elements such as a National REDD+ Strategy, Forest Monitoring Systems (NFMS), Forest Reference Emission Levels (FREL), and a Safeguards Information System (SIS). However, countries have considerable flexibility in selecting methodologies for carbon accounting, particularly for FREL, resulting in diverse approaches that are influenced by national contexts, funding sources, and actor preferences (Brockhaus et al., 2019; Korhonen-Karki et al., 2019; FAO, 2018).

One major challenge is avoiding double counting of emission reductions, especially when both national and sub-national projects claim the same credits. Nesting integrating smaller projects into larger jurisdictional frameworks is a proposed solution to address this issue. However, nesting is still in the developmental phase, with emerging guidelines, such as those from the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) and the Architecture for REDD+ Transactions (ART).

At the jurisdictional level, some initiatives are gaining traction, incentivizing the sourcing of commodities from areas that have reduced deforestation. This movement aligns REDD+ with broader forest governance efforts, such as legality verification and supply chain commitments, exemplified by initiatives like the Commodities/Jurisdictions Approach (CJA), driven by companies like Unilever and Marks & Spencer. Countries are increasingly conducting national safeguards assessments to ensure that REDD+ actions align with local legal, institutional, and international frameworks. These assessments typically involve identifying governance arrangements, setting institutional procedures to uphold safeguards, and creating systems for monitoring and reporting safeguard compliance. However, challenges in standardizing and integrating these safeguards persist, partly due to the fragmented and evolving funding landscape (Parrotta et al., 2022).

2.6.1 Progress and Challenges in Safeguard Implementation

Despite significant challenges, countries have made progress in meeting the UNFCCC's safeguard requirements. As of 2020, 15 countries had developed their Safeguard Information Systems (SIS), and 17 countries had submitted summaries of safeguards information to the UNFCCC. Moreover, eight countries have met the necessary safeguards to access Results-Based Payments (RBPs), demonstrating advances in integrating safeguards into REDD+ initiatives.

Nevertheless, complex and costly safeguard frameworks, such as the REDD+ Social and Environmental Standards (REDD+ SES), have led to stakeholder fatigue and shifted the focus from the broader social objectives of REDD+ to narrow technical compliance. As the international funding landscape continues to evolve, there is a need for clearer guidance and greater coordination to ensure the successful implementation of the Cancún safeguards. Despite these hurdles, REDD+ remains a promising tool for addressing climate change, with the potential for significant positive outcomes if its safeguards are respected and adapted to local needs.

2.7 Evolution of Forest Governance and REDD+ in Zambia

The evolution of forest governance in this study is discussed in terms of governance during the colonial era and the post-colonial era. The policy reforms that occurred establishing Community Based Forest Management are also highlighted in this section.

2.7.1 Colonial Era

The land reform of 1924, which took place during the colonial era, served as the foundation for Zambia's forest governance structures. Land in Zambia was divided into crown and native reserve land during this time, which were intended for the sole usage of African and European settlers, respectively (Van Loenen, 1999; Brown, 2005). Based on customary law, the chiefs oversaw the management of the forests in native reserves. On the basis of formal law, the British colonial authority in contrast managed the forests on crown land (Brown, 2005). Customary land administration was superseded upon independence by formal legislation, which had hitherto only applied to crown land. Nevertheless, under customary law, the practice of customary land isolation persisted. Crown land became state land after Zambia gained independence in 1964, and the Ministry of Lands then took over its administration (Brown, 2005).

2.7.2 Post colonial Era

The recognition of shortcomings in the centralized system of forest governance led the government of the republic of Zambia (GRZ) to embark on more participatory approaches to forest management beginning the 1990s onwards. This was a common trend even among other nations of Sub-Saharan Africa such as Tanzania, Cameroon and the Gambia at that time. Joint forest Management (JFM) was identified as the most suitable form participatory forest management for the country's gazette national forest systems. Hence the National Forest policy issued in 1998 officially recognized JFM as a key strategy (GRZ, 2007; Hobley, 1996). Within the same year act was passed to adopt a multi-stakeholder approach to forest management and proposed for the establishment of the Zambia Forestry Commission (ZAFCOM) and the establishment of local level village management institutions to support SFM and locally based enterprises. However, this act never came into effect. In 1999, statutory instrument (S.I.) 52 was passed and it clearly outlined official procedures for forming a JFM. This instrument was later superseded by S.I.49 of 2006.

Despite the 1998 forest policy being pivotal in creating the foundations for PFM through JFM, it had certain inadequacies similar to the previous regimes. Similarly, the 2010 forest policy continued to focus on harvesting of none timber forest products (NTFPs) such as fruits, fibers, medicinal herbs, grasses); leaving out the economically viable products such as timber and firewood or charcoal. The only difference is that the 2010 version emphasized on the significance of NTFPs for poverty reduction. In 2013, the Forestry department introduced Statutory instrument 52 of 2013 through parliament, with a focus on limiting biodiversity loss and limiting local populations' access to particular NTFPs. The statutory document, however, seemed to be at conflict with the 2010 NFP, which viewed NTFP as a tool for enhancing the local communities' standard of living. In response, the 2014 Revised National Forest Policy placed a high priority on involving local communities, traditional institutions, the private sector, and other stakeholders in the management and utilization of forest resources at all stages of decision-making, implementation, and monitoring (Mulenga, Nkonde, and Ngoma 2015). The contribution of NTFPs to the wellbeing of the majority of rural households, however, is still little understood (Mulenga et al. 2014).

The Forest Department (FD), a government organization founded under the Forests Act of 1973 that has a primary responsibility to protect and manage the nation's forest resources (Bojang, 2013), piloted JFM across seven provinces with strong support from international donor

agencies. According to Bradley, Mickels-Kokwe, and Moombe (2019) there were more than 20 pilot projects for JFM throughout the country between 1999 and 2008. However, the process stagnated as there was no clear legal framework on how benefits would be shared between community members and the state, as well as the lower value forest products (Nansikombi et al., 2020).

Table 6: Developments in PFM from 1999 to 2008

Developments in JFM	Location	Development Partner
Provincial Forestry Action Programme (PFAP II)	Central, Copperbelt, Luapula, and Southern Provinces.	The Government of Finland
JFM methodology development	Katete and Mambwe Districts in Eastern Province	Cooperative League of the USA (CLUSA)
JFM Pilot projects	Central, North-Western and Luapula Provinces	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)

Source: Author (Bradley, Mickels-Kokwe, & Moombe, 2019)

In the following ten years after 2008, no officially sanctioned JFM initiatives were launched for ten years after 2008, and the issues identified for stagnation remained unresolved. The identified institutional limitations ultimately prevented most attempts to involve communities in JFM from making any progress. "The lack of tangible and promised benefits has created a general feeling among the communities of being used by the forest department," a 2014 study of JFM said in its conclusion. Moreover, according to Leventon, Kalaba, Dyer, Stringer, and Dougill (2014), "rules are not followed by the communities because the rules of [JFM] participation do not deliver tangible benefit, and do not allow the communities to manage all aspects of forest use." According to the FAO's newest brief, "20 [JFM] pilots were attempted in total, but nearly all were abandoned due to the lack of a clear legal framework along with other factors" (Bradley, Mickels-Kokwe, & Moombe, 2019).

As eluded, efforts have been put in place by the government to decentralize the management of forests in order to give locals more control over local decision-making. In order to improve

the quality of service delivery at the sub-national level, revised decentralization policy called for the devolution of decision-making authority, functions, responsibilities, and resources to the provincial, district, and sub-district levels for JFM to thrive. However, efforts to develop JFM in the nation have met with little success due to a number of difficulties, including institutional, technological, and financial (Mfune, 2011). Also, the developments in forest governance did not seem to have livelihood incentives for the ordinary citizens to participate in forest management. As a result, the government of Zambia along with governments around the world embarked on forest policy reforms to further incentivize PFM for sustainable forest management through community arrangements.

2.7.3 Forest Governance Policy Reforms and Community Based Forest Management

The year 2014 set precedence to the establishment of a clearer frame for forest management in order to overcome the shortcomings of the previous frameworks through the issuance of the 2014 National Forestry Policy. The policy laid strong emphasis on key issues such as sustainable use and management of forest resources including the goals of climate change, income generation, poverty reduction, job creation and the protection of biodiversity (GRZ, 2014). According to the policy, public participation in forestry is a means to an end, and community empowerment is central to participatory forest management. Hence it emphasizes that for adequate protection and management of forests to occur, local communities and traditional leaders ought to be empowered (GRZ, 2014).

The year 2015 also set a significant milestone for community forest governance in Zambia. The forest Act was passed to recognize a range of PFM approaches and the creation of new forest categories. Of the most significant category is the establishment of “community forest management” which provides a legal basis for communities living near or within a forest to obtain user rights, through a legal agreement with the forestry department. For the first time, communities were made eligible to obtain commercial rights in the use of forests apart from the subsistence rights that they already possessed. Apart from NTFRs such as honey, fuelwood, grazing or medicinal herbs, communities were now eligible for rights over timber products, eco-tourism, and plantation establishment (through non-resident cultivation) (Section 32 (2), 2015 forestry act of Zambia).

However, for communities to be eligible for these rights, the act gave a procedure through which they had to follow. Community groups needed to apply to be recognized as community forest management groups by the Forestry Department. Upon recognition, the established

CFMG may now enter into agreement with the Forestry Department to collaboratively manage forests. The agreement actually confers forest user rights to the group. Apart from that the group also has to prepare and implement the forest management plan. In this regard, the foundation for community forests on the two documents, the community forest management agreement and the community forest management plan. Hence, the practical aspect for the commencement of community forest management requires significant support from third party-facilitation and guidance from government to develop the required management plans. In addition to creating and putting into effect a forest management plan, some of the main duties of CFMGs include safeguarding and conserving the concerned forest area; and notifying and alerting the staff of the Forestry Department regarding management and risks to the forest (Davis et al., 2020).

The 2015 forestry act highlighted on the specific forests that are eligible for community forest such as open areas (land outside of officially designated protected areas where wild animals are found, often in customary areas) or local forests (forest reserves managed by local authorities with the Forestry Department) as long as there is no concession or sawmilling license (GRZ, 2015). The other significant aspect of the forestry act of 2015 is that under section 31 (4), it permits Community Resource Boards (CRBS) to apply for community forestry agreement “as if the community resource board were a community forest management group (GRZ, 2015a). This was further reinforced in Section 4 (1) of the 2018 Community Forest Regulations which states that community forest management may be applied in game management areas (GMAs). Most forest governance arrangements in GMAs were mostly under the auspices of Community Resource Management Areas which included the management of wildlife.

Hence in line with Bradely et al., (2019) who states that in Zambia community forest management is suitable for tenure types such as community forests; community woodlots; GMAs (customary); and forest reserves (statutory), the current study focuses on examining community governance arrangements such as CBNRM in forest dependent communities, particularly GMAs of South Luangwa National Park.

Another key provision of the Forests Act is that, if the local community or forest owner agrees to the declaration, a JFM area may be established by statutory instrument in a local forest, botanical reserve, plantation, private forest, or open area. The Act also calls for the creation of joint forest management committees (JFMCs) made up of nine to twelve members who

represent the chief, various government agencies, the local community, and other stakeholders. The JFMCs have a legislative obligation to create and carry out a forest management plan. This is a challenging process that calls for the creation of maps, engagement with local and international stakeholders, and a solid grasp of current laws governing lands, natural resources, and the environment. Therefore, outside facilitation and support are required (Bradely et al., 2019).

Table 7: Summary of key policy reforms for CBFM in Zambia post-independence

Forest Policy Reforms	Year
Zambian Forest Action Plan	1996
Forest Policy	1998
Forest Act	1998
S.I. 52	1999
S.I. 47	2006
Forest Policy	2010
S.I. 52	2013
Revised National Policy	2014
Forestry Act	2015
Community Forest Regulations	2018

Source: Generated by author

Private woodlands may also register with the Forestry Department under the 2015 woodlands Act for sustainable forest management. Under this arrangement, owners receive technical assistance, are exempt from production licenses, permits, and fees, and are given complete discretion over how to use and dispose of forest products. Evidence of tenure must be shown, such as a leasehold title deed or lease agreement, in order to engage in private forestry. Private forestry, which by definition favors larger, more formalized farmers and agricultural enterprises with official tenure paperwork, excludes smallholders with traditional or customary rights over land and woods (which includes the majority of households and small farmers). In the form of a statutory instrument, regulations pertaining to community forests were released in 2018 (GRZ, 2018).

The community forest regulations of 2018 give further detail on the permissive rights. Section 9 expressly states that the "community forest management area shall be for the exclusive use of the local community. Although it isn't stated directly, it seems that the money made from

harvesting in community woods isn't taxed or distributed to other tiers of government (GRZ, 2018).

2.7.4 Forest Governance Structural Challenges in Zambia

The importance of forests of forests remain undermined as estimates by GRZ (2016) indicate that between 79,000 and 150,000 ha of forest land is lost every year. Some of the key drivers of deforestation are strongly tied to the livelihoods of the rural communities i.e. fuel extraction, agricultural expansion, mining and infrastructure development. Another key background factor influencing the high rates of deforestation in the country as highlighted by Nansikombi et al., (2020) is the tenure and the governance context of the country. The tenure arrangement of forest resources in the country is organized in such a way that 82% of forest in the country are found on customary lands making the management and user rights to be overlapping and contesting among those of local authorities, local governments and national governments as these all hold various rights. The rights of these entities are defined in law but they are not enforced and they provide contradictory incentives for effective forest management.

a) Statutory Forest Governance Arrangements

This type is characterized by tenure systems applied by governments and codified by law (Charnley and Poe). The Forest Department of the Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources - under the ministry of green economy and environment is the central government organization with a legislative obligation to manage forest resources. The formulation, review, and coordination of all regulations pertaining to forest management fall under the purview of the forest department (Chileshe, 2001; Ministry of Tourism, Environment and Natural Resources, 2009). The provincial, district, and sub-district administration units, often known as the area and ward, make up the sub-national government levels. According to the forestry strategy and current legal framework, the provincial and district units are in charge of creating and implementing bylaws and assisting the appropriate and efficient administration of forest estate (Chileshe, 2001; Ministry of Tourism, Environment and Natural Resources, 2009). Additionally, the district unit is in charge of managing forest woodlots and plantations, providing extension services, collecting revenue from the sale of forest products, enforcing regulations through patrols and licenses, and coordinating lower administrative levels. Zambia currently consists of 10 provinces and 117 districts, with a district council serving as the primary policy- and decision-making body in each district. The Area Development Committees (ADCs) are the council's representatives at the sub-district level. The ADCs are locally elected,

democratic organizations of government that must collaborate with representatives from each ward to create strategies for managing natural resources and take part in their development (GZR, 2015).

b) Customary forest Governance arrangements

This kind is characterized by tenure systems established by custom or tradition and determined at the local level, rather than by law or contract, often based on oral agreements (Charnley and Poe). Within each district, the Constitution of the Republic of Zambia guarantees a robust customary administrative framework that runs concurrently with the aforementioned political administration (Mason-Case, 2011). According to Mason-Case (2011), customary government is comprised of 73 tribes with 240 chiefs, 8 senior chiefs, and 4 paramount chiefs who assign duties and rights to head people and sub-chiefs under their control. According to regional customs, traditional authorities are required to manage customary lands. On customary land, traditional authorities decide on land use, access, and user rights. Traditional institutions must be consulted before any political administration actions are taken on customary lands because political administration frequently has little control over traditional administration. However, in reality, the central government is reluctant to give local governments control over protected forests (Mfunne, 2013). Additionally, managing open forests is beyond the financial, human, and technical means of local government. Likewise, conflicting land tenure policies restrict local government's ability to manage customary forests (Chikulo, 2009). While the District Council is mandated by the Local Government Act of 1991 to plan and oversee the management of customary forests, the administration of these lands is under the control of customary authorities under the 1995 Land Act. Additionally, customary authorities occasionally contest the legitimacy of the sub-district governance arrangements (Mfunne, 2013).

Since traditional authorities such as chiefs have already established authorities to administer customary land for purposes (such as communal grazing, charcoal production, brick making and timber collection for subsistence use), most forest land has been converted to agricultural land with the process itself being overseen by the headmen. The practice of traditional authorities managing the forest for subsistence use, while the central government via the forestry department manages the 'same forest' for commercial purposes has contributed to the high rates of deforestation. More unsustainable, and illicit harvesting of forest resources became the normal order of things in those communities as the monetary benefit was only left to the central government whereas monetary opportunities for the locals was very limited and highly regulated. Also, Area Development Committees (ADCs) are in theory the official focal

point of local collective action for the enhancement of the environment and livelihoods on customary lands, these governance structures in practice appeared to be dysfunctional and are not regarded as a political administrative unit in some communities (Mfune, 2013).

2.7.5 The Role of REDD+ in the Evolution of Forest Governance in Zambia

As the REDD+ initiative was being developed, there were concerns about challenges faced by forest communities, particularly indigenous groups, in securing formal tenure over forest land and carbon rights. Governments in many regions claimed statutory rights to large portions of forest land, leaving customary or informal rights of local communities unrecognized, which would exclude them from REDD benefits (Springate-Baginski, O. and Wollenberg, 2010).

As noted in the Zambia's evolution of forest governance, at some point there were risks of poorly defined or ambiguous rights, which can lead to the capture of REDD benefits by elites or the state, exacerbating inequality and would thus reduce the effectiveness of carbon markets. Additionally, the formalization of rights, while important, would marginalize poor communities and undermine customary governance structures. Hence while clearly defined, legitimate tenure was essential for REDD's success, ideally it was to be approached carefully to avoid social exclusion or conflict. In the short term, emphasis was to be placed on shared rights and equitable benefit distribution, with legal reforms pursued alongside thorough consultation to ensure fairness and stability (Springate-Baginski, O. and Wollenberg, 2010).

The recognition of the stagnation in participatory forest management (managerial and political) (Bojang, 2013 and Mfune, 2011), and the influence of the international community led the government of Zambia to embrace REDD as an opportunity to directly address the drivers of deforestation and forest degradation in pursuit of its long-term development vision that emphasizes poverty reduction and development based on “sustainable environment and natural resource management principles” (Vision 2030). In REDD design there was emphasis on the importance of governance and political participation in the successful implementation of REDD (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation) initiatives. Poor governance was identified as a key driver of deforestation and forest degradation, often due to illegal activities, corruption, and the lack of participation from local communities and civil society. Good governance in REDD+ design went beyond managing funds and monitoring results; it included recognizing forest and carbon rights, ensuring transparency, and enforcing laws against illegal activities (Springate-Baginski, O. and Wollenberg, 2010).

Historically, local communities have had limited influence, meaningful political participation by forest communities in the design and implementation of REDD programs, was not only important for effective forest management but also a matter of social justice. Decentralization of decision-making to local governments or community-based forestry projects has been shown to improve outcomes. However, Springate-Maginski and Wollenberg (2010) note that achieving ideal governance may be difficult in practice, and calls for a more pragmatic approach, supporting the emergence of good governance over time rather than expecting immediate reforms. Political challenges were considered in implementing REDD, noting that achieving reforms often requires compromise and the involvement of powerful stakeholders. In this context, "good enough" governance might be a practical goal, with the recognition that REDD initiatives should aim to support long-term governance improvements, despite the complex political realities on the ground (Springate-Baginski, O. and Wollenberg, 2010).

REDD programs further emphasized that past programs were most effective when they incorporated decision-making by local institutions, including local governments, civil society organizations, and customary institutions. A nested approach, which integrates both national and local efforts was likely to be the most successful. This approach addresses large-scale drivers of deforestation at the national level while considering local drivers and institutional conditions at the subnational level. Initiatives such as the Payments for Environmental Services (PES) proved to be more successful when tailored to local contexts and adapted to the specific conditions of each area. It suggests that uniform, one-size-fits-all programs can result in uneven outcomes, as local conditions such as property rights, culture, and politics differ from place to place. While user-funded PES schemes tend to be more effective than government-run ones, they also present challenges, such as higher transaction costs and limited local capacities for implementation. Also complexity of working at smaller scales, noting that local institutions often lack the knowledge, capacity, and effective communication needed for successful implementation. Additionally, local institutions cannot operate in isolation and must be understood in relation to other institutions, like local governments and ethnic associations (Springate-Baginski, O. and Wollenberg, 2010).

As one of nine pilot nations, Zambia was chosen to get first "quick start" assistance to set up a national REDD+ readiness process through a National Joint Programme (NJP). The UN-REDD initiative aimed at determining if carefully designed payment mechanisms and capacity assistance can generate the incentives necessary to assure long-term, attainable, dependable,

and measurable emission reductions while maintaining and enhancing other ecological services that forests provide (Nansikombi et al., 2020).

Through the UN-REDD support in the REDD+ readiness process, Zambia completed its national REDD+ strategy that incorporates improved forest governance from the planning stage (Matakala et al., 2015). The National Strategy to Reduce Emissions from Deforestation and Degradation of the nation (March 2017) places a strong emphasis on community involvement in the sustainable management of land and natural resources. The Zambia's National Development Plan 2017–2021 (Ministry of National Development Planning, 2017) is also another framework which calls for improved forest governance in Zambia includes within the national strategy for the REDD+, with Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) is as an overarching theme.

According to MCPFE (1993) SFM is “the stewardship and use of forest lands in a way and at a rate that maintains their productivity, biodiversity, productivity, regeneration capacity, vitality and their potential to fulfil now and in the future relevant ecological, economic and social functions at local, national and global levels and that does not cause damage to other ecosystems.” It was thus emphasized within the national REDD+ strategy of Zambia to expand the Participatory Forest Management (PFM) agenda from the JFM foundation to include other forms such as Community Forest Management (CFM) and Private Forest Management (PvFM) (UNDP et al., 2010). Threats and leakages will be less likely thanks to the creation of community buffers through CFM and JFM around high-conservation value supporters. Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), out-grower agreements in collaboration with the commercial sector, and sustainable charcoal and wood fuel production may be taken into account (UNREDD-FAO-MLNREP 2012). This hybrid approach is envisaged to improve the security of National Forest boundaries and lessen the dangers associated with upcoming infrastructure and mining growth.

The possibilities for integrated community-based natural resources management (the engagement of local/traditional authorities and communities) have grown significantly in the context of REDD+ and the enhanced freedom for maneuver created by the Forests Act of 2015 and the more recent Community Forest Management Regulations (2018). In these processes, it was established for the FD to continue to undertake a central role. And that projects and activities must be adjusted to local specificities, given that communities across the nation are characterized by socio-cultural diversity. Thus, the National REDD+ strategy recognizes that

a variety of institutions, competencies, skills, and other resources must be gathered for SFM and rural livelihoods (GRZ, 2018).

To that effect, the Government and development partners have embarked on a series of programmes and projects that have considered the deficiencies identified. Others significant REDD pilot/demonstration projects that were implemented simultaneously included the USAID/CIFPR projects in Eastern Province and the one by BioCarbon Partners (BCP) in Central Province both aiming at reducing deforestation and degradation around elements of JFM and community resource management. By adopting Community Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM) as a method of implementing REDD in compliance with safeguards, Zambia shares this characteristic with the majority of other nations taking part in the UN-REDD programme (Blom et al., 2010; Phelps et al., 2010).

The following section highlights on empirical studies on the effect of Community Forest Governance on livelihoods; the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance; and the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihoods. The gap that the current research attempts to fill is presented at the end of the empirical studies.

2.8 Empirical Review

This section highlights the review of the various empirical studies that have been conducted on the effects among the identified variables. The reviewed studies are done on topics such as community forest governance and livelihoods; REDD+ and community forest governance practices; and studies on REDD+ and livelihoods. The research gap is stated afterwards as a basis for the current study.

2.8.1 Community Forest Governance and Livelihoods

The studies reviewed emphasize key aspects of community-based forest management (CBFM) and participatory forest management (PFM), particularly in relation to livelihoods, governance structures, and their impacts on equity and poverty alleviation. A common finding across multiple studies is that while CFM and PFM contribute to improving livelihoods, their impact on poverty reduction is often limited and unequal. Pelletier et al. (2016) found that CFM improved livelihoods but had a limited effect on poverty reduction, particularly in terms of equitable benefit distribution. This resonates with the findings of Agrawal and Gibson (1999), who observed that CFM governance often undermines equity, particularly disadvantaging poorer households and women-headed households. Social inequality, including gender

disparities, tends to be reinforced in the absence of effective governance structures, as highlighted by Edmunds & Wollenberg (2003) and Schreckenberg & Luttrell (2009). Wealthier and more powerful community members often dominate governance processes, exacerbating these inequalities.

Several studies highlight that weak governance structures undermine the benefits that these programs could offer. In Nepal, Malla (2000) and Malla et al. (2008) noted that decentralization and devolution of forest management resulted in negative effects for the poorest households, who faced reduced access to forest products due to stricter harvesting regulations. Similarly, Vyamana (2009) found that devolved management in Tanzania excluded the poor from income-generating opportunities due to the high initial investment costs required to participate. In Ethiopia, Gobeze et al. (2009) showed that, despite positive short-term outcomes, the sustainability of PFM was undermined by weak government support. Zambian (Rukundo, 2018) and Cameroonian (Piabuo et al., 2018) studies confirm that insufficient government backing, along with poor governance practices, often limits local participation and the long-term effectiveness of these forest management programs. Both studies stress the importance of effective governance to ensure that forest management systems are inclusive and sustainable.

The type of forest products available and the quality of forests under CFM/CFM arrangements play a significant role in determining whether these programs can produce sustainable and equitable economic benefits. In Ethiopia, Ameha et al. (2014) found that access to timber harvesting increased income and asset levels for forest user group members. This underscores the importance of access rights to high-value forest products in determining the economic success of CFM. However, in regions where forests have been degraded, such as those reported in Nepal (Maharjan, 2009), Mozambique (Chomitz et al., 2007), and Tanzania, CFM can fail to provide sufficient financial benefits due to poor forest quality. The quality of governance in managing these forests and ensuring sustainable practices becomes paramount to avoiding this pitfall.

Complementary livelihoods also play a key role in the success of CFM and PFM. Studies by Gobeze et al. (2009) and Abebe (2021) show that diversifying income sources beyond forest-based activities helps reduce dependence on forests, enhancing economic resilience. These complementary activities (e.g., agriculture, livestock) can boost household income levels and asset accumulation while enabling communities to buffer against forest degradation. However, without complementary livelihood interventions, the financial sustainability of CFM and PFM

can be limited (Rukundo, 2018). Household income diversification is key to improving economic outcomes, as shown in Ethiopia and Zambia.

In Nepal (Adhikari & Falco, 2008), Zambia (Rukundo, 2018), and Uganda (Mawa et al., 2021), community forestry programs have demonstrated positive impacts on rural livelihoods but also highlight significant disparities in participation and benefits. Wealthier and more educated households are more likely to be involved in decision-making and reap the financial rewards, while marginalized groups especially lower-caste individuals in Nepal and women in Zambia are often underrepresented in governance structures. The unequal distribution of benefits, often favoring elites or external actors, has hindered the full potential of these programs in reducing poverty and improving equity. These studies collectively emphasize the importance of inclusive decision-making processes and targeted interventions to ensure that the benefits of forest management reach all community members.

Governance is also explored in depth by Okpoko (2019), who focused on the role of customary laws and local governance in sustainable forest management in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Okpoko found that the integration of customary laws and local institutions significantly increased community participation in forest management. This finding aligns with Piabuo et al. (2018) in Cameroon, where strong governance practices contributed to improved community participation, representation, and empowerment of indigenous groups like the Baka. Both studies emphasize that effective governance structures, incorporating local customs and traditions, can improve engagement, equitable distribution of benefits, and long-term forest sustainability.

Studies from Mozambique (Siteo & Guedes, 2011), Philippines (Hashiguchi et al., 2016), and Cameroon (Beauchamp & Ingram, 2011) discuss the challenges local communities face in balancing conservation and livelihood needs. While community forestry initiatives often improve forest conditions and resource management, they do not always result in substantial financial benefits. In Mozambique, for example, forest-based income was insufficient to meet household needs, with agriculture and other activities competing for attention. Similarly, in the Philippines, while CBFM improved forest conditions, it did not lead to significant income increases. These findings suggest that economic diversification, through alternative income sources and forest-based enterprises, plays a crucial role in achieving long-term sustainability.

In Cameroon (Beauchamp & Ingram, 2011), Zambia (Rukundo, 2018), and Indonesia (Kaskoyo, 2017), weak governance structures and insufficient legal frameworks undermine the

success of community-based management. In Cameroon, the 1994 Forestry Law was criticized for its failure to decentralize authority and empower local communities. Similarly, in Zambia, the lack of clear benefit-sharing mechanisms and legal rights for local communities hindered the effectiveness of Participatory Forest Management (PFM). In Indonesia, the study pointed to challenges in ensuring sustainable forest management due to governance issues and increasing land demand. These findings highlight the need for stronger legal frameworks and the devolution of decision-making to local communities to foster more effective and equitable forest governance.

External support in the form of training, technical assistance, and financial resources is consistently identified as crucial for the success of community forest programs. This was evident in Mozambique (Siteo & Guedes, 2011), Namibia (Leonard & Lileka, 2024), and China (Chen et al., 2012), where external support was necessary for effective community engagement in forest management. In Namibia, for example, while community forests provided valuable resources, limited government support hindered long-term success. Similarly, in Mozambique, external support such as financing and training was critical for community participation but not sufficient to ensure that forest-based income alone could support local households. These studies underscore the importance of sustained technical and financial support to empower local communities and improve forest management outcomes.

Lastly, Abebe (2021) and Gobeze et al. (2009) in Ethiopia showed that PFM can improve household income and asset levels, but these outcomes are often dependent on stronger governance frameworks. PFM members showed significant increases in forest-related income (Abebe), and these impacts were more evident when complementary interventions such as agricultural support and access to markets were integrated into forest management systems. However, like other studies, the lack of effective governance and insufficient government support were identified as key challenges.

2.8.2 REDD+ and Community Forest Governance Practices

The literature on REDD+ highlights the persistent challenges of governance, equity, and local community integration into climate change mitigation frameworks. While REDD+ is often framed globally as a tool for environmental justice, many studies reveal a gap between these ideals and the realities of local implementation, where the needs and rights of local communities are sometimes overlooked.

Johnson (2021) critiques the implementation of REDD+ in Ghana, arguing that although environmental justice is acknowledged in policy documents, it is depoliticized in practice. This disconnect between theory and practice is particularly evident in the concentration of state control over forest resources, which marginalizes local communities, particularly in rural areas. The study highlights the limitations of REDD+ in achieving sustainable development and empowering local actors. Similarly, Gautum et al. (2021) explore the challenges faced by REDD+ in Nepal, where an emphasis on carbon outcomes has overshadowed local needs such as access to forest products and income generation. The involvement of new actors in pilot projects has been promising, but local participation in decision-making remains insufficient, complicating efforts to decentralize forest governance. Their findings underscore the need to balance climate mitigation priorities with the livelihood needs of local communities.

In contrast, Osei (2024) and Morgan et al. (2023) present more optimistic views on the potential of REDD+ to improve governance through collaborative frameworks. Osei's study of the Ghana Cocoa Forest REDD+ Programme (GCFRP) stresses the importance of recognizing the interdependence of stakeholders in managing forest resources. The study shows that successful REDD+ implementation requires shared knowledge, collective action, and cross-sector leadership. Similarly, Morgan et al. (2023) highlight the potential of REDD+ to enhance governance in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), despite challenges such as political instability. Their research identifies key success factors, including capacity-building, community consultations, and long-term partnerships, suggesting that collaborative governance models can address structural weaknesses in REDD+ implementation.

A recurring challenge across several studies is the equitable distribution of benefits. Soliev (2021) analyzes benefit-sharing dynamics in REDD+ programs in Ghana, Tanzania, Cameroon, and Uganda, distinguishing between appropriation-oriented and provision-oriented models. The study identifies systemic challenges to equitable benefit-sharing, such as weak land tenure systems, conflicts between agricultural and conservation interests, and the concentration of benefits among a few powerful actors. These issues exacerbate existing inequalities and hinder the effectiveness of REDD+ in promoting both environmental sustainability and equitable livelihoods. In a related study, Flores (2023) examines the role of Indigenous Peoples' organizations (IPOs) in shaping Peru's national REDD+ policy. The study highlights how IPOs have employed a rights-based and equity-focused approach to influence REDD+ governance, leading to more inclusive coordination with the Peruvian state. This case

underscores how Indigenous leadership can foster more equitable REDD+ outcomes by ensuring local perspectives are integrated into national policies.

The role of local governance and community participation is also emphasized as crucial for the success of REDD+ initiatives. Both Poudel et al. (2015) and Satyal et al. (2020) investigate the social equity implications of REDD+ in Nepal's community forestry system. Poudel et al. (2015) find that while marginalized groups, such as women-headed households, received targeted support, the benefits were insufficient to address deeper issues of inequality. Similarly, Satyal et al. (2020) reveal that while some social groups, particularly indigenous women, benefited from REDD+ initiatives, others, such as Dalit women, continued to face political and social exclusion. The study highlights that entrenched social inequalities hinder the effective operationalization of environmental justice in REDD+.

Scheba (2018) and Corbera et al. (2020) explore how governance practices in Tanzania and participatory forest management schemes affect REDD+ outcomes. Scheba's study identifies challenges such as mismatched governance structures and political tensions in rural communities. She advocates for more flexible and context-specific approaches to REDD+ implementation. Similarly, Corbera et al. (2020) found that while some positive income changes were observed, they were unrelated to enhanced forestry revenues, and participant villages did not experience significant improvements in wealth indicators. These findings suggest that REDD+ may have limited impact on local wealth and welfare without addressing broader socio-economic factors.

Hajjar et al. (2021) provide a broader perspective on REDD+ and decentralized forest governance systems, particularly community forests. Their systematic review found that while REDD+ improved participation and cross-scale connectivity, it also imposed restrictive rules that limited local adaptive management. The study emphasizes the need for policymakers to ensure that REDD+ initiatives allow communities to retain adaptive capacity and respond effectively to environmental or economic changes.

Across these studies, the importance of governance reforms, local participation, and equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms is clear. While there is considerable variation in the effectiveness of REDD+ across different contexts, these studies collectively highlight the need for inclusive, flexible approaches that prioritize the needs and rights of local communities alongside environmental goals. By addressing these challenges, REDD+ has the potential to contribute

not only to forest conservation but also to the empowerment of marginalized groups and the promotion of sustainable livelihoods.

2.8.3 REDD+ and Rural Livelihoods

The literature on REDD+ initiatives emphasizes the significant challenges and opportunities associated with improving local livelihoods while simultaneously achieving forest conservation and carbon sequestration goals. A central theme across multiple studies is the interplay between livelihoods and environmental outcomes, and how REDD+ can be structured to both support local communities and contribute to climate goals. Fischer et al. (2023) highlight the crucial role of local governance and community involvement in REDD+ success, finding that formal community management associations and local participation are strong predictors of positive outcomes in forest restoration. Kim (2023) supports this, underscoring that social capital and community forest governance are key to improving both livelihoods and forest management in Cambodia and Myanmar. Furthermore, Andoh et al. (2024) show that aligning social safeguards with local well-being in Ghana enhances the effectiveness of REDD+ initiatives, advocating for stronger Benefit Sharing Mechanisms and better access to markets and communication networks for local communities.

Several studies explore the dual challenge of enhancing livelihoods while achieving environmental goals, revealing the complex dynamics between forest conservation efforts and local economic needs. Andoh et al. (2024) investigate the Ghana Shea Landscape Emission Reductions Project (GSLERP), identifying key drivers of deforestation such as bushfires and illegal logging. Their study highlights the importance of addressing these drivers through enhanced livelihood capital, particularly access to resources and income-generating opportunities. Similarly, Nantongo et al. (2024) find that while REDD+ projects in Tanzania lead to increased forest-based incomes and enhanced carbon storage, the trade-offs between improving livelihoods and achieving environmental benefits remain significant. These results are consistent with those of Groom & Palmer (2012), who identify similar tensions in the N'hambita Community Carbon Project in Mozambique and China's Sloping Lands Conversion Program (SLCP), where tenure insecurity, market dependence, and sustainability issues pose challenges to achieving long-term success.

Land tenure is another critical factor influencing the livelihoods benefits of REDD+ projects. Theresia (2023) observes that projects involving community land tenure holders tend to offer stronger tenure-related benefits, while those in private land tenure contexts often fail to provide

equitable outcomes. This aligns with the findings of Demarchi et al. (2022), who argue that clarifying land tenure rights and offering alternative livelihoods can help mitigate deforestation and promote sustainable agricultural practices. In Melanesia, Sha & Race (2024) call for policy reforms to address equity concerns, such as gender marginalization and insecure land tenure, to improve the effectiveness of REDD+ projects and enhance local livelihoods.

The sustainability of REDD+ projects is a further concern, particularly in relation to their ability to provide long-term livelihood benefits. Several studies point out the risks of short-term incentives leading to the abandonment of conservation efforts. Groom & Palmer (2012) warn that in Mozambique's N'hambita project, livelihoods may shift away from carbon sequestration, potentially undermining the long-term sustainability of carbon sinks. In Melanesia, Sha & Race (2024) report limited adoption of REDD+ due to barriers such as inadequate stakeholder engagement and a lack of sustainable livelihoods. Nantongo et al. (2024) also caution that economic crises and the absence of safety nets could lead to forest exploitation, compromising the environmental goals of REDD+ projects.

Several studies propose specific policy recommendations to improve the equity and effectiveness of REDD+ initiatives in supporting local livelihoods. Andoh et al. (2024) advocate for reforms in tenancy laws, enhanced access to financial services, and improved market access to reduce risks and support sustainable livelihoods in Ghana. Nantongo et al. (2024) emphasize the need for stronger forest governance and the involvement of NGOs with local knowledge to ensure that both livelihood improvements and environmental goals are met. Theresia (2023) highlights the importance of designing tailored benefit-sharing mechanisms that consider land tenure, financial sources, and regional contexts to ensure equitable and sustainable outcomes for local communities.

In addition to these broader findings, several studies examine the specific effects of REDD+ on local livelihoods in different regions. Ken et al. (2020) conducted a livelihoods-focused study in Cambodia, assessing the impact of REDD+ on local assets before and during project implementation. While the study finds a slight increase in livelihood assets, it also notes a sharp decline in natural capital, primarily due to illegal logging. The study suggests that strict enforcement and the development of reliable financial mechanisms are necessary to ensure sustainable livelihoods and mitigate the negative effects of carbon market volatility. Similarly, Atela et al. (2015) argue that the success of REDD+ in Kenya depends heavily on local assets, such as water access and land tenure, and the role of state institutions in shaping the interactions

between these assets and the project's objectives. They contend that while pro-poor initiatives are essential, the broader institutional context, including national reforms and global carbon pricing, must align with local livelihood needs to achieve effective REDD+ outcomes.

Other studies, such as those by Kapinga (2015) in Tanzania and Loaizia et al. (2015) in Ecuador, also highlight the limited financial incentives provided by REDD+ projects and the weak willingness of local communities to participate in forest conservation activities due to insufficient compensation. Shrestha et al. (2017) find that while REDD+ payments offered economic benefits to the poorest households, these payments were insufficient to support significant livelihood-enhancing activities. Additionally, they highlight the role of household wealth disparities in the distribution of benefits, which sometimes leads to social tension.

Studies in private tenure contexts, such as Manda and Mukanda (2023) in Zambia, reveal that REDD+ projects under private tenure arrangements often exacerbate inequalities and limit community agency. The study finds that although some infrastructure development occurred through carbon payments, REDD+ activities were narrow and failed to address broader community needs, reinforcing existing inequalities. This points to the challenges of implementing REDD+ in private tenure arrangements, where resource restrictions and unequal benefit-sharing mechanisms can undermine community participation and long-term success.

In conclusion, the literature on REDD+ highlights the importance of integrating local livelihood needs with environmental goals to ensure the success and sustainability of forest conservation initiatives. While governance, tenure rights, and financial mechanisms are crucial factors in improving local livelihoods, challenges such as tenure insecurity, market volatility, and inadequate stakeholder engagement must be addressed. Ultimately, the effectiveness of REDD+ depends on a holistic approach that considers local context, equitable benefit-sharing, and long-term sustainability to ensure both environmental protection and the improvement of livelihoods.

2.8.4 Research Gap

The gap in literature on community forestry and REDD+ focuses on the lack of comprehensive studies on within-community governance and its impact on forest conservation and livelihoods, particularly in Zambia. While extensive research exists on government-community relations, there is limited exploration of local governance structures, especially within community forest management groups. Current studies often concentrate on specific issues without addressing the broader factors that contribute to successful outcomes or their scalability. REDD+ initiatives have introduced both opportunities and challenges, including governance decentralization and risks like elite capture. More research is needed on context-specific governance models that promote inclusivity, accountability, and long-term sustainability. Additionally, further investigation is required on how to effectively align local livelihoods with environmental goals to ensure that REDD+ and community forest management contribute to both poverty alleviation and forest conservation

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents a detailed explanation on the entire process of addressing the research problem in a logical and systematic manner. It provides explanations on the study area, research design, population of study, sources of data, methods of data collection, methods of data analysis, validity and reliability, and ethical considerations.

3.1 A Profile of Forest Areas in Zambia

Zambia is one of Africa's most resource-rich countries. Roughly two-thirds of Zambia's land area is forested, and nearly 40 percent of the land area is contained within a network of national parks and forest reserves, and co-managed areas that overlap with customary community lands. In terms of land proportion, State protected areas such as national parks cover about eight percent of Zambia's land area, while forest reserves cover ten percent of the country. Game management areas (GMAs), which overlap with customary lands and include many settlements, cover approximately an additional 23 percent of the country (Davis et al., 2020).

According to Mukosha and Siampale (2009), 24% of Zambia's forest area is on state territory, while the remaining 56% is on privately owned land. The majority of Zambia's forest acreage (63%) is located on customary grounds. The national parks and wildlife management areas, both overseen by the Zambia Wildlife Authority, are included in the state's land holdings. In national parks, living resources cannot be extracted without a permit. Although they are inhabited and a variety of industries, including as timber extraction, mining, and small-scale farming, are permitted there, game management areas function as buffer zones around the national parks (Richardson et al. 2012). Forests in 178 national and 307 local forest reserves under the management of the Forestry Department total little under 7.7 million ha. (GRZ, 2015; ZFD 2012; and Kalinda et al., 2008). According to formal legislation, using forest resources in state forests is only permitted with certain permits. State lands also contain private forests, making up 10.6% of the total forest area. Through leasehold tenure, registered individuals or businesses are the owners of these (Davis et al., 2020).

The national forests, some of which are located within game management areas, are protected regions created with the goals of preserving biodiversity, ecosystems, and forest resources. These are a part of the state's property and are off-limits to habitation and agriculture, albeit a permit is required to access them and make use of the forest resources. With a similar goal but a focus on helping local communities, local forest reserves are on customary land. The removal

of forest products and other operations, such as agriculture, also call for licenses. Some of the forest reserves have been over-exploited to the point that they have been de-gazetted, or they have been encroached upon by burgeoning agriculture and settlements (Campbell et al. 2010).

Land use in GMAs is effectively under the control of traditional authorities and shaped by local livelihood and land use decisions. These areas, which include key buffer zones and migratory corridors between national parks, depend heavily on community engagement and local conservation measures. The Department of National Parks and Wildlife (DNPW) has wildlife management and planning responsibilities in these GMAs; thus, balancing community and state rights and responsibilities has a critical role in effective management. (Davis et al., 2020).

As the focus of this study, there has been significant forest loss and degradation in and around GMAs, and adjacent undesignated customary lands, as a result of open access exploitation and the lack of clear legal provisions to provide for community-level management and sustainable harvesting of forest products. While this forest loss and degradation may not be as dramatic as expansion around urban areas, human expansion in GMAs has a large impact on both forests and wildlife populations.

3.1.1 Description of Study Site

Nyimba District in the Eastern Province is mostly made up of the Nsenga and Chewa ethnic groups. Maize, sunflower, and cotton are the principal crops grown by the neighborhood's population. In the Nyimba district, tree cutting for charcoal and timber is also frequent. Timber harvesting, charcoal manufacture, photographic tourism, and safari hunting firms are among additional economic activities in the Luangwa Valley. According to Umar and Kapembwa (2020), the area's dominant ethnic group is the Kunda, and ChiKunda is the primary language used there. ChiBisa and ChiChewa are also spoken.

Due to deforestation, the amount of forest cover in Eastern Province has decreased during the past 20 years. Between 2000 and 2014, a total of 156,000 hectares of forest were destroyed. Increased unsustainable forest usage is likely due to the rise in deforestation. According to a preliminary report prepared for REDD+, deforestation primarily takes place along the country's railway from the south to the Copperbelt, although new hotspots are beginning to emerge also distant from the railway (Vinya et al., 2012).

According to Vinya et al. (2012), infrastructural development, wood exploitation, smallholder subsistence shifting cropping, and fires are the primary causes of deforestation. The loss of

biodiversity and genetic resources of many tree species is one effect of deforestation, endangering their survival or potential future use (Forestry-Department 2016). The National Strategy to Reduce Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+), created in 2014, aims to address the various factors that contribute to deforestation in the forestry industry as well as other major sectors including agriculture, energy, mining, and infrastructure. By 2030, the strategy aims to support a thriving economy that is resilient to climate change and is based on the sustainable management and use of the country's natural resources for better lifestyles (GRZ, 2014).

Figure 3: Location of study area (A= Chinambi, B = Kaliwe, C = Mombe)
Source: Author's Construction

3.2 Research design

In order to collect data for this project, a mixed methods approach was used, integrating components of quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Mixed methods supported data collection and integration of socio-economic and ecological data, providing a deep understanding of complex socio-ecological systems in the Luangwa Game Management Areas

in Nyimba district of Eastern province. This research is interdisciplinary and examines the multifaceted interactions between socio-economic issues, institutional governance, and ecological conditions. This was accomplished by using a variety of data sources, including surveys, in-depth interviews, focus groups and participant observation, which will support data triangulation and corroboration, increased the study's scientific rigor, and strengthened the validity of the findings (White et al., 2005; Salkind, 2010).

In order to overcome the rigidity and bias that come with employing a single method, conservation research is increasingly using mixed methods approaches to acquire a better understanding of the phenomenon being studied (McKim, 2017; Creswell, 2014; Johnson et al., 2007). For instance, Lund et al. (2014) used a mixed method approach to evaluate the effects of community forest governance on outcomes for livelihood and forest conservation in Tanzania. The author used qualitative interviews to evaluate the methods of forest management, which they connected to biophysical proof from measurements of the forest inventory. Using a similar methodology, Lonn et al. (2018) evaluated the performance of a community-based initiative in Cambodia by examining changes in forest cover from 2000 to 2012 using locals' opinions and globally published maps. In order to gather more detailed and comprehensive information about conservation management practices, socioeconomic data, and ecological information, as well as to explicitly understand people's perceptions, values, preferences, and attitudes (Sutherland et al., 2014; Creswell, 2014), qualitative methods complement one another and are used in conservation research (Sutherland et al., 2014; Creswell, 2014).

3.3 Target population

The primary target population consisted of forest dependent households in Nyimba District; whereas the secondary targets consisted of government officials from the Ministry of Green economy and Environment – forestry department, Ministry of tourism and wildlife, and the ministry of local government and rural development; and lastly, the officials facilitating the REDD+ project, the Bio Carbon partners (BCP); World wide Fund for Nature (WWF) and the Community Markets for Conservation (COMACO). Using the triangulation technique of data collection, it was hoped that the current research obtained an accurate picture of forest governance practices at community level and associated livelihood outcomes.

3.4 Sampling frame and Sampling technique

The primary respondents of the study (households) were selected through random sampling techniques to ensure representativeness. A register was obtained from the REDD+ implementing partners comprising all the villages/households under CFMGs/CRMGs. Based on this information, a representative sample was derived based on the following formula.

$$\text{Sample Size} = \frac{(Z\text{-Score}) \times 2 \text{Std Dev} \times (1 - \text{Std Dev})}{\text{Confidence Interval} \times 2}$$

Using 95% confidence level, a standard deviation of 0.5 and a confidence interval (margin of error) of $\pm 5\%$ the following is the calculation of the sample size.

$$\frac{((1.96)2 \times .5(.5))}{.0025} = \frac{.9604}{.0025} = 384.16$$

A sampling fraction was derived and applied to ensure that each proportion representing an implementation partner is neither over represented or under represented.

For the secondary respondents (for soliciting qualitative data), the study adopted a combination of purposive and snowballing sampling to select respondents for the study. These techniques are considered appropriate for the study because the researcher attempted to solicit information from individuals who are deemed specialized and very knowledgeable on the topics mainly because they are involved in the implementation processes. These individuals were purposely selected from the secondary target population described above. Afterwards, the snowballing techniques was used to identify more departments and individuals more specialized in addressing the research questions of the study.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were considered in this study to ensure that data was collected according to scientifically acceptable standards. With regards to the administering the interviews, first, the researcher introduced himself then obtained consent from the participants to be interviewed. This process was important for the purpose of ensuring that participants clearly understood risks of participating if any, the levels and nature of participation, and given the assurance of confidentiality (Giordano, et al 2007;48 Sarantakos, 2005). Other ethical procedures involved during data collection obtaining permission to access the respondents or premises where other respondents were located. In most cases it required presentation of an official letter from the Pan African University and an official clearance letter from the ethics committee (University

of Zambia. The researcher made efforts to ensure that the interviews are conducted with minimal disturbances and within the agreed upon time (Creswell, 2009).

3.6 Data Collection

This section highlights the various data types and their associated sources deployed in the current study. The study consists of both primary data and secondary data as described below.

3.6.1 Primary Data

This type of data was collected in the field using administered questionnaires and Focus Group Discussions (FDGs) for the primary respondents; and interview guides will be used for the key informants.

a) Qualitative Data

Methods used to collect qualitative data for the current study comprised of in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

3.6.1.1 In-depth Interviews

According to Young et al., (2018) qualitative approaches such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and participant observation are essential for gathering ecological and socioeconomic information on specific conservation concerns (Young et al., 2018). These methods are employed to fill in knowledge gaps and enhance understanding, particularly when researching complex behaviors (Reddy et al., 2017; Minichiello et al., 2008). In addition, qualitative methods are frequently used in conservation research to discuss individual experiences and perceptions about a specific topic, attitudes, beliefs, motivations, and/or conservation practices (Nyumba et al., 2018; Bennett, 2016). All of these factors can be difficult to measure using quantitative methods.

In-depth interviews, focus groups, and participant observation are some of the qualitative techniques this study will employ to evaluate the importance of ecosystem services, local attitudes toward them, perceptions of governance and implementation, and socioeconomic/livelihood effects of PFM. Open-ended inquiries and probing were permitted through qualitative methods like in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, which will result in nuanced knowledge and rich narrative descriptions of the impact, perceptions/beliefs, experiences, and preferences of PFM. Understanding residents' conservation-related behaviors depends on their ideas and perceptions about the governance structures of CFMGs as they

relate to openness, accountability, inclusion in decision-making, and equity in benefit sharing (Bennett, 2016).

For the purpose of learning more about different natural resource management strategies, in-depth interviews are crucial. Data about preferences, views, attitudes, and sociocultural experiences within communities can be gathered using them. To make wise decisions in favour of conservation programs, it can be helpful to consider these experiences and peoples' perceptions (Sutherland et al., 2018; Nyumba et al., 2018; and Bennett, 2016). For instance, people or local groups who think a conservation program violates their entitlement to benefits from food security and livelihoods may adopt unfavourable attitudes and be opposed to conservation. In-depth interviews can better capture this information and result in recommendations that address both local needs and conservation (Shibia, 2010; Hazzah et al., 2013; Hariohay et al., Røskraft, 2018).

3.6.1.2. Focus Group Discussions

Focus group discussions have been widely used in efforts to improve conservation decisions, often with a small number of participants, to explore in-depth insights and understanding of conservation programmes like CBFM through narrative discussions and descriptions of people's perspectives on social-economic, ecological, and conservation issues/impacts (e.g. Nsonsi et al., 2017; Andersson et al., 2014; Soe & Yeo-Chang, 2019). Twelve to fourteen people will participate in each of two focus groups, one for respondents under a community forest management group and the other for non-member respondents, allowing for relaxed and in-depth discussions on the PFM programme's impacts (socio-economic and ecological), benefits, preferred ecosystem services, governance structures (lack of), socio-cultural experiences before and after PFM, challenges, and preferred future scenario.

Focus group talks included a set of questions to help facilitate conversation. According to Nyumba et al. (2018) and Morgan (2002), group conversations with fewer participants helped participants better grasp PFM and benefited from complex personal experiences, views, and motives (or lack thereof). Decisions to improve conservation outcomes must be based on strong evidence, and qualitative methods can offer deep insights into the chaotic and complicated social-ecological contexts in which conservation happens (Adams & Sandbrook, 2013). This can help decision makers make more informed choices.

b) Quantitative Data

3.6.1.3 Survey Methods

Quantitative approaches are crucial for gathering data because they may be used to describe patterns, make connections, and investigate the correlations between different variables. In order to gather information on socioeconomic characteristics, governance and management practices, respondents' attitudes toward PFM, involvement, preferences and values, and skills obtained through PFM, this study will use a survey. Data collection allowed for comparisons between groups and the correlations between variables by providing quantitative descriptions of socioeconomic, ecological, and conservation behaviors (White et al., 2005 and Creswell, 2014).

Surveys are increasingly used in conservation research as suitable tools for gathering data and are used in rating (e.g. using a Likert scale), ranking, quantifying human behaviour, and comparing (e.g. between groups, sites or countries) quantitative indicators of perceptions of social, attitudinal, ecological, governance, and livelihood considerations (Quintas-Soriano et al., 2018; Oteros-Rozas et al., 2014; Bennett, 2016; Amano et al., 2018; Mollick et al., 2018). In order to examine human-environment linkages and make informed decisions, it is essential to use quantitative tools to understand perceptions of change and its effects (Andersson et al., 2014).

For a fuller knowledge of human-environment links and linkages, studies are seeking to integrate ecological data with socio-economic characteristics. For instance, similar studies have examined the extent into which environmental benefits and management practices (e.g. rulemaking, enforcement) influence ecological outcomes (e.g. Hayes, 2006; Persha, Agrawal, & Chhatre, 2011; Lund et al., 2014). Related methods are employed in this study to enable a deeper comprehension of local governance frameworks and their connections to livelihood and forest sustainability results, offering a more nuanced knowledge of the intricate processes that underlie PFM and community conservation projects.

By examining the underlying motivations behind behaviours, preferences and values, attitudes, governance legitimacy, and preferred future scenario, triangulation between qualitative and quantitative methods are crucial in gaining a clear picture and deeper understanding of PFM processes, impacts, and governance structures. This is essential in order to give the unbiased scientific data and evidence (Sutherland, et al., 2004; Pullin et al., 2013) required to support

wise conservation decisions and overcome conservation obstacles. By doing this, both livelihood and conservation progress can be attained.

c) Study Pilot

In order to reduce potential bias from interviewers' perceptions, survey questionnaires were piloted to measure completion rates and response types versus expectations. Additionally, the piloting process gave respondents the chance to ask questions for clarification when necessary. This enhanced the review of the questionnaire by incorporating any problems found and removing any redundant or non-information-adding questions.

In order to avoid mixing up topics that could affect the quality of respondents' answers through typos, the questions were logically arranged, related topics are classified or grouped together, and the flow of the questions was chronological (National Research Council, 2013). Additionally, in order to build rapport with respondents, the first questions were easy to answer (e.g., about education or family size) (Creswell, 2014; Patton, 2002). This helped to avoid asking difficult or sensitive topics that could arouse respondents at the beginning of the interview.

3.6.2 Secondary Data

Secondary sources of data include data from physical and virtual libraries, internet sources and websites of intergovernmental organizations and civil society organizations, journal articles, and documents retrieved from the key line ministries. Policy documents provided useful information on forest policies and the government's implementation strategies, part of the context of the research problem for this study. Documents collected from the relevant government agencies and NGOs provided useful preliminary information for understanding the social, economic and political context at the national level. Operational plans and the constitutions of the CFUGs will provide information about the formal rules and rights of forest management. Data from these documents will be used as a means of triangulating the data from focus group discussions and interviews.

3.7 Methods of data analysis and presentation

This research involved both qualitative and quantitative data which was be analyzed differently. Before the analytical process was done for the qualitative data, data was edited by scrutinizing the completed questionnaires to ensure that the collected data was accurate and consistent with the objectives of the study. The data was afterwards organized and prepared for

analysis by transcribing interviews, typing file notes, sorting and arranging different types of data depending on the sources of information. Content analysis was employed creating a description of themes for representation in the qualitative narrative.

Quantitative data on the other hand was analyzed using SPSS through the following procedures. Data cleaning and coding was done before entering it into SPSS. Upon entering the data into SPSS, statistical tests were run on the data set for both descriptive statistics and hypothesis tests. Descriptive, predictive and exploratory statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS. Findings were summarized in frequencies and percentages and presented in tabular forms using excel.

To test the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables Goodman and Kruskal's gamma was utilized. This is a statistical measure utilized to evaluate the strength and direction of association between two ordinal variables. Given that the nature of the variables under question are ordinal variables, this was considered as the appropriate test for the study. The gamma coefficient applies to ordinal data sets with multiple tied ranks or orders with continuous or discrete variables. The gamma value ranges between -1 and 1, where -1 indicates a perfectly negative association between the data pairs, 1 represents a perfectly positive correlation, and 0 resembles no relationship. It extends Spearman's rank correlation coefficient and is particularly useful when working with non-parametric data.

The data obtained for the study correctly fulfil the conditions in which this statistical test can be conducted. Such as the test being designed explicitly for ordinal variables. Thus the assumption for the application of the Goodman and Kruskal's gamma test emphasizes for the paired sets comprising of ordinal variables. These contained categories with natural order but lack specific numerical values i.e. likert scale responses (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree). The other assumption is that the paired variables should exhibit a monotonic connection whereby a rise in one variable results in an apparent increase or decrease in the rank of another variable.

$$\gamma = \frac{N_c - N_d}{N_c + N_d}$$

Where:

N_c denotes the number of concordant pairs; and

N_d represents the number of discordant pairs.

Interpretation

The value of the gamma coefficient is between -1 to +1. The closer the value to the extreme ends, i.e., -1 or 1, the stronger the relationship between the data pairs. It resembles the following:

-1 indicates a perfect negative association;

1 represents a perfect positive association; and

0 signifies no association between the variables.

Like any other statistical measure for hypothetical testing, the gamma statistics also prove the null hypothesis when the gamma value is not zero, thus indicating a positive or negative relationship or connection between the data pairs.

3.7.1 Quantitative Analysis According to Objective

Three objectives of the study were analyzed through quantitative techniques. The first objective; the relationship between CFMG governance practices and rural livelihoods in Zambia, the third objective; the effect of REDD+ on CFMG forest governance practices; and the fifth objective; the effect of REDD+ on Rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia.

a) Analysis of the first objective: The relationship between CFMG governance practices and Rural livelihood outcomes

The following are the ordinal variables were included in the analysis to test the relationship between CFMG governance practices and Rural livelihoods, measured on ordinal scales.

i) Governance practices considered (Independent variables)

Accountability and Transparency	Selection process of Income and expenditure reporting
Participation	Rule of law and policy
Benefit Sharing	Benefits of forest conservation efforts Forest Products
Efficiency and Collective action	CFMG constitutional availability & Maintenance

Source: Author (Indicators adapted from PROFOR & FAO, 2011; UNDP, 2011).

ii) Livelihood outcomes considered (Dependent variables)

Livelihood Outcomes	Livelihood Outcomes
Human Capital	Level of access to Education Services Level of access to Health care Services
Social Capital	Membership in informal networks

	Membership in formalized networks
Natural Capital	Access to forest resources
	Access to fertile soils
Physical Capital	Water Infrastructure
	School Infrastructure
	ICT infrastructure
	Household Assets
Financial Capital	Level of savings in possession
	Access to credit services

Source (DFID livelihoods framework)

b) Analysis of the second objective: The Effect of REDD+ on CFMG governance practices in Zambia

The following are the variables were included in the analysis to test the effect of REDD+ on CFMG governance practices, measured on ordinal scales.

i) REDD+ Indicators (Independent Variables)

	REDD+ Initiatives
	REDD+ activities provide for the active participation in decision making on matters of forest conservation & utilization
	REDD+ has brought about initiatives that improves community access to Natural resources
	REDD+ activities provide for the active participation in decision making on matters of forest conservation & utilization
	REDD+ has put in place activities that improve specific dimensions of governance
	REDD+ activities has improved overall CFMG Governance

Source: author's construction

ii) Governance Practices (Dependent Variables)

Governance Practices	Selection Process of Officials
Accountability and Transparency	Annual general meeting held as per constitution
	Income and expenditure reporting
Efficiency and Collective Action	Constitution availability and maintenance
	Membership list and maintenance
	Participation and list of duties
Participation and Collective Actions	Monitoring and patrolling (security)
	Rule of law and policy enforcement
Benefit Sharing	Benefit sharing in Forest products
	Benefits of forest conservation
	Plot sharing in LGMA

Source: Author (Indicators adapted from PROFOR & FAO, 2011; UNDP, 2011).

b) Analysis of the third objective: The effect of REDD+ on Rural Livelihood Outcomes

The following are the variables were included in the analysis to test the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihood outcomes, measured on ordinal scales.

i) REDD+ (Independent Variable)

REDD+ Initiatives	
	REDD+ has brought initiatives for knowledge and skills
	REDD+ has brought initiatives that encourage social group membership
	REDD+ has brought about initiatives that improve community access to Natural resources
	REDD+ has brought community development projects e.g water, schools, markets
	REDD+ has enabled community to afford new household assets

Source: author's construction

ii) Rural Livelihood Outcomes (dependent variables)

Livelihood Outcomes	
Human Capital	Level of access to skill development opportunities/knowledge
	Level of access to Information
	Level of access to Education
Social Capital	Membership in informal networks
	Membership in formalized networks
Natural Capital	Access to Land
	Acess to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc)
	Access to fertile soils
Physical Capital	Access to road infrastructure
	Access to water Infrastructure
	Access to school Infrastructure
	Access to ICT infrastructure
	Access to produced goods
	Access to Health care
	New Household Assets
Financial Capital	Level of Savings in possession
	Level of access to credit services and institutions
	Proportion of income from employment
	Proportion of income from remittances

Source (DFID livelihoods framework)

The descriptive statistics generated from the data were described visually and summarized using contingency tables, pie charts, and graphs. The study findings were afterwards linked to the empirical studies under the confines of the identified theories.

3.7.2 Analysis of Qualitative data according to objectives

The objectives were analyzed using qualitative techniques were appropriate. This was done in instances where the nature of the objectives demanded narrations and explanations on the challenges experienced thereby hindering the attainment of the desired outcomes.

3.8 Validity and Reliability

Friedman Test is non-parametric test (distribution-free) that was used to test the observation repeated on the same subjects, it is used to differences in treatments across multiple tests attempt. The procedure involves ranking rows together, then considering the value of ranks. Reliability and validity of results of this evaluation study depended on the correctness and truthfulness of information obtained from respondents and the perception of the interviews (Babbie, 2002). Existing secondary information (observation and existing information) was also used to increase reliability and validity of the data collected (Babbie, 2002; Kumar, 2002; USDJ, 2006). The study also triangulated different methods to collect data will help to cross check correctness of data with different people using different methods and these methods complement each other through triangulation (Kumar, 2002).

The study further conducted tests of the scale of measurement, using the Cronbach’s Alpha to check for reliability. This was done for the variables that were considered by the researcher to measure the same attributes such as, ‘the selection process of CFMG officials’ and ‘the level of household assets’ as follows.

The following are the livelihood variables (physical capital dimension) that were used to construct a new variable, ‘Household assets.’

Old Variables	New variable
Level of machinery in possession	Household Assets
Household equipment in possession	
Livestock in possession	

The variables presented in the table above were subject to the Cronbach Alpha’s reliability tests. The following table shows the test results.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.746	3

The result shows a result of 74.6% which is acceptable. According to the stipulations of Cronbach alpha test, any result above 70% is accepted as a reliable test.

Another variable that was created was under the governance practices – accountability and transparency dimension, ‘selection process of CFMG officials’ which was a combination of three variables as shown below.

Old Variables	New variable
Election or selection process	Selection Process of CFMG Officials
Voting methods	
Selection of delegates	
Attendance of presiding officers	

The variables presented in the table above were subjected to the Cronbach alpha test and the result is shown in the table below.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.856	4

The result in the table shows a Cronbach alpha of 85.6% which is good. According to the stipulations of Cronbach alpha test, any result above 80% is accepted as a good scale.

The other variables could not be merged in their respective dimensions both in terms of livelihoods or governance practices because they separately measured different attributes. Hence could not meet the assumptions of the Cronbach alpha test.

CHAPTER FOUR: PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In analyzing the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices and rural livelihoods, this chapter is divided into five (5) sections: the socio-economic and demographic characteristics; rural livelihood outcomes; community forest governance practices; the effect of community forest governance practices on rural livelihood outcomes; the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance; and the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihoods.

4.1 Socio-economic and demographic characteristics

The socio-economic and demographic characteristics are described in terms of the ward of the respondent, name of CFMG/CRB grouping, chiefdom of the respondent, gender, age group, number of persons in the household, level of education, duration of residence in the area, and their religious education.

a) Name of CFMG/CRB and Ward

Figure 4: Distribution of respondents by CFMG, VAG and ward per chiefdom

As noted in the table above, the largest distribution of respondents was from Chinambi ward under chief Lwembe representing 4 (four) VAGs with Chinambi VAG supported by BCP being the largest, 117 (30%) of the total respondents. The other chiefdoms, Nyalugwe and Ndake had

one VAG each with 73 (19%) and 21 (5%) respondents respectively. The distribution by responses is shown in the map below.

Figure 5: Map showing the distribution of responses in Nyimba District

Three chiefdoms selected to participate in the current study as shown in table 7 below. Chief Ndake’s chiefdom had more female participants, 75% as compared to Lwembe and Nyalugwe chiefdoms. Most respondents fell in the 25 to 44 years category and were older in Ndake’s chiefdom. Number of persons per household was also common among the three chiefdoms as at least 55% per chiefdom reported the range of between 4 and 7 people per Duration of residence was also considered important in the current study because it provided information on how knowledgeable an individual is about development initiatives within the community., Common to all chiefdoms, Christianity was the mostly practiced religion.

b) Focus group Discussion Participants

Table 8: Focus group study participants

VAG Name	Pseudo Name	Participant Number range
Nkhasako	FGD A	1 to 8
Chinambi	FGD B	1 to 10
Ng’ambwa	FGD C	1 to 12
Simalama	FGD D	1 to 9
Luangazi	FGD E	1 to 17
Mwansanika	FGD F	1 to 8

The table above shows the distribution of FGDs that were conducted during the study and their associated pseudo names.

c) Socio-demographic characteristics summary (primary respondents)

Table 9: Social-demographic characteristics summary

Demographic characteristics % per chieftom		Chief Ndake	Chief Lwembe	Chief Nyalugwe
Gender	Male	24	44	45
	Female	76	56	55
Age	15 to 24 years	19	19	15
	25 to 34 years	24	29	23
	35 to 44 years	38	24	22
	45 to 54 years	14	10	18
	55 to 64 years	5	10	15
	65+ years	0	8	7
Tribe	Nsenga	95	89	96
	Chewa	5	7	0
	Other	0	4	4
Persons in Household	Less than 3 people	10	26	21
	Between 4 and 7 people	76	55	56
	Between 8 and 10 people	14	17	18
	11 + people	0	2	6
Education attainment	None	24	7	12
	Primary	62	70	71
	Secondary	14	21	16
	Tertiary/ Trades Diploma / Certificate	0	1	0
		0	1	0
Duration of residence	Less than 5 years	24	24	12
	5 to 10 years	10	14	22
	10 to 15 years	10	11	7
	15 to 20 years	5	5	7
	20 to 25 years	14	13	8
	25 to 30 years	10	6	7
Religious affiliation	30+ years	29	26	37
	Christian	100	98	100
	Muslim	0	2	0
	Other	0	0	0

d) Characteristics of Secondary respondents (Government and Implementing partners)

Table 10: Details of secondary respondents

Organization Representative	Office	Pseudo Name
World wide fund for nature (WWF)	WWF Nyimba office	Respondent 1
Bio Carbon Partners (BCP)	BCP Nyimba office	Respondent 2
Community Markets for Conservation (COMACO)	COMACO Nyimba office	Respondent 3
Ministry of Green Economy and Environment – Forestry Department	District Forestry Office	Respondent 4
Zambia Integrated Landscape Project (ZFILP)		

4.2 Rural Livelihood Outcomes

In determining the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices and rural livelihoods, cross sectional data was collected on the livelihood outcomes of the study populations. The data on livelihood outcomes is divided into human capital, social capital, natural capital, physical capital, and financial capital.

4.2.1 Human Capital

In determining the human capital of the target population, data was collected included form of training received; distance to their nearest social amenities; and the respondents' major sources of information.

a) Form of training received in the last 12 months

To determine the state of human capital, the respondents were asked to comment on whether or not they received any form of training to improve their livelihood situation in the last 12 months. As shown in the figure below, over 50% Ndake's chiefdom did not receive any form of training. Training on conservation farming and climate change was common in Lwembe's chiefdom over 25%, whereas malaria prevention and hygiene training were common in Nyalugwe's chiefdom, over 65%.

Figure 6: Form of training received in the last 12 months

b) Distance to Social Amenities

Social amenities considered to be essential for human capital in this study include market facility, religious facility, school facility and health facility.

Figure 7: Distance to social amenities

According to the figure above, access to health facilities was a challenge in Ndake's chiefdom as above 50% stated that the nearest health facility was above 15 kilometers. The other key

challenge that was faced was access to market facility was so particularly in Lwembe’s chiefdom with close to 40% indicating that their nearest market facility was above 20 kilometers.

b) Source of Information

Source of information was also considered to be important in shaping the human capital of community members. Identified sources of information include television, radio, social media and community/neighbor.

Figure 8: Source of Information

As shown in the figure above, Ndake’s chiefdom got its information primarily from social media, whereas Nyalugwe’s chief got information from the TV. Lwembe’s chiefdom got its information from a diversified mix of sources.

4.2.2 Social Capital

In order to measure social capital as a livelihood outcome, the respondents were asked to comment on the types of groups they belonged to; whether or not they received any form of social support for their livelihoods and sources of support.

a) Social group membership

The following are the types of social groups that the people belonged to as shown in the table below.

Figure 9: Social group membership within chiefdoms

According to findings, the common social group membership in Ndake’s chiefdom was a cooperative, in Nyalugwe’s chiefdom there was a mix of types of group membership with women’s association dominating and church association being the least. Similarly, Lwembe’s chiefdom had close to equal distribution in terms of the types of social groups present in the chiefdom.

b) Social support for livelihoods

Social support for livelihoods was also used to measure livelihood outcomes.

Figure 10: social group benefits and sources

According to the findings in figure 9 A above, though Ndake’s chiefdom had diversity in terms of social benefits derived, it got most of them from family remittances, whereas Nyalugwe’s chiefdom enjoyed mostly from FISP and Social cash transfer. Lwembe’s chiefdom on the other hand enjoyed a diversity of social benefits almost distributed equally.

Sources of such support came from mostly government and development partner such as UN/WFP/FAO/BCP/WWF/COMACO as shown in figure 10 B.

4.2.3 Natural Capital

a) Ownership of land

Ownership of land was considered as an important component to measure livelihood in the current study. Respondents were asked whether or not they owned land and size of land owned.

As shown in figure 11 below, 5 hectares or less was common among all chiefdoms with a few outliers.

Figure 11: Size of land owned

The findings in the table above indicate that the size of land common among all chiefdoms was 0 to 0.5ha with a few outliers across chiefdoms.

A non-parametric test, independent-samples Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to check if there was statistical difference between size of land and households in community forest management groups. The results are as follows.

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	If yes, what is the size of this land?
Kruskal-Wallis H	26.301
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Name of CFMG/ Institution supporting CFMG/ Forest type

As seen from the table above, the sig-value of the test = .000 which is <.05. Implying that there is a statistically significant difference in the land size among the different groups.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of what is the size of this land? is the same across categories of Name of CFMG/ Institution supporting CFMG/ Forest type.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

The ranks of the different groups are shown below.

	Ranks		
	Name of CFMG/ Institution supporting CFMG/ Forest type	N	Mean Rank
If yes, what is the size of this land?	Lwembe/ BCP/ GMA	245	185.73
	Lwembe/ COMACO/ Open Area	37	241.58
	Mwansanika - Nyalugwe/ ZFILP/ Open Area	73	142.45
	Nkasako/ WWF/ Open Area	9	176.44
	Total	364	

As shown in the above, the Lwembe under the stewardship of COMACO, had the highest mean rank (241.58); followed by Lwembe under the stewardship of BCP (185.75); Nkasako by WWF ranked 176.44; whereas Mwansanika had the lowest mean rank (142.45).

Figure 12: Usage of forest resources

b) Usage of forest resources

According to the figures A and B above, farming for food had high usage indicating a high level of importance to their livelihoods. For medicinal herbs, most of the respondents were skeptical on use for medicinal purposes because they feared being associated to witchcraft. Firewood was considered to be very important in almost every household as it is the primary cooking source of energy. Other uses of forest resources that was considered important to livelihood activities of the communities included grass for thatching and poles/posts/timber has these had usage by the majority of the respondents across chiefdoms. Food for grazing was

only common in Nyalugwe chiefdom where livestock rearing was heard of. The forest as a source of water was also highly used in Nyalugwe chiefdom. Charcoal production had low usage as an importance source of livelihoods except in Ndake chiefdom, where communities depended on it. Spiritual and cultural use of forests was low across all chiefdoms targeted.

4.2.4 Physical Capital

Physical capital was considered as an important measure of livelihood outcomes in the current study as shown in the figure below.

Figure 13: Physical capital

4.2.5 Financial Capital

In determining rural livelihoods, financial capital was considered as important measure of livelihood outcomes in the current study. Measures under this dimension included main occupation of respondents; major sources of livelihood finance; and access to alternative finance i.e. distance to financial institutions as shown below.

a) Main occupation of respondents

As a way to measure respondents' financial capital, they were asked to comment on their main occupation as shown in the table below.

Figure 14: Occupation and sources of income according to level of importance

The distribution of major occupation was also done according to chiefdom so as to give a clear picture of distinctiveness in the utilization of forest resources for their day to day livelihoods as shown in the figure 13(A).

Level of importance of income source to livelihoods was considered as an important measure of determining which one contributed more to households, Figure 13(B). When it comes to overall importance of the various sources of income among all the groups aggregated together, agriculture had high perception in terms of average. Nyalugwe chiefdom reported selling of forest resources highly due to relatively high dependence for their livelihoods. All the other sources of income had low perception. These findings indicate that with the involvement of other stakeholders such as implementing partners, there is reduced dependence on forest degradation activity such as charcoal burning.

As a way of proving the differences in occupation among the CFMGs within chiefdoms, a Pearson chi-square test was conducted as shown in the table below.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	82.109 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	61.222	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.573	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	385		

a. 11 cells (55.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.

As seen from the figure above, there is a statistically significant difference in occupation and CFMG all the P-values are less than 0.05. The similarity in of occupation may only be due to chance. The communities closer to the main road, reported to depend to a large extent on charcoal burning, whereas those in the interior depended more agriculture.

b) Distance to financial institutions

The distance to financial institutions was also considered as an important to determine the livelihood outcomes of the respondents. This is shown in the table below.

Figure 15: Distance to financial institutions

As shown in the figure above, the distance to financial institutions was above 20km for over 75% of the respondent in each category. Hence initiatives to boost financial capital should be prioritized as future development interventions.

Figure 16:: Levels of satisfaction with livelihood outcomes by dimension

4.2.6 Level of satisfaction with Livelihood Outcomes

The respondents were further asked on their perceptions with their livelihood outcomes in terms of their human capital, social capital, natural capital, physical capital, and their financial capital as shown in figure 15. Access to education was considered to have an average score of 4 (good) across the chiefdoms (Figure 15 A). Level of access to health care in was considered to be very poor in Ndake’s chiefdom. The levels of satisfaction across chiefdoms were similar in the social capital dimension (figure 15B) of the livelihood framework. On a high note, access to natural capital (figure 15C) was considered to range from fair to good across all chiefdoms. Implying that development projects such the REDD+ initiative might not be highly restrictive for communities to have such access thereof.

Physical capital (figure 15D) at the level of community were generally reported to high satisfaction levels ranging from fair (3) to good (4) across all chiefdoms except in Ndake chiefdom where water infrastructure was reported to be poor (2). At the same time physical capital at the level of household was considered poor and very poor among all chiefdoms. Implying that development projects might not have an impact at household level. The satisfaction levels in the access to financial capital (figure 15E) were equally similar across all chiefdoms as the average rating was poor (1) to very poor (2). Hence initiatives to improve such access need to be incorporated in future development programmes.

4.3 Community Forest Governance Practices

In measuring the effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural Livelihoods, forest governance practices were measured by determining membership in community forest group; level of participation in governance of forest resources; and the presence or absence of accountability and transparency mechanisms.

4.3.1 Duration of Membership in Community Forest Management Group (CFMG)

Duration of membership in CFMG in the current as it determined the level of experience in dealing with livelihood initiatives that may come to the community. The figure below shows the duration of membership in the CFMG.

Figure 17: Duration of membership in CFMG

4.3.2 Decision Influence in CFMG

The decision influence in the CFMG was considered important in the study as it would give a picture of community perceptions on how decisions are made as shown in the figure below.

Figure 18: Position held in CFMG

According to the findings presented in the table above, even though the majority stated that they collectively influence and make decisions, there were still traces of people who stated that people in high positions in society having a direct influence over decisions made within the CFMG.

4.3.3 Livelihood Benefits Derived from CFMG/CRB Membership

Figure 19: Benefits derived from CRB membership

4.3.4 Level of Participation in CFMG Governance

The level of participation in CFMG governance is another key variable which was measured by participation in planning; participation in constitutional setting; participation in meetings to address issues; and the presence or absence of accountability and transparency mechanisms.

Figure 20: Levels of participation and accountability in CFMG

Furthermore, respondents were asked to comment on whether or not they are granted the opportunity to influence the decision-making process as shown in the table below.

Figure 21: Influence in decision making

According to the findings regarding the statement, there was a low perception implying that most of the respondents disagreed with the statement therefore proving that indeed members were usually given an opportunity to influence the decision-making process (figure 21A).

The respondents were also asked whether or not their suggestions, opinion or decisions regarding forest management were considered by the CFMG officials. There was a high perception regarding the statement implying that the majority of the respondents' opinions or decision were taken into consideration by the CFMG committee (figure 21B).

4.3.5 Membership and usage of forest resources

Considering that rural communities largely depend on environmental resources for their livelihoods. The respondents were asked whether or not their membership in the CFMG affected their usage of forest resources as shown in the table below.

Figure 22: Effect of CFMG membership status on usage of forest resources

Overall in FGDs most participants agreed that it was prohibited to cut down trees in protected areas above 50% respondents across all chiefdoms.

4.3.6 Frequency of access to information regarding CFMG (forest conservation, participation, or opportunities etc.).

Figure 23: Information frequency on CFMG activities

4.3.7 Perception levels on community forest governance practices

The respondents were further asked on their perception levels on the community forest governance practices in terms of Accountability and Transparency, Efficiency and Collective Action, Levels of Participation and Benefit sharing as follows.

Figure 24: Perceptions towards governance practices by chiefdoms

According to the figure above, perceptions towards governance practices were generally ranging from fair to very good across all chiefdoms. The low perception was generally on the benefit sharing dimension where chiefdoms like Nyalugwe and Ndake were perceptions ranged from very poor to fair. It should be noted that chief Ndake's chiefdom had not yet started receiving benefits as the CFMG there was recently formed.

4.4 REDD+ and CFMG forest governance practices

a) The Effect of REDD+ on CFMG governance practices

The respondents were asked on their perception levels of REDD+ on the community forest governance practices in terms of Accountability and Transparency, Efficiency and Collective Action, Levels of Participation and Benefit sharing.

According to findings, there was an overall high perception among respondents on how REDD+ has affected community forest governance practices among CFMGs. The responses ranged from neutral to strongly agreed. Ndake's chiefdom recently formed an CMFG and was yet to experience its governance practices hence the respondents couldn't agree to most of the statements they were being probed.

Figure 25: The effect of REDD+ initiative on CFMG Governance practices among chiefdoms

4.5 The Effect of REDD+ on Rural Livelihood Outcomes

The respondents were further asked on their perceptions on how REDD+ affects their livelihood outcomes in terms of their human capital, social capital, natural capital, physical capital, and their financial capital as follows.

Figure 26: REDD+ effect on Livelihoods among chiefdoms

As shown in the table above, the findings indicate that there was an overall high perception on the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihood outcomes among community members. However, the exception was under the statement, “REDD+ has enabled community members to be able to afford new household assets,” which had mid perceptions. This could be the case because most community members seemed to not be satisfied with how REDD+ contributes to household asset accumulation. Ndake’s chiefdom couldn’t agree on any of the statements as it had not yet started deriving benefits at the time of the study.

4.6 Qualitative Findings

4.6.1 Background to community forestry Zambia

The use of forest resources has been more beneficial to the community members way before they started forming the CFMGs. Respondent 1 highlighted on how community members have become presently responsible in the way they extract forest resources with the formation of CFMGs. Before, they used to extract medicine from trees without considering sustainability. The CFMGs have contributed to the progress by seeking help to extract the best resources from the forest resources at their disposal. “For example, previously we had Nyimba Forest Commodities Association which sensitized the same communities on certain medicinal plants and the people have started benefiting actually as previously there was nothing like people being helped on identifying which kind of tree. All this is done with the view of managing these resources in terms of extraction/exploitation.” (Respondent 1).

On the changes that have taken place regarding community forestry, respondent 4 stated that previously, the forestry department was the only department which was in the forefront in trying to manage forest resources. But with time, there was a realization that the people who lived with the resources were left out. Representation was a serious issue because the department lacked presence in the remotest parts of the country. This was different when compared with other sectors such as education and health whose presence is felt all across the country. The forestry sector was only limited to district level, making management very difficult. According to respondents 3 and 4, communities for a long-time perceived forest resources as belonging to the government, resulting in little care given to conserve or protect them. According to respondent 4, such challenges led to the revision of the policy to make it more inclusive. The communities had to come on board to manage these resources in order to guard them jealously. Unlike the situation before where people would come from as far as China to harvest forest resources such as the Mukula tree and nothing would be done about it. With new incentives for forest conservation, communities are now able to earn carbon fees which they can now use to implement different projects.

According to respondent 4, the new forest act was put in place in the year 2015 and the act being used is act number 4 of 2015 which is supported by the forestry policy of 2014. The 2014 forestry policy tried to bring in different stakeholders in the management of forest resources. So besides engaging the community members, various implementing partners have come on board such as BCP (Bio Carbon Partners), COMACO, World Vision, and the Worldwide Fund

for Nature (WWF). The government has thus created a conducive environment for different players to conserve forest resources so that they can benefit the nation (at the district level), and worldwide.

4.6.2 Community Forest Governance Architecture in Zambia

It was also considered important to understand the governance architecture of the CFMGs in the current study. According to respondent 2, in these chiefdoms, there are structures within the clustered village called Village Action Groups (VAGs). Village Action Groups have sub-committees that convene to inform the board, which is the CFMG. Given that a village has a very large catchment area and one board committee cannot cover all the needs of the chiefdom, the chiefdoms have clustered them into small village groupings called Village Action Groups. These groups within their catchment area focus on their common needs. In these groups, two of the top executives who sit on the board are members of the larger committee, the Community Forest Management Group (CFMG).

4.6.3 Accountability and Transparency

When asked to comment on accountability and transparency, respondent 1 stated that they assisted in conducting elections for the selection processes of the CFMG committee members. He noted that elections enabled the entire community to come together in that way they would what to expect from the CFMG committee put in place. Furthermore, he stated that as development partners, it was their role to ensure that everyone in the community, starting from the headmen to ordinary members, participated. It was usually a significant event where people lined up to vote for the leaders to oversee those forests.

To complement this information, FGD participant D 8 stated: “We usually do vote. When they register to be voted, they go around campaigning, and when the right time comes, they teach us how to vote and choose the person we want.” Furthermore, FGD participant D 7 highlighted some of the characteristics they look for in voting for the leaders both at VAG and CFMG level. They look for characteristics such as the level of commitment of the aspiring candidate, stable-mindedness, and a developmental mindset. FGD participant E 17 further noted: “There is usually no fighting during the process, and sometimes we usually invite some people to come and monitor and observe the whole voting process. Immediately after voting, then we start counting, and find who the winner is and then at last after finishing counting then we will know that this is the winner and he is the leader.”

On income and expenditure reporting, key informants were asked to comment on whether or not the community members have access to information regarding the progression of the projects being implemented. On this matter, respondent 4 referred to the forestry act. The respondent stated that the act provides for the need to call for meetings on a frequent basis, either quarterly or monthly, so that they give financial reports to the community to ensure they are moving at the same level. As one of the key informants, respondent 4 highlighted their role as implementation partners to prioritize setting up these meetings to clear misconceptions that may arise in communities regarding projects being implemented and to build the credibility of their leadership.

To complement this information, FGD study participants were asked to comment on the level of transparency in project implementation. FGD study participant C4 noted that

“We only know that the funds are done when the project is done. We don’t know if some funds remain or not. Sometimes we just hear of the amount that have been released. We proposed a number of things funds released only to hear that the chief has diverted the funds to something else, and the bridge is still giving us problems.” This scenario, raises questions on whether or not the patron, chief, in these communities continue to influence the outcome/transparency of community development projects even when they were already allocated their share.

4.6.4 Efficiency and Collective Action

When asked to comment on efficiency and collective action, participant B 2 in the FGD stated: “I remember attending the CRB meeting, and what I recall is that they mentioned the laws and rules. I usually attend the CRB meetings, and I am certain that there is a paper containing the law regarding what is not allowed and what is allowed.”

FGD study participant D 6 highlighted some of the laws they are taught to follow during the meetings they attend. It was noted that they were informed that community members became more careless with issues like cutting down trees, which resulted in climate change affecting the amount of rainfall. The key laws highlighted included not burning charcoal and not cutting down trees indiscriminately. However, most FGD participants revealed that they were not aware of any written document or constitution they could refer to, despite having knowledge of the do’s and don’ts.

According to respondent 2, in any general meetings, there are attendance registers that people are required to sign if they attended, and minutes are produced to cover their needs. Once the

need is put forward and financed, they go back and inform the community as feedback. If the CFMG decides to deviate from community needs, a general meeting is held, consensus is reached, and minutes are recorded to provide reasons for the change from what the community proposed to another project, as there might be certain dynamics at play. For example, a certain community might choose a health post, but for it to be constructed, certain dynamics need to be considered. A district engagement meeting would be held with government stakeholders, and the Ministry of Health would advise whether or not it can be done. If not, justifications might include “a hospital cannot be built within a radius of 2 kilometers. This is the radius set by the council under the standards of the Ministry of Health. The community is thus informed that the next health facility can only be permitted within a radius of 8km. Facilities cannot be everywhere as staffing, equipment, and referral problems would arise if a health post was to be built within this radius. The community members are thus given another opportunity to decide on something else.”

Respondent 2 emphasized that all these are done participatorily. According to the respondent, the participatory approach with CFMGs was conducted to train them in the criteria for choosing a project. This was in alignment with the response given by FGD participant A5 who stated: “Membership lists are already in place.” However, respondent 3 stated that the patron, the chief, still retains the power to decide which project to approve or not. This contradicts the provisions of a CFMG stating that chiefs are considered as the patrons of the projects being implemented and are not supposed to interfere with community funds as they are already allocated with a certain percentage of finances coming into the community.

4.6.5 Rule of Law and Policy Enforcement

On rule of law and policy enforcement FGD participant A5 stated,

“The membership of the executive which consists of 10 people is there, the membership list for the forest guards looking after the protected hill is there, and there is also one for the fire management team.”

According to FGD participant A5,

“The laws were made together with those who helped us choose the leaders. Those laws were made by us and not someone who came, we made all the laws very well.”

Respondent 1 supplemented this information by stating that the process of decision making is very participatory as decision making starts with ordinary community members who are

consulted before a decision is reached. The respondent further noted that they sensitized them so that whatever happens they will know as a strategy to ensure participation. In doing so, it is easy to spot where committees are going astray and not living up to expectation. Thus, committee members strive not to do anything outside the community's expectations.

According to respondent 2, the formation of CFMGs is done in way that implementing partners are involved from the initial phases where the committee members have to be selected, to the processes where they have to implement their roles until the end of tenure where community members have to select and vote for a new committee. In this regard, during the implementation of community projects, the selection of the projects is participatory in nature where the community members are involved.

Respondent 2 further mentioned that communities have needs that have to be reflected in decisions by the CFMG committees. As an implementation partner, they facilitate annual planning with different communities in the VAGs which are elected to represent the needs of their communities. Some areas of priority in the communities include education, health, road infrastructure or any other activity to improve household incomes. According to respondent 2, if the community representatives choose activities to improve household income, they assist in carrying out investigations on how it would be done and via which channels i.e. clubs. When these activities are in place, dependence on forest resources is also lessened to permit for regeneration.

Further on rule of law and policy enforce participants from FGD D 7 noted that:

“there are even some scouts, there are some scouts for game ranch and do if one is found burning charcoal then what follows is a case to answer and if one is found cutting down trees without any proper reason.” FGD participant D 8 also noted that all these laws apply to everyone regardless of being in leadership or not. They all go about the situation as though they were all leaders by following those laws.

4.6.6 Benefit Sharing in CFMG

On the question, can you comment on the benefit sharing mechanism within CFMG?

Respondent 1, an implementing partner, noted that the benefits go beyond the committee members of the CFMGs by cutting across the entire community including the forestry department. He further noted that at the end of the day, they have to monitor and see what is happening and they required a bit of benefit.

“The benefit sharing mechanism encompasses the traditional leaders, the development committee like the ward development committee, the vulnerable people within the community, also there is what we call the fire management committee because those forests need to be managed so there are various sub-committees like fire management committee that also needs to be given part of the benefits for the work that they are doing to protect those forest resources. So, the benefit sharing mechanism starts actually with the chief.”

Further, respondent 1 explained the how the benefits are distributed. He noted that 10 percent of what they got went to the chief. The committee got a bigger proportion, about 60 percent, because they had to implement projects on behalf of the community. These projects included education services infrastructure, health care infrastructure, roads, or bridges within the community based on their priorities.

However, there were also negative views on the way in which forest resources are distributed. According to respondent 4, when there are issues of distribution of benefits to the communities, there will always be complaints. For instance, vast chiefdoms might be implementing as many as 10 or 15 projects. Depending on the resources available, the projects are ranked in order of priority. As resources come in, they implement. When the resources do not suffice for the full completion of the project, they are carried forward to the following year. It happens in some instances when previous projects are abandoned by communities as they change their priorities. Thus, respondent 4 highlighted that due to scarcity of resources members of the community may complain. Other complaints might also arise from issues of a project that is selected might not be desired by segments of people within the community. Hence complaints are inevitable. Respondent 4 highlighted that sensitization activities help in reducing the negative perceptions that the community members might have towards the mechanisms.

4.6.7 Community Forest Governance Challenges Among CFMGs

To uncover on the governance challenges faced by the CFMGs, participants (FGDs and Key informants) were asked, ‘what governance challenges have you observed in the operations of the CFMGs?’ the responses are as follows.

i) Accountability and Transparency

Furthermore, FGD participants revealed some gaps in the governance practices which affects the associated livelihood outcomes. According to FGD B, participants unanimously agreed that they usually did have access to information on project related expenses once a project

commences. According to focus group discussion B, whether the money is completely utilized or some remains after the implementation of the project usually remains unknown. The climate of the governance structure can be described to have a culture which attributes faith in the leadership in a way that questioning them on financial matters would be a sign of disrespect. According to participant B10 of an FGD:

“We are usually afraid.”

Also linked to accountability and transparency, FGD B also stated that they had no information on who decides how much benefits the CFMG committee members are entitled to. The committee members are considered to be in different social class on their own. As FGD participant B 3 revealed that when it came to distribution of benefits for example seeds, one household is entitled to 1x10kg bag of seeds but those in leadership got 3x10kg bag of seeds. The FGD B unanimously did not have any information on who determined the benefits that those in leadership are entitled to. The community represented by FGD D had their leaders collect 2x10kg bags of seed and they did not see anything wrong with that. They claimed that those were privileges associated with being a leader. Besides participant D8 stated that the leaders do a lot of work moving up and down to make sure that the entire community benefits while the rest of the community members just stay at home.

Other speculations observed during the FGDs is that some committee members have become wealthy overnight upon being elected to the board. However, other speculations picked during the meetings were that CFMG committee members usually have workshops, exchange visits and opportunities to travel across the country to learn on how to govern forest resources. Such opportunities accompanied with their allocated financial compensation is what people see to have caused their supposed overnight wealth. This information is not clearly stipulated to the ordinary community member who might feel left out in terms of their livelihood outcomes connected to forest conservation efforts.

When the researcher further inquired as to why was it that they never sought for this information despite having attended most of the meetings. FGD B participants unanimously agreed to the statement given by participant B6 as one of the factors why some key questions might be skipped during these meetings:

“When they call for a meeting and they usually cook lunch so that the people can eat, now the way the food is eaten, and usually there is no proper order. When they prepare the food, some they eat even without washing hands, there is usually scramble for the food.”

Another key factor that affects the livelihood outcomes as a result of the governance practices is the surprising revelation that was given in one of the FGD sessions. According to FGD B, the community had selected a market shelter to build for them as one of the key priority projects as remuneration for their conservation efforts. Distance to the nearest market in the areas was more than 20km. But once the project started it stalled for about 2 years. As it was commissioned to start in the year 2021. When the researcher asked them to comment on why that was the case, the response was given as follows.

According to participant B 7:

“at the meeting what they usually say the money was spent on Tuwimba ceremony. We don’t have much question because it is the Chief himself who makes those decision about this money. When the chief asks for the money, we get the same money.”

This goes to show that the patron, the chief has a higher degree of influence to change the course of any implementation of a project. This was the case despite the chief being allocated a percentage of the benefits derived from the forest conservation efforts. There was a high degree of fear among community members stating that the chief is given whatever he asks for as he is the owner of everything. However, this was only one case where such a diversion was observed and thus cannot be generalized to the entire study population.

On the question, whether or not community members had access to information concerning CFMG’s activities and benefits, FGD participant B 1 noted,

“We are usually sensitized, they usually call for a sensitization meeting. They make us all aware and asked as to what project that we can do within this year. So once that is done, there are different VAGS, then you are given to choose the development you want.”

However, there were some instances where members of certain communities claimed they did not receive adequate information on the entire project cycle (refer to section 4.6 on the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices below).

ii) Quality of project implementation

From the field data, respondent 2 noted that one of the challenges faced in governance that can be linked to livelihood outcomes comes from the mandate that requires implementation of projects to be done by the local representative according to their legislative governance bodies. The level of qualification and exposure of the selected representatives thus determines how the

projects will unravel. This is one key factor that was observed to affect the livelihood outcomes as noted by respondent 2.

In line with this, respondent 3 and respondent 4 (implementing partners) agree that stalling projects are caused by under costing during planning by the committees; or changes in prices between planning and implementation. Implementing partners such as respondent 2 and 3 state that implementation of every activity is community centered, they are the ones that decide the projects, when and how to implement them. Another reason for stalling according to respondent 4 could be that priorities might have changed in a given year making the on-going projects placed on hold. Other factors that might account for that according to respondents 2, 3 and 4 include fuel prices going up, the dollar exchange rate goes up which might in turn affect the project costing.

However, to the contrast, FGD D expressed a lot of confidence on governance practices and associated livelihood outcomes. According to the group, in instances where they have a project such as a market as a community, they live it to their leaders at board or CFMG level to discuss the intricacies involved in implementing that particular project. It is when they discover that the money is not enough that they again come back to the community to ask the members to select an alternative project equivalent to the amount of money released.

These issues according to respondent 4 might lead to misconceptions among community members they become suspicious against each other or may be that the committee is trying to syphon some resources. This also led to questioning the availability of information and issues of accountability and transparency by the elected committees.

iii) Benefit sharing mechanisms

Another challenge that did arise related to the benefit sharing mechanism was the issue of certain chiefdoms are having more projects than other chiefdoms. For instance, it was observed that in Chief Lwembe's area, each and every household received a bag of seed where as in Chief Nyalugwe's area households were skipped. On this observation, respondent 4 highlighted that the amount of financial gained from conservation efforts depended on the size of forest under protection. For instance, chief Lwembe's area, the forest area under protection is 289,000 hectares of forests under protection (Refer to the map below). So, in terms of the financial value that they receive is way more as compared to the other chiefdoms. For example, they receive 12 million kwacha in a year whereas the chief Nyalugwe's area only receives 3 to 4 million kwacha. This fact and taking into the vastness of the chiefdom lead to the decision of

making a certain number of households getting the benefit in one particular year whereas those who didn't would get in the following year. Or another way of distributing the benefits was when certain number of community members get seed this year, it will imply that they would be skipped the following year when there is the distribution of iron sheets, then in the following years, they swap.

According to FGD participant B9; people choose different projects. Certain VAGs choose the sheds, others the market shelter, some stated childhood centers. Only to find out that only one was picked, complaints become inevitable. But they are made to understand that development projects are delivered depending with the money allocated. The source of income is usually one, and the VAGS are many for instance there are 10 VAGS in Lwembe chiefdom. So those VAGS with a small project are the ones who will receive the full funding and finish it.

This was further confirmed through triangulation as FGD F benefit revealed that sharing mechanism was negatively perceived by the members of the community. This group had a unique distribution system as finances being received are not adequate for the vastness of the chiefdom. Village headmen were aware of community members who received benefits from other avenues such social cash transfers. For such individuals, they were not eligible to benefit from the carbon financing to give opportunities to other members to benefit. The headmen determined who got to benefit using some sort of criteria. As a result, committed people to forest conservation efforts felt neglected. Participants of FGD F felt that those members who were close to the headmen stood a better chance to receive benefits from these efforts. The group further stated that based the selection criteria, households received 5 iron sheets to build permanent houses, directly reducing their dependence on forest resources.

According FGD participant D 9:

it's not that it's their wish or they chewed part of the money no, but maybe things do not work out here. We are not accusing them but they do remind us that we should be doing things together.”

Figure 27: Map showing forest areas being protected by different implementing partners
 Source: Author’s construction

4.6.8 REDD+

In order to determine the effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural livelihoods, key respondents were asked to comment on REDD+ and its role thereof.

According to respondent 2, REDD started a long time ago, it started somewhere in the 1980, 1979 in another form. But their system of comparison was different until somewhere in 1988 when they said internationally determined contributions should be at play because what they are saying is that at first countries met in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change where they met for designing the protocols, they had agreed that each country should contribute equally. Eventually, it was realized that Africans produce more forests whereas the global effects of climate change are equal regardless of where you are. So, the idea of nationally determined contributions was out of balance. Advantages had to be accrued to Africa because development would halt in the continent if no benefit was given in exchange for their conservation efforts. Conservation efforts would imply communities who depend on forests to stop using them for their day to day livelihoods. Hence a financial value was created, a form of payment for keeping the forests intact. When this is done, the already industrialized countries would continue to produce. It was further realized that it was manageable to reduce carbon

levels by zero if the forests were kept intact. So, continuing in a situation where forests are consistently being destroyed while production is going on in the industrialized world, a point might be reached where climate problems would be uncontrollable.

According to respondent 2, REDD is concept developed to try and address climate issues/problems through forest protection and also sequestration of carbon dioxide. The respondent further stated that the concept is internationally agreed upon to address the issue of carbon emission using the primary agent of carbon sequestration, a tree. Intact forests permit for a cool and nice air flow for pollution when there is no emission that in the atmosphere. It is the loss of trees that caused the birth of REDD, Reduction in Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation. It is based on this development that the respondent's organization was founded to implement REDD+.

Respondent 4 stated:

“Quite alright we know that these resources are the ones that people use in order for them to earn a living in one way or another. But how do we protect these resources because if we don't protect them it means the future will be very devastating. Look at these climate change issues that have come, we don't have rains, enough rains, droughts, excessive water or may be little rains. So, we have to combat those. Then people should try to benefit from what they conserve.”

The respondent further emphasized the primacy of his organization being the first REDD+ developer that has been verified for ten times. According to respondent 2, their role as implementing partners is to partner with community members to mitigate climate change problems. Given that REDD+ comes with a package of carbon financing, the communities have been made to understand the importance of forest protection. The concept was designed in such a way that forest protection efforts by communities are to generate financial revenue via carbon stock which is the stock of carbon stored in the trees.

4.6.8.1 REDD + in Operation

The procedure as stated by respondent 2 was done first by beginning with a baseline data survey which entails the levels of carbon stored in the tree. Interventions are then put in place and afterwards, an evaluation is conducted. Carbon financing is done through the sale of the carbon units known as verified carbon units (VCUs). It is this money that is then given back to the communities to actually help them as an exchange for their benefit in protection. In this regard, once communities continue to protect the forests, they continue to generate carbon units and

these carbon units are translated into the financial value. The respondent stated that the primary role of the organization was to assist the community in trading these units. These units are then traded to those companies that want to off-set their carbon foot print. Those who off-set the carbon foot print are those companies that produce high levels of carbon emission.

According to respondent 2, the levels of production determine the carbon foot print that would require off-setting. If you are a mining company for example that mines oil, that company is likely to produce more carbon, it is likely to produce more carbon and give danger to the community. The respondent referred to why currently there is transformation from oil using companies to green energies, electrified vehicles and stuff because they are trying to discourage those companies. In fact, globally, the first world countries, the industry countries, Germany, Japan, Italy, America, China are the high emitters of carbon dioxide because of the levels of industries in their countries.

Respondent 2 gave examples of categories of companies that are high carbon emitters such as ship companies and oil companies. These companies are mandated globally to subscribe by off-setting carbon emissions. So as an implementing partner respondent 2 stated that they set up a standard to their communities to conserve forest resources and have their forests verified i.e. VCUs which are then translated into financial value once the emitter off-sets their carbon foot print by paying off. Hence respondent 2 highlighted that the concept is performance-based arrangement. Highlighting the fact that carbon is non-tangible and yet has value. So as an intervention, REDD+ is happening to respond to climate problems. But the financial value is supposed to translate into livelihood change for the people. Respondent 4 added by stating that when the revenues are generated through the support of the implementation partner, it is divided into three parts. One part goes to the patron (the chief); one part goes to the committee members of the CFMG (for administrative duties); and the third part goes to the community projects. According to respondent 4, when the communities see the benefits coming from conservation efforts, they are now able to guard the forest resources jealously.

According to respondent, to determine significant impact by REDD+, a bigger evaluation is conducted after 5 years apart from the yearly ones. The forms of evaluation are known as principal holdings. The 5-year audit is also called community climate biodiversity (CCB) as it looks at what has transformed in the period of 5 years. As stated by respondent 2, some of the questions asked during the audit include:

“Communities have been receiving financing from carbon, what has changed? If it is a livelihood program, a household program, what has changed in their individual income? If it’s a school project, where has it been built? How many pupils have now been enrolled? How many have accessed education? If it was a program for supporting tertiary education, how many have been supported? Are these the problems that were identified in that community?”

According to respondent 2 every after 5 years a CCB audit is conducted to help communities, VCAs and also to act as a global standard in determining impacts on how their revenues are actually being put in use. These processes were similar to those reported by respondent 2. As an implementation partner, respondent 2 stated that their role is to facilitate legislative body aspect, the structures that government has put in place and the system that REDD+ provides in the protocols.

4.6.8.2 The role of Forestry Department in REDD+ Implementation

Respondent 4 highlighted on the role of the forestry department throughout the REDD+ process to work hand in hand with the community to impart knowledge in them so that they see some benefits which come from conserving the resources that they have. The respondent further stated that their role was also to enforce the law. Even though traditional laws are used to manage forest resources but if certain things go beyond traditional laws, community members come in to work hand in hand with the forestry department to take charge of certain issues so that if the matter is supposed to be taken to court, the department would facilitate the process. For example, when community members find somebody cutting forest resources illegally and such a person is arrested, the department comes in to take up the case with those who brought them to book as witnesses at the courts of law. Thus, the department comes in to interpret the law so that the person, the perpetrator or the offender is punished by the law. This is aside from the education given to help them understand why they need those resources. To make them understand that funds which are coming in from REDD+ are more than 10 times compared to the money that they receive from wildlife or logging depending on the hectareage under conservation.

This is reinforced further by respondent C12 who stated: “with wild animals, we would poach a lot but we have now stopped because we now know the benefits of these animals that they bring us money. We could cut down trees because of honey but now COMACO has brought beehives where we keep our bees from.”

FGD participant A8 complimented this information by stating:

“If one is found wanting, they have to be penalized first from here, if that fails then we have to engage the Forest department so that we deal with that culprit and if the culprit is more stubborn then we take that particular person to the police. For us to keep our forest well.”

To gain a thorough understanding on the evolution of forest governance, the key stakeholders were asked to comment on skepticism throughout literature and among community members at large that REDD+ threatens to take away forest governance from the communities back to government due to the voluminous sums of money that is left to the control of the communities.

According to respondent 4, the forest act is very clear in terms of control of forest resources. It is only when the communities try to mismanage the rights that they’ve been given, instead of managing those resources prudently, they involve themselves in practices which are illegal, the forest act says the control of forest resources can be revoked and be taken back to the government. Control according to the act is given to the community because, the communities are the ones who stay closer to those resources.

Respondent 4 further stated that if those speculations in literature and among community members was true, it will be contradicting to what the forest act states and people would start to vandalize those resources as they did before under the belief that they did not own the forest resources. It can only be so when the act and the policy is revised. The current legal provisions state that management is hands of the community under the condition that they establish a certain area. However, those areas which are not established are currently under the government control. REDD+ is benefiting communities more than the government. If the government had benefited more, people would not be incentivized to guard the forest resources.

4.6.9 The effect of REDD+ on rural livelihoods

Respondent 2 highlighted on the role REDD+ plays in rural livelihoods. According to the respondent there were 2 identified agents of deforestation that give danger to climate problems. The agents that were prevailing the area of study, Eastern province is charcoal production and agricultural expansion. Thus, according to respondent 2, the aspect linking the livelihood aspect to REDD+ is asking how the initiative comes in to stop the aspect of cutting down trees for charcoal, cutting the trees to produce income. Hence the carbon revenue explained above is given to the communities for them to initiate livelihood initiatives. The respondent stated that as an organization spearheading REDD+, they come in to empower, to train communities as agents of change so that communities can appreciate the life of a tree and gain revenue from the sale of carbon at the same time contribute to climate reduction problems. As established,

the trees by nature contribute to the reduction of emissions and that will mean that the world will be a better place to live in with an improved climatic system.

In line with what the implementing partner stated, FGD participant C1 stated:

“We have benefited in a way that we are able to take our children to school, when we sell some goats that we are given it helps us to take our children to school.”

Respondent 2 gave examples on some livelihood projects implemented. The respondent mentioned on how a particular chiefdom, a CFMG realized that communities were using more trees to construct houses every year, they decided to procure iron sheets to build permanent houses. Respondent 3 mentioned of many projects being implemented such as construction of clinics, teachers houses, boreholes for community water supply and various trainings. In mitigating the other agent of deforestation, agricultural expansion, respondent 2 highlighted on their role as an organization is the introduction of climate smart agriculture which enables community members to produce better yields on the same piece of land without expanding. These technologies have been proved and being implemented from the carbon financing.

Respondent 4 stated that integrated gardening was implemented in Mwansanika area which they use to raise something as they try to minimize dependency on forests. They sunk 4 boreholes equipped with four tanks in order for them to do gardening. Similar to respondent 2, modern farming techniques are being taught to community members where they are not supposed to use bigger chunks of land. Demo plots and farmer school fields are established where communities learn the modern technology of tree agriculture so that they reduce on opening more land and also from the same piece of land, small piece of land, there is maximum utilization.

FGD participant B 10:

“we usually receive the maize seed through the carbon project, we received goats, we received chickens for the cooperative.”

FGD participant B 3:

“Even the water that we are drinking, the money to drill boreholes came from the benefits of preserving the forest. Other developments, there is also a grinding mill, there is also a maize sheller and oil expelling machine, all that money came from CRB so these are benefits we are getting.”

FGD participant B 5:

“There was a market that was belt for us, there is a hospital and there are schools.”

FGD participant B 6:

“Even the houses at the school were belt by CRB. So, all this money came from the forest we are preserving. Development is progressing and we not going behind.”

FGD participant B 4:

“Some Years back we could drink water from the unprotected wells or streams, very bad water such that when one drinks one could even suffer from Diarrhea, especially during this hot season, but the benefits we have seen, as long as it is a village, you will find that there are boreholes through the same carbon project.”

FGD participant B 3:

“this carbon on my side am really grateful, as for me at my home, I was given a treadle pump on the part of choosing development so even as am talking, the machine is being used watering the garden, I am really grateful that this development is as a result of this research of carbon. Help is there and benefits are there.”

Also, on a household level FGD participant C12 noted:

“I have benefited in way that I was given seed which I planted and harvested quiet a lot of maize which helped me to buy household goods for the first time in my life and also built a house which I can proudly point at to start these are the benefits of being a member of Carbon.”

Another livelihood outcome that was appreciated by the research respondents was that the project also gave cooperatives to finance income generation activities to boost their livelihoods. According to respondent E 16:

“there was some money that was released to be given to cooperatives, they were being given K7, 000 plus, all of them were given per group, even the elderly one who also formed some groups received some money.”

“The main thing that we really need here in our community is a hospital because we walk 8 km just to get to the clinic, women give birth on the way sometimes in the clinic yards which attracts a penalty.” (FGD participant C9).

Through the REDD+ initiative, communities have been offered trainings through different implementation partners. According to respondent 2, these trainings have enabled community members to understand the legislative aspects that government has put across. As a partner/developer, respondent 2 highlighted the importance of adhering to the systems that governments have put in place as they begin receiving carbon financing. The sums of money given to the communities are huge for example one of the chiefdoms, Lwembe with 289,000 hectares under protection, received 12 million Kwacha for the year 2023 which is a huge sum of money. As one of the initiatives to strengthen community forest governance practices, the communities were introduced to a system of financial management. According to respondent 2, these committees have a working document, an annual work plan they use to expend their revenues from forest cover.

According to the respondent 2,

“And that is our day to day activity with them to make sure that whatever they have planned for, whatever cries, the needs of the communities should be responded through the financing that they getting from the carbon finance.”

4.6.10 REDD+ effect on Community Forest Governance Practices

On how REDD+ has improved governance practices via leadership, respondent 1 noted that as an organization they have lined up a number of activities such as exchange visits where they took committee members to other areas where these CFM areas are successful so that they also go and learn. This is among other activities such as trainings and exposure visits. The respondent further noted the organization having people from Muchinga, in a recent time to interact with the local committees so that they exchange the ideas. This is similar to the response given by Respondent 2 who noted that the projects being implemented are community based, through the REDD+ financing, a number of different trainings are introduced to help build their capacity in financial management, to help them build capacity not to be biased in the distribution of income received.

Respondent 2 stated that the REDD+ initiative is a global governance system has been adopted in the local governance system through the legislature. For instance, the forest act allows for the formation of forest management groups in order to manage forest resources and generate revenue thereof. According to respondent 2 the act further provides for the established CFMGs would partner with a developer or a company that would link them to carbon trading.

REDD+ effect on forest regeneration

“We used to make a lot of charcoal and we use to do it in large quantity. Just after the project started and they gave us this law, we stopped burning the charcoal, we were told that each household should have the energy efficient stoves made so that the trees shouldn’t be destroyed. The energy efficient stoves that does not need a lot of firewood, so we stopped cutting down of trees anyhow.” (FGD participant B 3).

“The addition which is there is that even burning of the bush anyhow is not allowed, there are rules that were made. Burning is one of the things of destroying the climate. A period was set when burning bushes is allowed for instance in the month of June. So that the wild animals can find the grass where to eat and even the domestic animals should find food. In this way, the grass should be given time to regenerate.” (FGD participant B 1).

“Before, we could burn the field, then we could just make some planting holes. After being taught, we stopped burning the fields and we are just slashing to preserve the soil fertility.” (Respondent B 3).

As one of the reasons why the forests have experienced some restoration and regeneration as noted by respondent C11 who noted:

“yes, the difference is there, because if people see boreholes, shelters and grinding meals even goats that they benefit from protecting the forest, it drowns them back from going to destroy the forest. As a result, the red zone plus is protected. It’s now different from the time this place was not protected.”

4.6.11 Challenges faced in the implementation of REDD+ linked to CFMG governance practices

However, there was some level of dissatisfaction among members of FGD E who questioned leadership on the delivery of projects. A number of issues were unraveled throughout the process. The issue that came out was over the construction a maternity wing which stalled over a period of two years, and construction of houses for teachers. According to the participants of the FGD, these projects were considered a priority for the community members as they travelled long distances to attain health care services especially women maternity services; and that teachers had no decent accommodation. However, despite the finances being dispersed by the development implementation partners, the project has remained on a stand still.

According to the skeptics of the group, they had suspected that the monies released from REDD+ were diverted to personal usage instead of the intended developmental project. According to the skeptics, they observed their leaders moving up and down with fuel that is intended to complete the project. Furthermore, the leaders are observed to be doing fine and eating well.

According to FGD participant E 2:

“this is the same money they using for their development with their children, with their wives and their children instead of doing development for the community. When this happens, that leader is no longer seen as a leader but as a thief.”

To counter this argument, participant E 16 stated that the money arrives though the top level, the CFMG before it arrives at the VAG level. At this level, there are other bigger people that includes the patron, the chief. Participant E 10 continued by stating that the amount of money that was released for the project was communicated to the community. This amount was ZMW 9,000 and from this amount, the patron deducted ZMW 9,000 for renovations at the palace, and for community motor vehicle insurance. This also affected the completion of houses for school teachers which had equally stalled.

FGD Participant E 11 jumped in as an optimist of the group by stating that the materials came for the construction of the maternity wing, 150 bags of cements were bought and some other materials. According to the participant, money doesn't come at once, so when the money is released, it delays for it to be released to reach not to the chairman but were it is coming from is delayed to be released and is being released in small quantities. That was on possible explanation why the projects could not be done quicker.

It was also noted by FGD participants who noted that indeed REDD+ provides such where the communities choose for themselves what development projects ought to come to their communities. However, there was an expressed concern regarding too costly projects being rejected. Project costs are compared among different communities. If one project selected in community A is relatively costlier as compared to the projects selected in other communities, it is rejected. Thus, FGD participant C 9 notes: That such instances make such communities to choose something that is not a necessity in the community at that particular time in fear of completely losing out.

4.7 Statistical Tests

The Association between Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural Livelihood Outcomes

The four major dimensions of governance that were associated with rural livelihood outcomes were accountability and transparency, efficiency and collective action, participation and collective action, and benefit sharing.

a) The association between Accountability/Transparency and rural livelihoods.

Using the Goodman and Kruskal tests, the 5 dimensions of the livelihood outcomes were associated with two variables under accountability and transparency (selection process of CFMG officials, and the income and expenditure reporting). The results are shown in the tables below.

i) The association between the selection process of CFMG officials and Livelihood Outcomes.

	Selection process *Livelihood Outcomes	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance	
HC	Level of access to Education	0.503	0.101	3.937	0
	Level of access to Health care	0.333	0.109	2.8	0.005
SC	Membership in informal networks	-0.175	0.097	-1.723	0.085
	Membership in formalized networks	0.236	0.103	2.171	0.03
NC	Access to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc.)	-0.364	0.113	-3.022	0.003
	Access to fertile soils	-0.287	0.115	-2.377	0.017
	Water Infrastructure	0.361	0.089	3.446	0.001
PC	School Infrastructure	0.384	0.097	3.288	0.001
	ICT infrastructure	-0.324	0.087	-3.265	0.001
	Household Assets	-0.098	0.107	-0.9	0.368
FC	Level of savings in possession	0.134	0.127	1.055	0.292
	Access to credit services	0.13	0.127	1.031	0.302
	N of Valid Cases	385			
	a Not assuming the null hypothesis.				
	b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.				

H = Human Capital; S= Social Capital; N = Natural Capital; P = Physical; F = Financial Capital

The table above shows that there was statistically significant relationship between the selection process of CFMG officials and majority of the assets under the livelihood outcomes. This governance practice was insignificant with household assets under physical capital. Denoting that the activity of the CFMGs were more community oriented than household oriented. The governance practice was also insignificant when associated with financial capital. Implying that the CFMG governance practice rarely caters for financial dimension in addressing the community needs.

The nature of the relationship was negative with informal networks under social capital implying that the high quality of the selection process drove people away from informalized groups to formalized ones. The association was also negative with natural assets implying that the confidence in the selected officials led to people in believing in the mandate of forest conservation even when it comes to losing access to fertile soils. ICT infrastructure was also negatively associated with the governance practice. This was general challenge in the area and it went beyond the mandate of the CFMG.

ii) The association between income and expenditure reporting and livelihood outcomes

Income and expenditure reporting * livelihood outcomes				
Livelihood Outcomes	Gamma Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
HC Level of access to Education Services	0.232	0.083	2.695	0.01
Level of access to Health care Services	0.304	0.068	4.203	0.00
SC Membership in informal networks	-0.296	0.064	-4.423	0.00
Membership in formalized networks	0.289	0.07	3.944	0.00
NC Access to forest resources	-0.354	0.074	-4.678	0.00
Access to fertile soils	-0.025	0.08	-0.311	0.76
PC Water Infrastructure	0.31	0.067	4.367	0.00
School Infrastructure	0.319	0.07	4.201	0.00
ICT infrastructure	-0.351	0.065	-5.025	0.00
Household Assets	-0.018	0.071	-0.258	0.796

FC	Level of savings in possession	0.152	0.079	1.924	0.054
	Access to credit services	0.047	0.078	0.608	0.543
N of Valid Cases		385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.					
b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.					
HC = Human Capital; SC= Social Capital; NC = Natural Capital; PC = Physical; FC = Financial Capital					

As noted in the table above, income and expenditure reporting of the CFMG is significantly associated to the all the assets of the livelihood outcomes. However, household assets under the physical assets and the levels of savings in possession under the financial assets were insignificant. Implying that household level progression is rarely covered in the governance of CFMGs in explaining the low levels of household assets. The access to credit services insignificance with the income and expenditure reporting can be explained that credit provision within the community or easier access to it might not be included in the CFMG agenda.

It should also be further noted that the majority of the variables under livelihood outcomes indicated a positive relationship with income and expenditure reporting. The negative association with membership in informal networks implies that the higher the level of income and expenditure reporting, the less likely it is for community members to associate themselves in informal networks, thus being a positive outcome. On forest resources under natural assets in the other hand, the negative association can be attributed to how accountability encourages people to reduce the utilization of forest resources, making this outcome to be positive. ICT infrastructure under physical capital also tested a negative significant relationship. This is likely due to the poor network infrastructure in the area which has not been prioritized by the CFMGs' mandate.

b) The association between Efficiency/Collective action and livelihood outcomes

Efficiency and collective action were measured using constitutional availability and maintenance and it was then associated with livelihood outcomes as shown in the table below.

Constitution availability and maintenance * Livelihood Outcomes					
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
HC	Level of access to Education	0.218	0.078	2.721	0.007
	Level of access to Health care	0.287	0.057	4.931	0
SC	Membership in informal networks	-0.13	0.065	-2.004	0.045
	Membership in formalized networks	0.323	0.063	4.955	0
NC		-0.368	0.06	-5.941	0

Access to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc.)					
	Access to fertile soils	-0.2	0.071	-2.805	0.005
PC	Water Infrastructure	0.289	0.065	4.296	0
		0.106	0.077	1.38	0.168
School Infrastructure					
	ICT infrastructure	-0.413	0.061	-6.469	0
	Household Assets	-0.129	0.081	-1.572	0.116
FC	Level of savings in possession	0.063	0.064	0.984	0.325
	Access to credit services	-0.172	0.066	-2.606	0.009
N of Valid Cases		385			

a Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

HC = Human Capital; SC= Social Capital; NC = Natural Capital; PC = Physical; FC = Financial Capital

The table above shows that efficiency/collective action is statistically associated to the majority of the assets under livelihood outcomes. However, school infrastructure and household assets under physical infrastructure was insignificant. Implying that when people attend to the affairs of the CFMG in terms of the requirement of the constitution, the change that occurs to household assets and their school infrastructure needs would only occur due to chance.

c) The association between participation/collective action and rural livelihood outcomes.

Level of involvement in rule of law and policy enforcement was used as a proxy indicator for measuring participation/collective action which was then associated with livelihood outcomes as shown below.

Rule of law & policy enforcement * Rural livelihood outcomes					
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
HC	Level of access to education	0.225	0.077	2.818	0.005
	Level of access to Health care	0.157	0.067	2.328	0.02
SC	Membership in informal networks	-0.094	0.066	-1.419	0.156
	Membership in formalized networks	0.243	0.066	3.59	0
NC	Access to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc.)	-0.339	0.065	-5.031	0
	Access to fertile soils	-0.039	0.074	-0.53	0.596
PC	Water Infrastructure	0.237	0.067	3.492	0
	School Infrastructure	0.113	0.073	1.538	0.124
	ICT infrastructure	-0.327	0.064	-4.905	0
	Household Assets	0.016	0.063	0.256	0.798
FC	Level of savings in possession	0.078	0.069	1.124	0.261
	Access to credit services	-0.072	0.07	-1.017	0.309
N of Valid Cases		385			

a Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

HC = Human Capital; SC= Social Capital; NC = Natural Capital; PC = Physical; FC = Financial Capital

As shown in the table above participation is only significant to 50% of the livelihood variables. Variables such as access to fertile soils, school infrastructure, household assets and the financial assets were insignificant implying that the higher the degree to which law and policies are enforced within the CFMG, the accompanied change that would occur in the insignificant livelihood variables can be due to chance.

d) The association between benefit sharing and livelihood outcomes

Benefit sharing mechanisms were also associated with the livelihood outcomes and the results are as follows.

Benefit Sharing		Benefits of conservation efforts* Livelihood Outcomes			
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
HC	Level of access to Education	0.145	0.058	2.488	0.013
	Level of access to Health care	0.161	0.049	3.28	0.001
SC	Membership in informal networks	0.476	0.046	10.001	0
	Membership in formalized networks	0.003	0.054	0.064	0.949
NC	Access to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc.)	0.467	0.05	8.881	0
	Access to fertile soils	0.061	0.059	1.024	0.306
PC	Access to Water Infrastructure	0.03	0.059	0.507	0.612
	Access to School Infrastructure	0.098	0.057	1.718	0.086
	Level of access to ICT services	0.258	0.053	4.838	0
	Household Assets	-	0.054	-0.83	0.407
FC	Level of savings in possession	0.023	0.059	-0.393	0.694
	Access to credit services	0.091	0.062	1.453	0.146
	N of Valid Cases	385			

a Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

HC = Human Capital; SC= Social Capital; NC = Natural Capital; PC = Physical; FC = Financial Capital

The table above shows that benefit sharing of forest conservation was only significant with human capital. Under social capital it was significantly associated with informal networks. Implying that the benefits were largely found in informal networks. Under natural capital, benefit sharing was significantly associated with access to forest resources. The only variable

that was significant under physical capital was ICT services. Implying that when the benefit sharing is high, access to ICT is also very high. Variables under financial capital had no statistically significant association.

4.7.1 Hypothesis 1: The relationship between Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural Livelihoods

The governance practices tested against the livelihood outcomes include accountability/transparency; efficiency/collective action; participation/collective action; and benefit sharing.

Based on the observed associations, it can be noted that accountability and transparency is significantly associated with human capital, social capital, natural capital and physical capital. Efficiency/Collective action was also statistically associated with all livelihood dimensions. Participation/collective action was associated with most of the variables under livelihoods except financial assets. Benefit sharing was only statistically significant with human capital, social capital and physical capital.

Therefore, the null hypothesis, "H₀ There is a significant relationship between forest governance practices and rural livelihood outcomes," is accepted.

b) The association between REDD+ and CFMG Governance Practices

To test the association between REDD+ and forest governance practices, community members were asked to rank statements shown in figure 25, 'REDD+ has improved overall CFMG governance.' These findings were further associated with the findings on the governance practices among CFMGs. Lastly, these findings were complemented with qualitative data from key informant interviews and FGDs.

REDD+ activities has improved overall CFMG Governance * Governance Practices					
Governance Practices	Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance	
	Selection Process of Officials	0.674	0.074	5.704	0.000
AT	Annual general meeting held as per constitution	0.659	0.054	9.113	0
	Income and expenditure reporting	0.696	0.052	9.23	0
EC	Constitution availability and maintenance	0.553	0.063	7.606	0
	Membership list and maintenance	0.641	0.062	7.294	0
	Participation and list of duties	0.491	0.067	6.555	0

PC	Monitoring and patrolling (security)	0.263	0.077	3.271	0.001
	Rule of law and policy enforcement	0.47	0.064	6.513	0
BS	Benefit sharing in Forest products	-0.39	0.055	-7.218	0
	Benefits of forest conservation	-0.17	0.065	-2.706	0.007
	Plot sharing in LGMA	-	0.064	-2.975	0.003
		0.188			
N of Valid Cases		385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.					
b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.					
AT= Accountability and Transparency; EC = Efficiency and Collective Action;					
PC = Participation and Collective Action; BS = Benefit Sharing					

As shown in the table above the relationship between the REDD+ and the governance practices is significant with all proxy variables. However, the relationship between REDD+ and benefit sharing shows a significant negative relationship. For the benefit sharing in forest products, this implies that the higher the improvement in governance practices, the lower the level of benefit sharing in such resources. This can be justified by the fact that the communities have been put in contracts not to derive any benefits from forest resources.

i) The association between REDD+ initiatives and associated CFMG governance practice

The association between REDD+ and Community access to natural resources

REDD+ has brought about initiatives that improves community access to Natural resources * Benefit Sharing				
Benefit sharing	Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
Forest products	-0.371	0.053	-7.223	0
Forest conservation efforts or community remuneration	-0.222	0.062	-3.652	0
N of Valid Cases	385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.				
b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.				

When further tested, the association of REDD+ shows a significant negative association with benefit sharing. As households mostly did not benefit at the level of household (boosting the household assets), also that their access to forest products was curtailed by their obligations not to embark on deforestation activities.

iii) **The association between REDD initiatives on participation+ and participation levels in CFMG**

REDD+ activities provide for the active participation in decision making on matters of forest conservation & utilization * Participation levels				
	Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
Ordinal by Ordinal	0.403	0.066	5.615	0
N of Valid Cases	385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.				
b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.				

The findings presented above show that there was a statistically significant relationship between REDD+ initiatives and participation in forest governance among community members. This is explained that community members are encouraged through the incentives provided by REDD+ to play an active role in governance.

Furthermore, the community members were asked to rank the statement, “REDD+ has put in place activities that improve specific dimensions of governance.” These findings were associated with the governance practices as shown in the table below.

REDD+ has put in place activities that improve specific dimensions of governance * Governance Practices					
Governance Practices	Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance	
	Selection Process of Officials	0.499	0.092	4.26	0
AT	Annual general meeting held as per constitution	0.402	0.069	5.231	0
	Income and expenditure reporting	0.502	0.066	6.397	0
EC	Constitution availability and maintenance	0.429	0.067	5.869	0
	Membership list and maintenance	0.488	0.073	5.519	0
	Participation and list of duties	0.403	0.068	5.488	0
PC	Monitoring and patrolling (security)	0.194	0.073	2.562	0.01
	Rule of law and policy enforcement	0.356	0.068	4.983	0
BS	Benefit sharing in Forest products	0.066	0.059	1.105	0.269
	Benefits of forest conservation	0.324	0.057	5.216	0
	Plot sharing in LGMA	0.284	0.056	4.803	0
N of Valid Cases		385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.					

The findings show that REDD+ activities are positively statistically significantly associated with the governance practices among CFMGs. This implies that if more initiatives are put in place by REDD+ to address specific governance challenges, the higher the likelihood of governance practices being improved among CFMGs.

4.7.2 Hypothesis 2: The effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance Practices

H₀ There is a significant relationship between REDD+ activities and the quality of community forest governance practices.

Based on the Goodman Kruskal tests conducted above, the null hypothesis has been accepted. As shown in the various tests conducted among different ordinal variables under REDD+ and forest governance practices, it can thus be concluded that global initiatives such as the REDD+, are indeed making a difference in strengthening the quality of community forest governance practices.

Statistical tests REDD+ and Livelihoods

The statements in the table above were also associated with livelihood outcomes as shown in the table below.

		REDD+			
		REDD+ has brought initiatives for knowledge and skills			
	Livelihood Outcomes	Value	Asymptotic Standard Error a	Approximate Tb	Approximate Significance
HC	Level of access to skill development opportunities/knowledge	0.055	0.076	0.728	0.467
	Level of access to Information	0.149	0.074	1.979	0.048
	Level of access to Education	0.237	0.076	3.087	0.002
		REDD+ has brought initiatives that encourage social group membership			
SC	Membership in informal networks	-0.06	0.065	-0.912	0.362
	Membership in formalized networks	0.195	0.062	3.091	0.002
		REDD+ has brought about initiatives that improve community access to Natural resources			
NC	Access to Land	0.154	0.06	2.588	0.01
	Access to forest resources (wood, food, grazing land etc.)	-0.365	0.059	-6.336	0
	Access to fertile soils	-0.054	0.067	-0.815	0.415
		REDD+ has brought community development projects e.g. water, schools, markets			
PC	Access to road infrastructure	0.026	0.055	0.477	0.633
	Access to water Infrastructure	0.358	0.058	5.826	0

	Access to school Infrastructure	0.125	0.063	1.966	0.049
	Access to ICT infrastructure	-0.272	0.057	-4.725	0
	Access to produced goods	-0.354	0.081	-3.874	0
	Access to Health care	0.229	0.049	4.561	0
	New Household Assets	0.145	0.073	1.999	0.046
REDD+ has enabled community to afford new household assets					
FC	Level of Savings in possession	0.014	0.058	0.237	0.813
	Level of access to credit services and institutions	0.158	0.059	2.677	0.007
	Proportion of income from employment	0.525	0.067	6.482	0
	Proportion of income from remittances	0.165	0.119	1.359	0.174
	New Household Assets	0.145	0.067	2.135	0.033
N of Valid Cases		385			
a Not assuming the null hypothesis.					
b Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.					

According to the findings in shown in the table above REDD+ shows a statistically significant association with human capital: access to information and access to information. This implies that the more community members are exposed to REDD+ initiatives, the higher the likelihood of them to have access to information and education services. However, it was not statistically significant to the level of access to skill development opportunities and knowledge. On social capital, the findings indicate that there was a statistically significant relationship between REDD+ activities and access to formal networks. Showing that REDD+ has the likelihood of encouraging community members to be part of formalized group settings which are beneficial to them.

The findings also show a statistically significant relations with access to land, and access to forest resources under natural capital. The nature of the relationship is negative with forest resources. This is explained by the nature of the agreement with communities which limits the usage of forest resources. Access to fertile soils was insignificant to REDD+ activities which can be explained by the nature of obligations that do not permit community members to expand agricultural lands at the detriment of forest resources. On physical capital, REDD+ is observed to having a positive significant effect on all the variables except access to road infrastructure. This result can be explained by the nature of road projects which go beyond REDD+ scope.

Lastly, on financial capital, REDD+ was statistically significantly associated with access to credit services and institutions. Which can be interpreted as, the higher the accumulation of assets because of REDD+, the more likely that these community members had access to credit services. Keeping in mind that REDD+ is also significantly associated with access to

formalized groups such as village banking and savings groups, it thus possible that access to finance might be readily available in such instances. REDD+ was also found to be significant with proportion of income from employment. This implies that REDD+ initiatives were found to be more appreciated with members who obtained some income from employment. The higher the income from employment, the more effective the REDD+ initiatives are considered. Also, REDD+ was statistically significant with new household assets. Implying that more involvement in REDD+ initiatives by community members, the higher likelihood of acquiring new household assets. Other variables such as the amount of savings in possession, and proportion of income from family remittances were statistically insignificant.

4.7.3 Hypothesis 3: The effect of REDD+ on Rural Livelihoods

Based on the findings above, the hypothesis, “ $H_0 =$ REDD+ positively rural livelihood outcomes among CFMGs in Zambia,” is accepted. It can thus be concluded that global initiatives such as the REDD+, are indeed making a difference in strengthening the quality of livelihood of forest dependent communities.

4.8 Discussion of Findings

In determining the Effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices and rural livelihoods in Zambia, this section is divided into the three sub-sections based on objectives of the research. The first part is the relationship between community forest governance practices and rural livelihood outcomes; the second part is the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices; and the last part is the discussion on the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihood outcomes.

4.8.1 The Relationship between Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural Livelihood Outcomes.

The findings from this study provide important insights into the dynamics of community forest management (CFM) and its implications for rural livelihoods. The governance of forest resources, particularly by Community Forest Management Groups (CFMGs), emerged as a key factor influencing livelihood outcomes in the communities studied. The shift toward community-based governance is seen as a progressive step in promoting the efficient protection of forest resources. However, as the study reveals, this shift also presents challenges.

These findings resonate strongly with the broader literature on community-based forest management (CBFM) and participatory forest management (PFM), which consistently point

out the strengths and challenges of such governance structures in enhancing livelihoods and ensuring sustainable forest management. In particular, issues related to accountability, the effective participation of community members, the equitable distribution of benefits, and the influence of local elites, such as chiefs, emerged as significant challenges that continue to undermine the effectiveness and fairness of CFM programs.

a) Accountability and Transparency

A key concern in community forest governance is the need for robust accountability mechanisms. In this study, elections for CFMG committee members and regular community meetings where financial reports are shared contribute to a sense of community involvement and accountability. As noted, elections help ensure that community members remain actively engaged in the governance process, and financial reports offer transparency regarding the allocation and use of funds. However, despite these efforts, significant challenges remain, particularly regarding financial transparency. Many community members expressed concerns about the unclear utilization of funds, particularly when funds intended for forest management projects were diverted for other purposes, such as cultural ceremonies. This lack of clarity regarding financial allocations often leads to suspicions of mismanagement and corruption, and it undermines the community's trust in the governance system.

This concern about financial transparency aligns with findings from Pelletier et al. (2016), who observed that CFM often leads to improvements in livelihoods but does not always translate into equitable benefits. The lack of clarity in fund utilization can breed mistrust, particularly when there is a perceived lack of accountability in financial management. As Agrawal and Gibson (1999) highlighted, the governance of CFM often falls short in addressing equity concerns, particularly disadvantaging poorer households and women-headed households. This failure to ensure financial transparency and accountability contributes to these inequities, limiting the overall impact of community forest management initiatives.

Moreover, the study found that while regular community meetings allow for some level of feedback and transparency, discrepancies in the access to information especially concerning financial reports and project expenses still exist. Some community members reported being unaware of the specifics of fund utilization and the decision-making processes behind financial allocations. This lack of clear and accessible information further perpetuates a sense of exclusion and disenfranchisement, which is a common challenge in many CFM and PFM programs (Malla et al., 2008). These findings emphasize the critical need for stronger and more

transparent governance structures, where all community members have equal access to information and can hold leaders accountable for their actions.

b) Participatory Decision-Making and Community Engagement

The findings also reveal a strong emphasis on participatory decision-making, with community members actively involved in selecting and prioritizing projects. This aligns with the principles of community forest management, which aim to empower local communities by giving them a greater role in managing their natural resources. However, despite the participatory nature of decision-making, the implementation of these projects is often hindered by practical challenges. Changes in project priorities, budget constraints, and rising costs for materials such as fuel often stall projects, leading to delays and incomplete outcomes. These delays, in turn, result in dissatisfaction among community members, who may feel that their involvement and contributions to decision-making are not being honored.

This challenge is well documented in the literature. For instance, studies in Tanzania (Vyamana, 2009) and Nepal (Malla et al., 2008) highlight how devolved forest management often faces significant financial and logistical barriers that limit the ability of local communities to implement the projects they prioritize. In many cases, these barriers result in disparities between community expectations and the resources available, ultimately leading to frustration and reduced confidence in the management system. Moreover, the inability to meet all community needs due to financial constraints can exacerbate feelings of exclusion and inequity, particularly among marginalized groups who may be most reliant on forest resources for their livelihoods (Rukundo, 2018).

The shifting priorities and under-budgeting of projects are notable challenges that can erode the legitimacy of the CFM process. As found in this study, when projects are delayed or fail to meet expectations, community members may question the efficacy and fairness of the governance structures in place. This is particularly problematic when community members feel that they are not receiving adequate explanations for the delays or misallocations, further deepening the divide between the leadership and the community. The challenges in financing and project implementation discussed here mirror findings from studies in Ethiopia (Gobeze et al., 2009) and Mozambique (Siteo & Guedes, 2011), where financial constraints were found to limit the success of forest management programs.

c) Rule of Law and Enforcement Mechanisms

Effective enforcement of community laws and regulations is another critical factor for the success of CFM programs. The findings from this study indicate that, while laws governing CFMGs were created through a participatory process, the enforcement of these laws is inconsistent. In particular, local elites, such as chiefs, were noted to have significant influence over decision-making processes, sometimes overriding community decisions or diverting funds for personal use. This concentration of power undermines the fairness and transparency of the governance system, as it perpetuates unequal access to resources and undermines community efforts to hold leaders accountable.

The unequal enforcement of rules, particularly in cases involving local elites, is a significant governance challenge that has been widely discussed in the literature. Okpoko (2019) noted that, in some cases, local elites may not be fully bound by the laws they help create, which leads to non-compliance and diminished community trust. Similarly, Piabuo et al. (2018) found that local governance structures often struggle to enforce laws consistently, particularly when influential leaders are involved. This lack of uniformity in law enforcement contributes to the erosion of the rule of law, as community members may feel that certain individuals or groups are exempt from following the rules.

While there are formal enforcement mechanisms in place, such as the role of scouts and law enforcement officials in holding individuals accountable for activities like illegal charcoal burning, these mechanisms often fail to reach all community members, particularly the powerful elites. This discrepancy in enforcement is detrimental to the overall goals of CFM, which aim to foster a sense of collective responsibility and adherence to common rules. Without effective and equitable enforcement of community laws, it becomes difficult to ensure the sustainability of forest management efforts and to maintain a fair and inclusive governance system.

d) Equity in Benefit Sharing

One of the most significant findings of this study is the issue of inequity in the distribution of benefits derived from forest management. While the benefit-sharing mechanism was designed to ensure that community members receive a fair share of the resources, there were consistent complaints about the unequal distribution of benefits. In particular, leaders and committee members were reported to receive a larger share of financial resources or goods, while other community members, especially those in larger chiefdoms, were excluded from benefit-sharing

due to financial constraints. This unequal distribution of benefits has led to dissatisfaction among certain groups, particularly those who feel that they are being left out or unfairly excluded from the distribution process.

The findings from this study align with broader discussions in the literature regarding the unequal distribution of benefits in CFM and PFM initiatives. As Pelletier et al. (2016) and Agrawal and Gibson (1999) observed, wealthier and more powerful individuals often dominate governance structures, which can lead to the marginalization of poorer households and women. These dynamics can reinforce existing social inequalities and prevent the equitable distribution of forest-derived benefits. In many cases, the elites or those with more influence within the community gain disproportionately from these programs, while the most vulnerable groups who may depend most on forest resources for their livelihoods such as respondents from FGD F who noted, charcoal burning had previously been a major livelihood activity their households, but the introduction of stringent CFM rules has prohibited this activity. This inequity in benefit-sharing is a significant barrier to the success of CFM initiatives, as it undermines the goals of poverty reduction and equity that are central to these programs (Schreckenberg & Luttrell, 2009). This issue of inequity in access to resources is a significant barrier to the success of CFM, as it can lead to resentment among community members and undermine the legitimacy of forest governance systems.

e) Governance Challenges and Project Delays

The governance challenges identified in this study, particularly the delays in project implementation and the lack of transparency, have a direct impact on the effectiveness of CFM programs. As noted, delays often result from financial mismanagement, shifts in priorities, or inadequate resources. These delays contribute to the erosion of community trust in the leadership, particularly when the reasons for the delays are not clearly communicated to community members. This lack of transparency and poor communication exacerbate the challenges of governance and undermine the legitimacy of the decision-making processes.

Governance issues, such as poor communication, financial mismanagement, and shifting priorities, have been well-documented in the literature. In Cameroon, Beauchamp and Ingram (2011) noted that weak governance structures often undermine the success of community-based forest management programs. Similarly, Rukundo (2018) found that ineffective governance structures in Zambia hindered the long-term sustainability of PFM programs. These studies highlight the importance of establishing strong governance frameworks that prioritize

transparency, effective communication, and equitable resource distribution to ensure the success of forest management initiatives.

The findings from this study reveal significant challenges in community forest governance, particularly related to accountability, transparency, and equity in benefit-sharing. While participatory decision-making is emphasized, practical issues such as financial mismanagement, shifting priorities, and resource constraints hinder the effectiveness of CFM programs. Moreover, the influence of local elites, such as chiefs, often results in unequal enforcement of laws and an inequitable distribution of benefits, exacerbating social inequalities and undermining the goals of CFM. To address these challenges, there is a need for stronger governance frameworks that ensure transparency in financial management, consistent enforcement of community laws, and equitable distribution of benefits. Without these elements, CFM programs will continue to struggle in achieving their full potential in improving livelihoods and promoting sustainable forest management.

4.8.2 The Effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance Practices

The empirical findings and literature on REDD+ highlight the critical role of governance structures in shaping the outcomes of these programs. REDD+ is designed to reduce emissions through forest conservation, and its success is deeply influenced by how governance frameworks are structured, particularly in relation to local community involvement, benefit-sharing, and the balance of power between state and community actors. This discussion synthesizes these insights, focusing on how REDD+ influences governance structures in terms of environmental sustainability and socioeconomic well-being.

a) Governance and Local Participation

REDD+ significantly influences the governance structure by encouraging a shift toward greater local participation in forest management. The financial incentives tied to carbon credits have motivated local communities to become more proactive in forest protection, as observed in the empirical data, where revenues are allocated to community development needs such as infrastructure and education (Gautum et al., 2021). This approach fosters a collaborative governance model, where local leaders, supported by the forestry department, play a pivotal role in overseeing forest resources and ensuring equitable distribution of benefits. The involvement of community leaders in managing forest resources demonstrates how REDD+ has driven a move towards more decentralized and participatory decision-making. This shift is aligned with Adaptive Governance Theory, which stresses the importance of decentralized

governance systems that promote flexibility, collaboration, and the inclusion of local knowledge in decision-making processes. REDD+ is encouraging such changes by creating spaces for local leadership and community control over forest management.

However, while REDD+ has decentralized some aspects of forest governance, it also reveals the tensions between state and local control. Despite the program's intent to empower local communities, the empirical findings show that state control often overrides local authority, limiting the influence of local actors. In many cases, REDD+ revenues are funneled through state-managed mechanisms, and local decision-making is constrained by central governance structures. This centralization has been noted in the Ghanaian context, where local actors struggle to exercise full control over forest management (Johnson, 2021; Gautum et al., 2021). REDD+ thus highlights a key tension in governance: while it can decentralize some elements of forest management, the overarching state control often diminishes the true empowerment of local communities. This discrepancy challenges the Multi-Level Governance Theory, which emphasizes the need for effective coordination across multiple levels of governance to facilitate shared authority and participation. In this case, REDD+ is pushing for greater local involvement but also reveals the persistence of top-down governance structures that undermine local agency.

Additionally, REDD+ has introduced challenges related to ensuring genuine local participation in decision-making. As the literature suggests, the focus on carbon outcomes in REDD+ programs sometimes leads to a top-down approach, where local communities are merely involved in the implementation rather than the design and decision-making phases. This lack of meaningful participation is a significant concern, as Adaptive Governance Theory emphasizes the importance of collaboration and continuous learning from local feedback. Despite this, REDD+ often imposes rigid frameworks that do not fully allow for local adaptive management, limiting the program's ability to adjust to changing circumstances at the community level. The empirical findings point to the crucial role of community leaders in managing carbon revenues and local projects, but ensuring that all members of the community, especially marginalized groups, have an equal voice in these processes remains a significant challenge as also noted by Gautum et al., (2021).

b) Equity and Benefit-sharing

Equitable benefit-sharing is another area where REDD+ influences governance structures, but not always in a way that promotes fairness. While REDD+ generates financial incentives that

are intended to be shared among local communities, the governance structures that manage this distribution often fail to ensure that all groups benefit equally. The empirical findings indicate that the revenues from REDD+ are often distributed among community leaders and local development projects, leading to improvements in infrastructure and education (Soliev, 2021). However, these benefits are not always equitably shared, with marginalized groups such as indigenous peoples, women, and low-income households often left out. This is consistent with findings in the literature, which suggest that many REDD+ programs are prone to elite capture, where powerful actors within the community appropriate the majority of the benefits (Soliev, 2021; Poudel et al., 2015).

REDD+ influences governance structures by prompting the development of benefit-sharing mechanisms, but these mechanisms often fail to address underlying issues such as land tenure and social inequalities. This concentration of benefits exacerbates existing social divides, as local elites are able to capture a disproportionate share of the revenues. The shift in governance structures introduced by REDD+ does not automatically translate to equity; instead, it requires that governance frameworks be carefully designed to include marginalized voices and ensure that all community members benefit. Multi-Level Governance Theory provides insight here, suggesting that for benefit-sharing mechanisms to be equitable, effective coordination across multiple levels of governance is necessary. However, in many cases, the failure to properly engage lower levels of governance or non-state actors limits the reach and fairness of benefit distribution.

Moreover, REDD+ can influence governance structures in such a way that communities are pushed to formalize land rights and redefine local leadership structures in response to the financial resources generated. These shifts can be positive, leading to more secure tenure and better governance, but they also risk reinforcing existing power imbalances within the community. Adaptive Governance Theory would argue that these challenges can be mitigated by allowing for adaptive decision-making processes that incorporate local feedback and continuously evolve based on experience. However, the centralized control over financial flows often impedes the flexibility and adaptive capacity needed to ensure equitable outcomes (Soliev, 2021).

c) Livelihoods and Socioeconomic Outcomes

REDD+ has had a significant impact on local livelihoods, primarily by providing financial resources that can be allocated to community development, such as improved infrastructure

and education. Similar to Poudel et al., (2015) empirical findings suggest that these positive outcomes have contributed to an improvement in local well-being, such as increased school enrollment and better access to services. However, the broader socioeconomic impact of REDD+ is influenced by the governance structures that manage the distribution of these resources. The literature highlights that, while REDD+ has provided income to communities, this income is not always directly linked to forest management or long-term economic stability. Studies by Scheba (2018) and Corbera et al. (2020) suggest that the socioeconomic impacts of REDD+ are limited unless deeper structural issues like land rights, market access, and governance capacity are addressed.

REDD+ influences governance structures by shifting the focus of local development toward carbon-driven funding mechanisms. This can result in improvements in specific areas, such as education and infrastructure, but it does not necessarily lead to long-term, transformative changes in wealth or economic stability. The governance structures that emerge in response to REDD+ often prioritize carbon-related outcomes over broader development goals, which can undermine the program's potential to address deeper socioeconomic issues. This reflects the critiques of Adaptive Governance Theory, which argues that governance systems must be flexible and capable of addressing the broader structural challenges that affect communities. Multi-Level Governance Theory also underscores the importance of a more integrated, cross-level approach to development that connects local interventions with regional and national policy objectives (Scheba, 2018).

d) Monitoring, Accountability, and Adaptive Management

Finally, REDD+ has introduced monitoring and accountability mechanisms, such as the Community Climate Biodiversity (CCB) audits, that evaluate the impact of the program on forest conservation and community livelihoods. These audits provide an important tool for assessing outcomes such as household income, infrastructure development, and social programs funded by carbon revenue as also noted in Corbera et al., (2020). However, the empirical findings emphasize that the rigid, standardized monitoring frameworks imposed by REDD+ can limit local flexibility in responding to environmental and economic changes. This reflects a key tension in REDD+ governance structures, where accountability mechanisms are necessary, but overly restrictive rules can stifle local adaptive management.

REDD+ has influenced governance by introducing monitoring tools that track the effectiveness of programs, but the flexibility required for adaptive management is often constrained by the

rigidity of these frameworks. Adaptive Governance Theory stresses that governance systems need to be flexible, responsive, and adaptive to the evolving needs of communities, especially in complex and dynamic social-ecological contexts. Multi-Level Governance Theory highlights the importance of coordination across multiple levels of governance to allow for the exchange of knowledge and the adjustment of strategies in response to emerging challenges. The empirical findings indicate that for REDD+ to be more effective, local governance structures must be able to manage forests and livelihoods flexibly, adjusting to both environmental changes and shifting community priorities as noted by Poudel et al., (2015) and Gautum et al., (2021).

REDD+ has had a profound influence on governance structures, particularly in terms of local participation, equity, livelihoods, and adaptive management. While it has encouraged decentralized decision-making and the redistribution of benefits, REDD+ has also revealed the limitations of current governance frameworks, particularly in addressing issues of power imbalances, local participation, and long-term socioeconomic impacts. By emphasizing flexibility, collaboration, and responsiveness, Adaptive Governance Theory and Multi-Level Governance Theory offer valuable insights into how REDD+ can influence governance systems to better support sustainable forest management and equitable development. However, for REDD+ to achieve its full potential, governance structures must be continuously adapted to local needs, challenges, and opportunities.

4.8.3 The Effect of REDD+ on Rural Livelihood Outcomes Among CFMGs in Zambia

The study explores the multifaceted role of REDD+ initiatives in improving the livelihoods of rural communities, while contributing to both forest conservation and climate change mitigation. These findings demonstrate how REDD+ activities have resulted in notable improvements in local livelihoods, particularly through infrastructural development, agricultural practices, and income diversification. These outcomes align with broader discussions on REDD+, which emphasize the dual purpose of these initiatives in enhancing local welfare while simultaneously achieving environmental goals (Fischer et al., 2023; Kim, 2023). The findings can be analyzed using the framework of the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA), which offers valuable insights into how various forms of capital shape the strategies communities adopt to improve their livelihoods and manage their natural resources sustainably.

a) Livelihood Improvements through REDD+ Initiatives

A central finding of this study is the significant improvement in local livelihoods as a direct result of REDD+ activities. One of the key contributions of these initiatives is the generation of carbon revenues through forest conservation efforts, which are then used to fund vital community development projects. These projects, such as the construction of schools, clinics, and boreholes, enhance the community's physical infrastructure and contribute to overall wellbeing. Respondent 2's insight into how carbon payments have been directed towards local development aligns with findings by Andoh et al. (2024), who emphasize the importance of aligning REDD+ initiatives with local community needs to achieve more effective and sustainable outcomes. In the context of the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, these infrastructure projects represent an enhancement of the community's physical capital, which is vital for improving access to essential services, promoting health, and fostering overall development.

Moreover, the introduction of climate-smart agriculture and integrated gardening techniques has played a crucial role in improving food security while simultaneously reducing pressure on forested areas. Respondent 2 described how these farming methods allowed communities to increase agricultural productivity without encroaching upon forests, which are vital for the community's long-term survival. This approach aligns with the broader literature on balancing development and environmental goals, as seen in the work of Nantongo et al. (2024), who discuss the delicate balance between improving livelihoods and ensuring environmental sustainability. By adopting these new agricultural techniques, communities can reduce deforestation while still enhancing their economic outcomes, thus improving both their environmental and economic capital, which are key aspects of the SLA.

The provision of livestock, such as goats and chickens, has also proven to be a vital source of income and food security for many households. Participants in focus group discussions, such as FGD participant B10, highlighted how livestock has supported families by providing a means of meeting household needs and facilitating investment in education. This diversification of income sources helps reduce pressure on forest resources and further supports the community's financial capital. The benefits of income diversification are consistent with the findings of Andoh et al. (2024), who emphasize the importance of offering communities alternative income-generating opportunities in addition to traditional forest-based livelihoods.

b) Social Capital and Community Empowerment

A crucial aspect of the success of REDD+ initiatives in this context is the role of community participation and governance. The study underscores how the involvement of local communities in the management and governance of forest resources is essential for the long-term success of REDD+ projects. Respondent 2 highlighted the importance of training and capacity-building programs that empower local communities to actively participate in forest management and carbon markets. This approach is consistent with the work of Fischer et al. (2023) and Kim (2023), who argue that strong community governance is essential for the success of forest restoration projects. Through participatory governance and decision-making, REDD+ initiatives help build social capital by fostering trust, cooperation, and shared responsibility among community members. In the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, social capital is a key element that helps communities address challenges, manage risks, and implement sustainable livelihood strategies.

The establishment of local governance structures, such as committees to manage funds and oversee the distribution of carbon revenues, ensures that REDD+ benefits are used transparently and equitably. The study found that this participatory approach has strengthened the social fabric of the community, as many respondents noted that the creation of local management committees has improved trust and cooperation among community members. Respondent 2's description of financial management practices, such as the use of annual work plans, further illustrates how effective governance structures can contribute to the responsible use of funds and the sustainable management of resources. This aligns with the SLA's focus on the importance of local institutions in building social capital and ensuring that development interventions are both effective and sustainable.

c) Challenges to Sustainable Livelihoods

While the study highlights numerous benefits of REDD+ initiatives, it also identifies several challenges that could undermine the long-term sustainability of these interventions. One of the primary concerns is the potential over-reliance on external carbon financing, which could discourage long-term planning and self-sufficiency. Respondent 2 pointed out that large one-time payments, such as the 12 million Kwacha received by the community of Lwembe, may create a sense of dependency rather than encouraging communities to develop more sustainable livelihoods. This concern echoes critiques of intentional development approaches, which often rely on external funding without fostering local ownership or capacity for long-term

sustainability (Morse & McNamara, 2013). Groom & Palmer (2012) also argue that short-term financial incentives can undermine the sustainability of conservation efforts by shifting focus away from long-term planning.

In addition, land tenure insecurity remains a significant challenge for many communities involved in REDD+ initiatives. The study reveals how unclear land tenure arrangements in some areas may hinder communities' ability to fully benefit from carbon payments and other REDD+ incentives. The importance of secure land tenure is well-documented in the literature, with Manda & Mukanda (2023) emphasizing that secure land rights are essential for ensuring that REDD+ initiatives lead to equitable and sustainable outcomes. Without clear land tenure, communities may struggle to access and control the financial rewards generated through forest conservation, which can lead to conflict and inequitable distribution of benefits.

Furthermore, the study highlights the continued barriers that limited access to markets and financial services pose for many rural communities. As noted by Andoh et al. (2024), without access to markets or credit, rural households may struggle to capitalize on their agricultural and forest-based products, which limits their ability to diversify their income sources. In response to this challenge, the study suggests that the establishment of cooperatives and the provision of financial support to these groups could help address this gap, allowing communities to access broader markets, improve their economic capital, and reduce reliance on forest resources.

d) Balancing Development and Forest Conservation

For rural communities in Sub-Saharan Africa, REDD+ offers a unique opportunity to balance the pressures of development with the need for forest conservation. Respondent 2 noted that the primary drivers of deforestation in the study area were agricultural expansion and charcoal production, both essential livelihood activities for the community. Without providing viable alternatives to these activities, efforts to reduce deforestation could inadvertently harm community livelihoods. This dilemma is consistent with the findings of Manda & Mukanda (2023), who argue that halting deforestation without offering alternative livelihood options will likely lead to failure.

The REDD+ mechanism offers a potential solution by providing financial rewards for forest conservation efforts. By participating in carbon markets, communities can generate income from forest conservation, thereby supporting their economic needs and environmental goals. This approach allows communities to secure a livelihood while preserving the forest, highlighting the potential of REDD+ to reconcile development and environmental protection.

This balancing act is central to the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach, which emphasizes the need to consider the full range of capitals such as human, social, physical, natural, and financial, and how they interact to support sustainable development.

This study underscores the positive impacts of REDD+ on rural livelihoods, particularly through improved infrastructure, income diversification, and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices. However, it also highlights several challenges that need to be addressed for the long-term success of REDD+ initiatives, such as over-reliance on external financing, land tenure insecurity, and limited access to markets and financial services. These findings align with broader critiques of the Sustainable Livelihoods Theory, which stresses the importance of context-specific interventions and a comprehensive understanding of the assets that underpin livelihoods. To ensure the continued success of REDD+ in enhancing both livelihoods and forest conservation, policies must focus on promoting sustainability, self-reliance, and equitable distribution of benefits, thereby addressing the key challenges identified in this study.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter is divided into four sections. Section one is the summary of the study; section two highlights the recommendation based on the findings; section three is the conclusion of the study; and lastly, the fourth section highlights areas for further research.

5.1 Summary of the Study

Forests are invaluable natural resources that provide essential ecosystem services and related advantages on a variety of scales. In the tropics, forests are essential to local communities' well-being, especially for rural households that depend on them (FAO, 2010). They help to sustain current consumption, provide as a safety net during times of crisis, offer dependable cash income, and may even provide a way out of poverty for households that depend on the forest for their livelihood. As estimated by FAO's (2014), 1.6 billion people depending on forests, Chao (2012) estimates that forests directly support the livelihoods of 500,000 indigenous people and 1.3 billion people worldwide as such households rely more heavily on forests for subsistence needs (e.g. fuel wood, wild foods, medicinal herbs) than wealthy households. Additionally, they aid biological processes, lessen the risk of natural disasters, and store 2.1 Gt of CO₂ year between 2011 and 2015. The sustainable flow of these advantages for societal well-being, economic growth, and biodiversity preservation depends on effective forest management (FAO, 2015).

Previously, forest governance practice was characterized by a centralized tight protectionist strategy to safeguard tropical forests from exploitation and human activities in order to counter the threat of resource loss. However, this strategy proved to be a futile exercise as governments alone were not efficient to ensure the protection of forest resources. The surrounding communities to the protected areas could not take ownership of the forests hence foreign entities would exploit forests without them being concerned. In this regard participatory forest management emerged as a strategy to partner with the local communities in the protection of forest resources. However, previous forms of PFM discouraged the participation of communities in forest management as they had limited rights to forest resources i.e. all commercial usage of forest resources were retained by the governments. Other issues such as equity in the distribution of benefits became of great concern. This in one way or the other led to massive exploitation of forests, an estimation of 156,000 hectares of forest were destroyed between 2000 and 2014 in the eastern province of Zambia. Hence, in 2014 the national strategy to reduce deforestation and forest degradation was created by government to promote resilience

to climate change. This together with the global agenda to mitigate climate through carbon sequestration, REDD+, it became recognized that CFMGs were the primary channels through which the goal could be achieved. The objectives of these policies are to improve forest conditions, empower communities, and provide sustainable livelihoods for poverty reduction (Charnley & Poe, 2007; Maryudi et al., 2012). CBFM method is predicated on the idea that balancing conservation and local needs by promoting livelihoods and initiatives that benefit communities economically will help win over the local population and mitigate risks to biodiversity. However, weak governance practices characterized by heightened financial incentives and benefits, along with weak enforcement and monitoring may accelerate resource extraction and exploitation. Hence the aim of this study was to determine the effect of REDD+ on community forest governance practices and rural livelihoods in Zambia. To support this main aim, the study addresses the following specific objectives:

- To examine the relationship between Community Forest Governance Practices and rural livelihood outcomes in Zambia.
- To determine the effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance practices in Zambia.
- To investigate the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihood outcomes among CFMGs in Zambia.
- To determine the challenges in governance faced by CFMGs in Zambia under the REDD+ implementation and their associated rural livelihood outcomes.

The study reviewed literature on the evolution of forest governance during the colonial era and the post-colonial era which subsequently led to forest governance policy reforms establishing community forest management in Zambia. This background provided a foundation on how the REDD+ initiative came to become part of community forestry. Three broader theories were used to guide the study. The first theory, forest governance decentralization theory (adaptive governance; and multi-level governance), highlighted on the evolution of forest governance i.e. from being centrally oriented by governments to the inclusion of multipolar institutional entities in the governance of public goods. These theories provide a general background to the rise of community based natural resource management before arriving at forest governance by community institutions as units of analysis and how they affect forest sustainability and livelihood outcomes. The second broader theory, Common-pool Resource governance theory

(tragedy of the commons; and common-pool resource theory). These theories narrow natural resource governance down to the context of traditional African society using a historical approach. Lastly, the sustainable livelihoods theory which explains how different interventions for development ought to be aligned with what underpins livelihoods and context specific. This theory was considered to be important for the current study as it purported to explain how the absence of livelihood concerns in development interventions might not lead to the desired outcomes.

The study adopted a mixed approach, integrating components of quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Mixed methods supported data collection and integration of socio-economic and ecological data, providing a deep understanding of complex socio-ecological systems in the Luangwa Game Management Areas in Nyimba district of Eastern province. This research is interdisciplinary and examines the multifaceted interactions between socio-economic issues, institutional governance, and ecological conditions. This was accomplished by using a variety of data sources, including surveys, in-depth interviews, focus groups and participant observation, which will support data triangulation and corroboration, increased the study's scientific rigor, and strengthened the validity of the findings. The primary target population consisted of 385 households in REDD+ areas in Nyimba District; whereas the secondary targets consisted of government officials and implementing partners. Data was collected using administered questionnaires and focus group discussions for the primary respondents. Whereas in-depth interviews were conducted with the secondary respondents. Descriptive, predictive and exploratory statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS and Excel computer programmes. Findings were summarized in frequencies and percentages and presented in tabular forms. Content analysis was used to analyze qualitative data.

5.2 Conclusion

The study found that indeed governance practices among CFMGs have a significant relationship with livelihood outcomes. The devolution of forest governance to community level would imply that the marginalized members being worse off as stringent rules affect their major livelihood activity such as charcoal burning. Thus, equity concerns ought to be applied in the governance of forest resources by the communities. In terms of accountability and transparency, community members lacking a system to access information on the progress related to community project might conceal information that might affect efficiency and effectiveness in terms of community resources. The findings also revealed that information on

benefit sharing between committee members of CFMGs and communities was not disclosed or agreed upon. It was found that societal customs and traditions influenced community's ability to question authorities or leaders. This could indicate the possibilities of committee members being able to derive more benefits from community conservation efforts. This lack of information led to various speculations among community members which might be detrimental to the CFMG committees. Statistically, the study also found that the higher the expenditure reporting was, the higher the livelihood outcomes among community members. The study also found rule of law and policy enforcement was statistically related to positive livelihood outcomes such as access to water at a community level. Other governance practices such as participation contribution in decision making; and the selection of officials were highly perceived among community members.

Benefits that affected the entire community such as access to health; education; and knowledge and information under human capital. Social capital and natural capital were also not problematic in these communities. However, when it came to aspects that go down to the household level such as access to produced goods; machinery; household equipment; livestock – under physical capital; and all aspects of financial capital, there were high levels of dissatisfaction among respondents. Similarly, findings by Mahanty et al., (2009) indicated that forestry income in most cases is diverted from individual households to community level.

On the effect of REDD+ on CFMG governance practices, the initiative received high perception in it having contributed to governance practices positively. The findings indicate that community members have become cautious in their day to day usage of forest resources. REDD+ has aided and in most cases facilitated the establishment of CFMGs and frequency of meetings with community members. This has led to high levels of participation among community members. Also, as a result of REDD+ CFMG committee members have been trained on good governance practices such as financial management systems and others. This is done on a regular basis. Exchange visits have also been facilitated for CFMG committee members to improve governance practices. However, the findings indicated that more entrenched issues of class, caste, ethnicity, gender and spatiality are over looked by the REDD+ initiatives. There were instances where resources meant for the development projects such as a maternity wing were diverted to the chief's palace or a traditional ceremony. Furthermore, information solicited from FDGs indicated that some CFMG committee members have become wealthy in short periods of time. Hence it becomes essential for information regarding financial reporting and project cycle to be made available to community members at all times. According

to findings, the financial incentive from REDD+ is managed by the community members themselves, other stakeholders such as the Forestry department provided technical advice to these communities. Hence, a government representative commented that there was a possibility that government would start deriving some benefit from these resources as this was still under discussion by the relevant authorities. This raised concern by community members who have had their livelihood transformed without the government's major involvement. At the same time, the government representative stated that there was no need to have such concerns as the forest act of 2015 gave all rights to forest resources to the community. These findings indicate that there is a subtle struggle for the control of REDD+ resources among the traditional leadership, forestry department and the representatives of the communities (CFMGs) during which in certain instances communities are left to speculate while deriving some benefit. In some instances, the opportunity cost of solely depending on REDD+ resources and completely abandoning forest resources is higher as equity concerns might not be considered; or REDD+ resources might not be aligned to the needs of the community.

Lastly, on the effect of REDD+ on rural livelihoods, the findings indicate that the initiative has positively affected several dimensions of livelihood outcomes as it has provided numerous opportunities for both community members and CFMG committee members to get exposure to livelihood alternatives. Training coupled with seed capital has also been provided both at individual household level and group level to carry out business ventures that would enhance human capital. This is in addition to agricultural training that has been provided to boost productivity on the same piece of land without having to expand to forest land. REDD+ has also provided opportunities for community members to expand access to social capital as it creates a platform which permits frequent meetings with all community members. On physical capital, REDD+ was highly appreciated by community members with regards to water infrastructure (boreholes); the construction of a market though it stalled i.e. not yet completed since 2021; repairmen of the community bridge; construction of a maternity wing; construction of houses for teachers and many other initiatives. However, physical assets at household level were not significantly impacted. Also given that vastness of the chiefdom and the amount of forest land under protection determines the amount of carbon finance received, some households might not be receiving sufficient benefit for their forest conservation efforts. Thereby creating a situation where REDD+ has locked community members in carbon contract which might not be flexible enough to cater for the livelihood needs of communities.

5.3 Recommendations

Addressing the complex challenges of forest governance and community livelihoods in Zambia requires a collaborative effort involving multiple stakeholders. Policy makers should prioritize integrating transparency, accountability, and community participation into forest management policies. Strengthening institutional capacities and ensuring effective oversight are crucial. Community members need to be empowered to participate actively, while implementing partners and funders should collaborate closely with communities to address their needs. It is essential for the government to foster an enabling environment for inclusive forest governance and collaborate with international partners for resources and expertise. Through concerted efforts, Zambia can make significant strides towards sustainable forest management and improved livelihoods.

a) Policy Makers

- Emphasize the importance of good governance practices such as efficiency, accountability, transparency, and benefit sharing in forest management policies.
- Ensure that policy implementation frameworks prioritize the capacity building of community forest management group (CFMG) committee members to mitigate incompetency and lack of exposure.
- Develop policies that facilitate collaboration between CFMGs and technical expertise to ensure appropriate project implementation and procurement of quality materials.
- Introduce and enforce systematic accountability mechanisms within REDD+ activities to provide transparency in fund disbursement and project progress.
- Review and adapt REDD+ financing mechanisms to better align with community needs and ensure equitable distribution of benefits.

b) Community Members (CFMGs)

- Advocate for inclusion and active participation in decision-making processes related to forest management and REDD+ projects.
- Seek opportunities for capacity building and training to enhance competencies in project implementation and management.
- Collaborate with implementing partners and funders to ensure that projects align with community needs and priorities (costs).
- Demand transparency and accountability in the management of REDD+ funds and project implementation.

- Engage in discussions and negotiations to expand forest protected areas and ensure fair compensation for the protection of forest resources.

c) Implementing Partners

- Provide technical expertise and capacity-building support to CFMGs to improve project implementation and management practices.
- Collaborate closely with community members to understand their needs and preferences when designing and implementing projects.
- Ensure the use of quality materials and adherence to project timelines to avoid project stalling and incomplete implementation.
- Establish robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to track project progress and outcomes, and facilitate learning and adaptation.
- Engage in dialogue with policy makers and funders to advocate for policies and financing mechanisms that better support community needs and priorities.

d) Funders

- Prioritize funding for capacity building initiatives aimed at improving governance practices and project management skills among CFMG members.
- Support initiatives that promote transparency, accountability, and community participation in REDD+ projects and forest governance processes.
- Provide flexible financing mechanisms that allow for adaptive management and response to changing community needs and circumstances.
- Invest in research and evaluation to assess the effectiveness and impact of REDD+ projects on livelihoods and forest conservation outcomes.
- Collaborate with policy makers, implementing partners, and community members to co-design funding strategies that address the identified challenges and promote sustainable development goals.

e) Government

- Strengthen institutional capacities and provide resources for effective oversight and enforcement of forest governance policies to ensure adherence to good governance principles.
- Promote the inclusion of marginalized communities, especially indigenous groups and women, in decision-making processes related to forest management and REDD+ projects.

- Develop and implement policies that prioritize the protection of community land rights and ensure equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms to enhance social equity and reduce inequalities.
- Invest in education and training programs to build the technical and managerial capacities of local government officials responsible for overseeing forest management activities.
- Collaborate with international partners and organizations to access technical assistance, funding, and best practices for improving forest governance and implementing REDD+ initiatives.
- Conduct regular monitoring and evaluation of forest governance practices and REDD+ projects to assess their effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.
- Engage in dialogue with stakeholders, including civil society organizations and community representatives, to solicit feedback, address grievances, and foster greater transparency and accountability in forest management processes.

5.4 Areas for Further Research

REDD+ is a recent phenomenon which has not been investigated at a larger scale either at country level or regional levels. Hence it can be recommended for a similar study to be conducted either in another region within the country, or in a different country, or at the level of a sub region such as SADC, EAC, ECOWAS or the entire continent of Africa.

Further research needs to be conducted to understand the effects of customs and traditions in the implementation of REDD+ community development projects. This would indicate which traditions might hinder or contribute to the development of community projects.

Community members during seed distribution from REDD+

Abandoned community gardening REDD+ project due to poor governance practices

From left to right: Imikani Banda (Research Assistant); Chief Luembe; Jonah Kondowe (Principle Investigator); and Grace (REDD+ Implementing partner representative)

Principal investigator conducting a focus group discussion

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Questionnaire for Primary Respondents

DATA COLLECTION SAMPLE QUESTIONNAIRE

NAME OF ENUMERATOR: _____ DATE: _____

CBFG: _____ CONSTITUENCY: _____ SUB LOCATION: _____

VILLAGE: _____

1.0 Socio Demographic Information (household head/spouse)

Notes

a. Household heads (CFMG/CRBs members and non-CFG members) to be interviewed or if absent, relatives (Spouses, sons, daughters etc.) over 18 years of age and familiar with the running of the household affairs to be interviewed to provide the required information.

b. Respondent to make a comment where other members of the household chip in during the interview (Make a mark on the questionnaire)

c. Household in this research comprises of a family/people which cook and eat together

1.1 Household head:

Yes =1 No =2

1.2 If No, Relationship to household head:

1.3 Gender:

Male= 1 Female= 2

1.4 Age: years

1.5 Tribe:

1.6 Number of people living in your household:

1.7 Education & number of years spent schooling

None (0) Primary (1) Secondary (2) Tertiary /diploma / Certificate (3)
University degree (4)

1.8 Years lived in this area:

1.9 Religious affiliation

1.10 Respondent code number (from list): Mobile No:

2.0 Livelihoods Outcomes

Human Capital

- 2.1 How many trainings have you attended in the past 12 months?
- 2.2 List down any form of training attended and provider
- 2.3 Do you have access to formal health care?
- 2.4 What are your major sources of information?

Social Capital

- 2.5 Do you belong to any networking/association group in this village? (tick)
Yes =1 No =0
- 2.6 List the types of social group membership
- 2.7 Are you a CFMG/CRB member?
Yes =1 No =0
- 2.8 If yes, what is the name of the CFMG of your membership?

Natural Capital

- 2.6 Does your household own land? (tick)
Yes =1 No = 0
- 2.7 If yes, what type of ownership (tick) and size (in acres) does your household own?

Inherited	Size:
Lease/rent in the forest	Size:
Lease/rent elsewhere	Size:
Owned/purchased	Size:
Others, specify	Size

- 2.8 Do you know the importance of Luangwa Game Management Area in your day to day livelihoods? (tick)
Yes =1 No = 0

- 2.9 If Yes above, list down the benefits you get from the forest important to you and your household.

a. Wild fruits g. Feed for zero grazing m. Charcoal production

Financial Capital

2.15 Are you involved in any kind of employment? (tick)

Yes =1 No =0

2.16 What is your main occupation?

2.17 List up to five main sources of household income carried out in the last 12 months and the proportion of total amount earned in the period.

2.18 Have you borrowed any money from a financial institution in the last 12 months?

2.19 Can you comment on some of the hindrances community members face in accessing loans or credit.

2.20 Current levels of livelihood outcomes

How would you rate your level of access to the following services and possessions?					
Human Capital	1	2	3	4	5
Level of access to knowledge					
Level of access to information					
Level of access to Education					
Level of access to Health Care					
Social Capital	1	2	3	4	5
Membership in informal networks					
Membership in formalized					
Relationships that facilitate co-operation and economic activities					
Natural Capital	1	2	3	4	5
Level of access to land					
Level of access to water resources					
Level of access to forest resources					
Level of access to fertile soils					
Physical Capital	1	2	3	4	5

Level of access to road infrastructure in the community					
Level of access to water infrastructure in the community					
Level of access to school infrastructure in the community					
Level of access to ICT infrastructure in the community					
Level of access to produced goods					
Level of machinery in possession					
Level of household equipment in possession					
Level of livestock in possession					
Financial Capital	1	2	3	4	5
Level of savings in possession					
Level of access to credit services or institutions					
Level of proportion of income from employment					
Level of proportion of income from remittances					

(1 = very poor; 5 = very good)

3.0 Governance Practices

- 3.1 For how long have you been a CFMG/CRB member?
- 3.2 Does membership affect the usage of forest resources mentioned in 2.9 above?
- 3.3 What benefits are you not allowed to get from the forest which you would like to harvest? List down.
- 3.4 List the main ways in which your participation in the CFMG has been a source of earning a living to you and the income earned annually in the last 12 months (September 2022 - September 2023).
- 3.5 Did you participate in the preparation of the management plan for your CFMG/CRB?
(tick)

Yes =1 No =0
- 3.6 If Yes above, did you give ideas/contributions/suggestions to be taken into account in the management plan?

3.7 Yes= 1 No =0 (If Yes, respondent to elaborate on contributions/ideas given and if were incorporated in plan)

3.8 Are you fully involved in decision making in your CFMGs? (e.g. rules and bylaws, fines to be paid, membership fees, activities to carry, who to implement them etc.)

Yes =1 No =0

3.9 (If Yes, respondent to elaborate on a variety of contributions made in decision making and give examples where applicable)

3.10 Who do you think most strongly influences the decisions made in your CFG by having a final say on the decisions made?

3.11 How do you agree with the statement below on a scale of 1 to 5 where 5 is strongly agree.

CFG members are only notified about decision(s) made without being granted the opportunity to influence the decision-making process (tick)	Strongly disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly agree 5
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3.12 Do you get sufficient information as you would like regarding the CFG, conservation, participation or, opportunities etc (tick.)

Never 1	Sometimes 2	Very often 3	Always 4
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3.13 Have you participated in meetings where all or some of stakeholders you mentioned in 4.2 were involved in joint review/ analysis of PFM (progress, challenges, review) to chat a way forward?

Yes = 1 No = 0

(If yes respondent to elaborate on his/her contributions during the meeting(s))

3.14 When the CFG members makes suggestions or opinions or decisions regarding PFM, the matter(s) are taken into consideration by CFG officials

3.15 Do you have ways/systems of holding CFG officials to be more accountable and transparent in the management of the CFG?

Yes= 1 No= 2 (Please elaborate your answer by giving examples)

3.16 Performance of Governance Practices in CFMG

Rate the performance of the forest governance practices in this CFMG.					
Accountability and Transparency	1	2	3	4	5
Election of group officials					
Voting Methods					
Selection of delegates					
Presiding officer(s) attendance					
AGM held as per constitution					
Income & Expenditure reports					
Efficiency and Collective action					
Constitution availability and maintenance					
Membership list maintenance					
Participation & Collective actions (1=very low; 5=very high)					
Participation (decision making & duty roster)					
Monitoring and Patrolling (security)					
Rule of law & Policy enforcement					
Benefit Sharing (1=very poor; very good)					
Forest products					
Plots for farming					

(1 = very poor; 5 = very good)
4.0

REDD+

I would like to find out on how the REDD+ activities in this CFMG has contributed to both governance practices and rural livelihood outcomes.

	REDD+ Community Forest Governance Initiatives	1	2	3	4	5
4.1	REDD+ activities has improved overall community forest management					
4.2	REDD+ has improved forest conditions (regeneration and restoration)					
4.3	REDD+ initiative provides for fair sharing of benefits and opportunities is among all CFG members					
4.4	REDD+ initiative has enabled the sharing of benefits to be fair between us in CFMGs and FD/Govt					
4.5	REDD + activities provide for the active participation in decision making on matters of forest conservation and utilization in our CFG					
4.6	REDD+ activities provide for improvements in the leadership by CFMGs					

(1= strongly disagree; 5= strongly agree)

	REDD+ Rural Livelihood initiatives	1	2	3	4	5
4.6	REDD+ has brought about initiatives that improves community access to Natural resources.					
4.7	REDD+ has brought initiatives that improves community knowledge and skills					
4.8	REDD+ has brought initiatives that encourage social group membership					
4.9	REDD+ has enabled community to be able to afford new household assets					
4.10	REDD+ has brought community development projects e.g water, schools, markets					

(1= strongly disagree; 5= strongly agree)

5.0 Governance Practices and Rural livelihood outcomes

5.1 Do you think that the way forests are governed by the CFMG contribute to rural livelihood outcomes for community members?

5.2 Kindly justify the answer given in 5.1

6.0 REDD+ and Rural Livelihoods

6.1 Do you think that the REDD+ initiative has contributed to Rural livelihood outcomes for the community?

6.2 Kindly justify the answer given in 6.1

7.0 REDD+, Governance Practices and Rural Livelihood Outcomes

7.1 Do you think that the efforts put in place by REDD+ in improving Governance practices also translates in improved livelihood outcomes for community members?

7.2 Kindly justify the answer given in 7.2

We have come to the end of the interview. Thank you for your time.

Appendix 2: Guide for Focus Group Discussion

NAME OF ENUMERATOR: _____ DATE: _____

CBFG: _____ CONSTITUENCY: _____ SUB LOCATION: _____

VILLAGE: _____

- 1) What livelihood benefits do you derive from the Luangwa Game Management Areas?
- 2) Would you regard forest resources as important to daily household needs? Please explain the reason for your answer.
- 3) How has your membership in community resources management influenced your access to forest resources?
- 4) Kindly explain the various types and resources derived from the GMA and uses by order of importance.
- 5) How has the REDD+ project contributed to your livelihoods such as
 - a) Natural Capital
 - b) Your Skills and knowledge
 - c) Group Membership
 - d) Your assets at home
 - e) capital in the community
- 6) Can you comment on the how you select officials to govern the CFMG/CRMG under CRBs?
- 7) Explain the extent to which you would consider the selection process fair and just.
- 8) Can you comment on the extent to which the documents such as constitution and membership list of the CRMG/CFMG are well maintained and accessible?
- 9) Can you explain on how engaged you are in making decisions on issues concerning use and management of forests in the group?
- 10) How do you deal with non-compliance in the CFMG/CRMG?
- 11) Can you comment on how benefits are shared within the Group? Will you consider the process fair? Please explain.
- 12) How has REDD+ contributed to forest governance practices
 - a) accountability and transparency
 - b) Efficiency
 - c) Participation and Collective action
 - d) Benefit Sharing among community members

Appendix 3: Interview Guide for Selected Officials

NAME OF ENUMERATOR: _____ DATE: _____

CBFG: _____ CONSTITUENCY: _____ SUB LOCATION: _____

VILLAGE: _____

- 1) Is there link between how forests are governed by community forest management groups and livelihood outcomes?
- 2) Can you explain on the governance challenges faced by the CNRM/CFMGs groups in Luangwa GMA?
 - a) accountability and transparency
 - b) Efficiency
 - c) Participation and Collective action
 - d) Benefit Sharing among community members
- 3) What efforts are being put in place to by your organization to improve local community forest governance practices in your operating areas?
- 4) Do community livelihoods pose a threat to forest conservation efforts by your organization?
- 5) How is the REDD+ project addressing these challenges?
- 6) How do the REDD+ activities address the livelihoods needs of the communities in the Luangwa GMAs?
 - a) Natural Capital
 - b) Skills and knowledge
 - c) Group Membership
 - d) Your assets at home
 - e) capital in the community
- 7) Do you have in your possession some documented achievements by your organization regarding community governance practices and livelihoods that this study would refer to?

Work Plan

Year	Activity	Duration	Start	Actual Duration	Actual start												
Months						1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
2022	Topic Development	4	8	4	8				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
2023	Topic Defense	3	3	3	3			■									
	Proposal Development	4	3	4	3			■	■								
	Lit. Review	5	5	5	5					■							
	Methodology	6	6	6	6						■						
	2nd Draft Proposal Review	6	6	6	6						■						
	Proposal Refinement	6	6	6	6						■						
	Proposal Approval	6	6	7	7						■	■					
	Data Collection	7	7	8	9							■	■				
	Data Entry	1	1	1	1										■	■	
2024	Data Analysis	2	2	2	2		■										
	1st Draft Thesis Write Up	3	3	5	5			■	■	■							
	Review of 1st Draft	6	6	7	7						■	■					
	Refinement of 1st Draft	8	8	8	8								■				
	Final Thesis Draft	9	9	9	9									■			
	Final Preparations	10	10	10	10										■		
	Preparations and Submission for defense	11	11	12	12											■	■

Key:

Complete	■
Incomplete	■
In-progress	■

Proposed Research Articles

The following gaps were identified in literature:

- There is little literature on community governance inside communities, although there is a wealth of research on the connection between government and communities. In the literature, there are still few studies and reports that discuss within-community governance, and those that do frequently focus on extremely particular issues. Hence, without examining the factors that contribute to favorable outcomes or how to scale them up, these scholars have also concentrated on the causes and mitigation techniques for within-community governance's negative effects. There hasn't been much of a holistic view of governance as a result. Especially in light of recent events, where the majority of countries worldwide have embraced REDD+ with an emphasis on SFM and governance.
- There is a gap in literature in Zambia regarding the governance of local institutions such as community forest management groups and their associated outcomes on forest conservation and livelihoods. A few studies have been conducted on how REDD+ has influenced governance practices and livelihood outcomes among community forest management groups. Taking cognizance that community forest management groups might score differently in terms of governance practices and livelihood outcomes.
- REDD+ activities are a recent phenomenon in community forestry, and are perceived to either further decentralize forest governance, granting more power and decision making to the marginalized communities, at the same time there are skeptics on REDD+ activities taking power and decision making from the affected communities. There are also speculations in literature on how REDD+ has the potential of reinforcing the prevailing challenges in community forest governance such as elite capture and not being representative of livelihood needs.

Based on the research gap identified during the proposal development, the following are the proposed articles to be derived from the current research.

- 1) Local Forest Governance Practices and associated livelihood outcomes in Zambia
- 2) The role of REDD+ in structuring Community Forest Governance in Zambia
- 3) The effect of REDD+ on livelihood outcomes of forest dependent communities in Zambia

Appendix 4: Ethical clearance form (PAN African University; and University of Zambia Ethical Clearance Committee)

 UNIVERSITE PANAFRICAINNE / PAN AFRICAN UNIVERSITY
Institut de Gouvernance, des Sciences Humaines et Sociales
Institute of Governance, Humanities, and Social Sciences
Siège institutionnel : Université de Yaoundé II-SOA, CAMEROUN
Host institution: University of Yaoundé II-SOA, CAMEROON

Ref: N°2023/ 139.5 /PAU/IGHSS/D/DAai/AR 07 AOÛT 2023

Subject: Authorization for Research 2022/2023

To Whom it May Concern

Sir/Madam,

It is with honor and respect I present to you one of our Ph.D students, Mr. **KONDOWE JONAH**, born on **19/04/1991** at **Lusaka** with registration number **19G338** at the Institute of Governance, Humanities and Social Sciences of the Pan African University of the African Union. HE intends to carry on his academic research on "The Effect of REDD+ on Community Forest Governance Practices and Rural Livelihoods in Zambia: The Case of Nyimba District, Eastern Province". **The research will be carried out in Nyimba District, Eastern Province (Zambia).**

The Pan African University was established by the decision of the fifteenth Ordinary Session of the Assembly of Heads of State and Governments of the African Union (Assembly/AU/Dec.290 (XV), of July 27 2010 in Kampala Uganda.

Sir/Madam, as a condition to obtain a Ph.D degree at the Pan African university, the students are obliged to go on the field for empirical research and gather data. We are pleading with you to facilitate the possibility of our student obtain information for her Ph.D thesis.

We wish to emphasis that every information obtained will be strictly for academic purpose. This ethical consideration is imperative for the Ph.D study and our university.

While expecting a positive response from you, I wish to thank you most sincerely for facilitating entry of our student in your reputable institution for research. It is with great honor and respect I hereby make this request.

The Academic Registrar:
Prof. Nsoh Ndikum

ACADEMIC REGISTRAR

Tel : 670 20 22 17 - B.P. 35065, Université de Yaoundé II-Soa, Cameroun
Site internet : www.paughss-au.org E-mail : director@paughss-au.org

THE UNIVERSITY OF ZAMBIA
DIRECTORATE OF RESEARCH AND GRADUATE STUDIES

Great East Road Campus | P.O. Box 32379 | Lusaka 10101 | Tel: +260-211-290 258/291 777 Fax: (+260)-211-290
258/253 952 | E-mail: director.drgrs@unza.zm | Website: www.unza.zm

APPROVAL OF STUDY

IORG No. 0005376
HSSREC IRB No. 00006464
REF NO. HSSREC-2023-SEPT-023

22nd September, 2023

Mr. Jonah Kondowe
The University of Zambia
P.O. Box 32379

LUSAKA

Dear Mr. Kondowe

RE: “THE EFFECT OF REDD+ ON COMMUNITY FOREST GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AND RURAL LIVELIHOOD IN ZAMBIA. THE CASE OF NYIMBA DISTRICT, EASTERN PROVINCE.”

Reference is made to your submission of the protocol captioned above.

The HSSREC resolved to approve this study and your participation as Principal Investigator for a period of one year.

Specific conditions will apply to this approval. As Principal Investigator it is your responsibility to ensure that the contents of this letter are adhered to. If these are not adhered to, the approval may be suspended. Should the study be suspended, study sponsors and other regulatory authorities will be informed.

REVIEW TYPE	ORDINARY REVIEW	APPROVAL NO. HSSREC-2023- SEPT-023
Approval and Expiry Date	Approval Date: 22 nd September, 2023	Expiry Date: 23 rd September, 2024
Protocol Version and Date	Version - Nil.	23 rd September, 2024
Information Sheet, Consent Forms and Dates	☐ English.	To be provided
Consent form ID and Date	Version - Nil	To be provided
Recruitment Materials	Nil	Nil
Other Study Documents	- Questionnaire - Interview Guide	
Number of Participants Approved for Study		

Conditions of Approval

- No participant may be involved in any study procedure prior to the study approval or after the expiration date.
- All unanticipated or Serious Adverse Events (SAEs) must be reported to HSSREC within 5 days.
- All protocol modifications must be approved by HSSREC prior to implementation unless they are intended to reduce risk (but must still be reported for approval). Modifications will include any change of investigator/s or site address.
- All protocol deviations must be reported to HSSREC within 5 working days.
- All recruitment materials must be approved by HSSREC prior to being used.
- Principal investigators are responsible for initiating Continuing Review proceedings. HSSREC will only approve a study for a period of 12 months.
- It is the responsibility of the PI to renew his/her ethics approval through a renewal application to HSSREC.

- Where the PI desires to extend the study after expiry of the study period, documents for study extension must be received by HSSREC at least 30 days before the expiry date. This is for the purpose of facilitating the review process. Documents received within 30 days after expiry will be labelled “late submissions” and will incur a penalty fee of K500.00. No study shall be renewed whose documents are submitted for renewal 30 days after expiry of the certificate.
- Every 6 (six) months a progress report form supplied by The University of Zambia Humanities and Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee as an IRB must be filled in and submitted to us. There is a penalty of K500.00 for failure to submit the report.
- When closing a project, the PI is responsible for notifying, in writing or using the Research Ethics and Management Online (REMO), both HSSREC and the National Health Research Authority (NHRA) when ethics certification is no longer required for a project.
- In order to close an approved study, a Closing Report must be submitted in writing or through the REMO system. A Closing Report should be filed when data collection has ended and the study team will no longer be using human participants or animals or secondary data or have any direct or indirect contact with the research participants or animals for the study.
- Filing a closing report (rather than just letting your approval lapse) is important as it assists HSSREC in efficiently tracking and reporting on projects. Note that some funding agencies and sponsors require a notice of closure from the IRB which had approved the study and can only be generated after the Closing Report has been filed.
- A reprint of this letter shall be done at a fee.
- All protocol modifications must be approved by HSSREC by way of an application for an amendment prior to implementation unless they are intended to reduce risk (but must still be reported for approval). Modifications will include any change of investigator/s or site address or methodology and methods. Many modifications entail minimal risk adjustments to a protocol and/or consent form and can be made on an Expedited basis (via the IRB Chair). Some examples are: format changes, correcting spelling errors, adding key personnel, minor changes to questionnaires, recruiting and changes, and so forth. Other, more substantive changes, especially those that may alter the risk-benefit ratio, may require Full Board review. In all cases, except where noted above

regarding subject safety, any changes to any protocol document or procedure must first be approved by HSSREC before they can be implemented.

Should you have any questions regarding anything indicated in this letter, please do not hesitate to get in touch with us at the above indicated address.

On behalf of HSSREC, we would like to wish you all the success as you carry out your study.

Yours faithfully,

Dr. J.I. Ziwa

DR. J. I. Ziwa
CHAIRPERSON

THE UNIVERSITY OF ZAMBIA HUMANITIES AND
SOCIAL SCIENCES RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE - IRB

cc: Director, Directorate of Research and Graduate Studies
Assistant Director (Research), Directorate of Research and Graduate Studies
Assistant Registrar (Research), Directorate of Research and Graduate Studies

Appendix 5: List of CFMGs in Nyimba District, Eastern Province

COMMUNITY FOREST MANAGEMENT AREAS IN EASTERN PROVINCE.

No.	District	Organisation support	CFMP Group	Chiefdom	Hectarage	Dist. From CBD	Date of Recognition	Date Enter into Agreement
6	Nyimba	BCP	Luembe	Chief Luembe	293,471	50	11-Oct-17	16-Apr-19
7	Nyimba	BCP	Nyalugwe	Nyalugwe	61,888	80	11-Oct-17	16-Apr-19
11	Nyimba	BCP	Mwape	Chief Mwape	30,800.00	70.00	26-Feb-21	22.11.2021
1	Nyimba	COMACO	Mwape	Chieftainess Mwape	13,691	70	12-Aug-19	26-Feb-21
6	Nyimba	COMACO	Luembe	Chief Luembe	15,181	50	12-Aug-19	25-Mar-21
9	Nyimba	COMACO	Nyalugwe	Chief Nyalugwe	45,907	80	26-Feb-21	25-Mar-21
10	Nyimba	COMACO	Ndake	Chief Ndake	9,339	10	26-Feb-21	Not yet
1	Nyimba	WWF	Nkasako	Ndake	132	25		
2	Nyimba	WWF	Kaselekete	Ndake	357	30		
3	Nyimba	WWF	Msimba	Ndake	538	25		
1	Nyimba	ZIFLP	Mwansnika	Chief Nyalugwe	13,017	50	14.02.2020	7.01.2021
27	Nyimba	ZIFLP	Chilinga	Nyalugwe	9,328		07.07.2022	07.12.2023
Grand total(for 66 CFMGs)					1,732,083		8,691	